

*NITRATE AND PESTICIDES
IN PRIVATE WELLS
OF OHIO:
A STATE ATLAS*

DAVID B. BAKER, LAURA K. WALLRABENSTEIN, R. PETER RICHARDS, & NANCY L. CREAMER

*THE WATER QUALITY LABORATORY
HEIDELBERG COLLEGE*

TIFFIN, OHIO 44883

JUNE 1989

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In 1988, the George Gund Foundation of Cleveland, Ohio provided a grant to the Heidelberg College Water Quality Laboratory to operate an "environmental extension program" in association with our studies of agrichemical contamination of private rural wells in Ohio. This atlas represents one of the products of that environmental extension program.

The data contained in this atlas were produced through the cooperative efforts of local organizations in 76 Ohio counties, more than 16,000 Ohio residents, and the Water Quality Laboratory of Heidelberg College. In particular, the efforts of state and county Farm Bureau staff, Soil and Water Conservation Districts, and Cooperative Extension Agents in organizing the county well water testing programs were essential to this program. The efforts of individual participants in picking up and delivering their sampling materials at central locations in each county were also essential to the program. By accomplishing the sample collection portion of the study, each well owner contributed much more than just the \$1.00 fee and a water sample.

Financial support to the Water Quality Laboratory for the analytical and interpretive portions of this program also reflected cooperative efforts. A 1986 grant received from the State of Ohio, and administered by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources' Division of Soil and Water Conservation, provided the base support. Additional support to our program by industries (American Cyanamid, Ciba-Geigy, Dow Chemical, DuPont, Hoechst-Roussel, Monsanto, Proctor and Gamble, Rhone-Poulenc, and Terra International) and by foundations (The Anderson Foundation of Toledo and the Toledo Community Foundation) enabled us to expand these efforts from a local to a state level.

Valuable technical assistance during the design and operation of this program was offered by staff of Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR), the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency (OEPA), the Ohio Department of Health, and the Ohio Department of Agriculture. Martin Williams of the U. S. EPA, Office of Pesticide Programs provided county-level DRASTIC indices for Ohio counties. Helpful review comments on partial drafts of the atlas were received from numerous state agency personnel, including Jerry Wager, Dan Kush, and Rebecca Petty from ODNR; Scott Golden from the Ohio Department of Health; and Carl Wilhelm, Ed Armstrong, and Gary Martin from the OEPA. Additional reviews were provided by Karen Mancl of The Ohio State University Cooperative Extension Service; Bob Burris of the Soil Conservation Service; Callie Childress, Donna Myers, and Mike Eberle of the U. S. Geological Survey; Bradley Ross of the Knox County Soil and Water Conservation District; and Bob Bash of the Farm Bureau.

This work capitalized on the high capacity, efficient, and highly automated analytical laboratory of the Water Quality Laboratory. This analytical laboratory has been developed by Jack Kramer (Laboratory Manager) with assistance from Ellen Ewing (Chief Technician), and Barbara Merryfield (Autoanalyzer Technician). The work of June Huss (WQL secretary) in entering most of the data into the computer from the participant information sheets is also greatly appreciated. Steve Eshelman, a geology graduate student from the University of Toledo, helped in encoding well coordinates for several counties. Finally, numerous WQL student assistants from Heidelberg College helped in various portions of this work.

INTRODUCTION TO THE STATE ATLAS

This atlas presents information on nitrate and pesticide concentrations in private water systems of Ohio. The atlas consists of two major parts. The contents of each of these parts is briefly outlined below.

PART 1 - STATE SUMMARY

- A. Introduction: Water Quality Issues Associated with Ohio's Private Water Systems
- B. Program Methods
- C. Program Limitations
- D. Program Results
- E. Summary
- F. Perspectives on Agricultural Contamination of Ohio's Private Water Systems

PART 2 - COUNTY SUMMARIES

In this part of the atlas, four-page summaries of nitrate data are presented for each of the 76 counties that participated in the program.

In addition to this state atlas, a second document, entitled *Nitrate and Pesticides in Private Wells of Ohio: Technical Reports*, is in preparation and will be available from the Water Quality Laboratory in December 1989. The technical reports will include more detailed information on selected parts of the program.

Many of the figures and tables presented in this atlas, including the county maps in Part 2, are available as 35 mm colored slides. Copies of these slides, as well as copies of the entire atlas, Part 1, or individual county summaries from Part 2, may be ordered from the Water Quality Laboratory.

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INTRODUCTION: WATER QUALITY ISSUES ASSOCIATED WITH OHIO'S PRIVATE WATER SYSTEMS

THE ROLE OF PRIVATE WATER SYSTEMS IN OHIO

According to the Ohio Revised Code (Sec. 3701.344) a private water system is defined as "any water system for the provision of water for human consumption, if such system has fewer than fifteen service connections and does not regularly serve an average of at least twenty-five individuals daily at least sixty days out of the year."

Approximately 2 million Ohioans rely on private water systems for their daily supply of drinking water. The vast majority of these private systems derive water from Ohio's estimated 700,000 private water wells. A small number of the private systems use springs, cisterns, ponds, or hauled water as water sources. These private water systems provide drinking water to about 18.5% of Ohio's population, including almost all of Ohio's rural population. Since the vast majority of the private water systems are wells, the terms "private water systems" and "wells" will be used interchangeably within the text.

By comparison, about 5.9 million Ohioans (about 55% of the state's population) obtain their drinking water from 400 community public water supplies that draw upon Ohio's surface waters. These surface water sources include the state's rivers and reservoirs and Lake Erie. Another 2.9 million Ohio residents (about 26.5% of the state's population) are served by 1,200 community public water supplies derived from groundwater sources. The proportions of Ohioans served by these various types and sources of daily drinking water supplies are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Drinking water sources used by Ohio's 10,800,000 residents.

An additional important type of drinking water supply consists of public, non-community supplies. This category includes many schools, restaurants, and gas stations that provide drinking water to non-transient or transient populations. It is estimated that there are about 17,000 such systems in Ohio, most of which are groundwater-based systems.

WATER QUALITY INFORMATION NEEDS IN OHIO'S PRIVATE WATER SYSTEMS

In general, much less is known about the quality of private water supplies than of public water supplies. Accurate assessment of water quality in private water supplies poses many difficulties. Regulations and rules governing private supplies differ substantially from those governing public supplies. Private system rules and regulations are set forth in Chapter 3701-28 of the Ohio Revised Code and are generally administered by the Ohio Department of Health. In contrast, rules and regulations regarding public water supplies are administered by the Ohio EPA. Some of the reasons why water quality information about private water supplies is lacking, but badly needed, are noted below.

No mandated periodic testing for private water supplies

Periodic water quality testing is required for all public water supplies in Ohio, including both community and non-community systems. Treatment plants utilizing surface water have more stringent testing requirements than those drawing upon groundwater, and larger plants are required to do more testing than smaller plants. Testing focuses on those chemical and biological parameters for which safe drinking water standards have been established. For Ohio's private water systems, **no** periodic testing is required. In fact, Ohio's safe drinking water standards are applicable only to public water supplies, and technically, do not apply to private water systems. The only testing requirement for private water systems is a bacteria test that must be completed when the system is initially installed. Even this standard is less stringent for private systems than for public water supplies.¹

In the absence of mandated testing for private water supplies, the information that is available is largely associated with testing in response to complaints. Such information is likely to be biased towards those private systems having water quality problems. Thus information about typical private water supplies is scarce.

The large number of individual private water systems and high analytical costs

Monitoring 1,600 community public drinking water supplies in Ohio provides information on the quality of drinking water for 8.8 million residents. Monitoring the drinking water quality for the 2 million residents using private water systems would require measurements of about 700,000 individual systems. The monitoring cost per person served is much higher for private water systems than for community systems. If both types of systems were to be tested for the same parameters and at the same frequency, private system monitoring costs would be about 2,000 times more expensive per person served than those for community supplies. This high cost of monitoring, relative to community supplies, is one of the reasons there is no mandated testing program for private systems. It is also one of the reasons for the protection of groundwater resources, which provide the water source for most private water systems.

The vulnerability of private water systems

Private water systems often draw upon water sources that are more vulnerable to pollution than community water supplies. Water wells supplying private water systems are often shallower than those supplying community systems. Shallow groundwater is more vulnerable to contamination from most human sources than deeper groundwater supplies. Faulty well construction, which can allow contaminated surface water to directly enter a well, is also more likely to be a problem in private systems than in wells supplying communities.

The need for local data

In many cases, contamination of private water supplies is a consequence of the interactions of a variety of specific local factors. Predicting these factors can be very difficult, and consequently effectively addressing water quality problems in private water systems may often require rather detailed local studies. Such studies can take a long time and can have high costs.

The high cost of treatment for private systems

Where pollutants in community supplies are found to be present in excess of safe drinking water standards, pollutant concentrations can often be reduced by the treatment plant at a relatively low cost per household served. Where unsafe conditions are found for private water systems, treatment can also be introduced, but the costs per household protected are much higher. This high treatment cost is also cited as one of the reasons for stressing pollution prevention in the development of groundwater protection policies. It should also be noted that unnecessary treatment is rarely implemented for public water supplies but is probably very common for private water supplies.

Groundwater contamination: reality and misconceptions

Not all groundwater is safe, let alone pleasant, to drink. In some areas, natural geological conditions exist that can render water unsafe as well as unpalatable. In recent years, many examples of groundwater contamination resulting from a wide variety of human activities have been documented across the United States and elsewhere. Most studies of groundwater contamination are focused in areas of high vulnerability to pollution and/or at locations of particularly inappropriate human activities. Furthermore, those studies in which pollutants are found receive far greater publicity than studies showing no pollution. Consequently, public perceptions of groundwater quality very likely overestimate the degree of groundwater contamination.²

In an environment in which surprisingly little information is available on groundwater quality, groundwater contamination has become one of the major environmental issues of the current decade and will likely remain so into the next decade.³ While multitudes of studies, reports, articles, books, strategy documents, symposia, and public education efforts have been mounted, they are only beginning to address various issues associated with groundwater contamination. In the absence of accurate and broad perspectives on groundwater quality, there is considerable danger that inappropriate and ineffective policies may be implemented.

SOME SPECIFIC CONCERNS ABOUT AGRICULTURAL CONTAMINATION OF GROUNDWATER

In Ohio, two groundwater protection and management strategy documents were prepared in 1986, one by the Ohio EPA in cooperation with a public advisory group⁴ and a second under the guidance of the Ohio Environmental Council.⁵ Both documents site the potential for widespread contamination of Ohio groundwater by agrichemicals, based on the extensive use of these chemicals in Ohio. These concerns focus on nitrate, which can pose definite risks to infants below 6 months of age, and on pesticides. Both documents also cite the lack of information regarding such contamination of Ohio's groundwater. In particular, the lack of water quality information regarding private water supplies is cited and recommendations for the establishment of some type of systematic monitoring of private water supplies are set forth. At a national conference in 1987 on agricultural chemicals and groundwater protection, the lack of- and need for- **information** on agrichemicals and their impact on groundwater quality and public health was noted as a major management and policy issue.⁶

In order to gain a national perspective on the magnitude and costs of groundwater contamination by agrichemicals, the Natural Resource Economics Division of the U. S. Department of Agriculture has relied upon models to predict such contamination.⁷ In their modeling approach, they combined information on the vulnerability of aquifers to contamination with information on the use of nitrogen fertilizers and pesticides. Both sets of information were developed on a county by county basis for the entire United States. Using this approach they concluded that, for Ohio, 60 of 88 counties were potentially contaminated by agrichemicals.

Contributing to concern about agrichemical contamination of groundwater is the uncertainty regarding the human health significance of chronic exposure to low concentrations of pesticides in drinking water supplies. Part of this uncertainty is associated with extrapolations from animal studies involving high dose rates to humans receiving very small doses.⁸ Until recently the U. S. EPA had not provided guidance regarding safe drinking water levels for most of the major pesticides which occasionally occur in groundwater.

Given the possibility of widespread contamination of Ohio's groundwater by nitrate and pesticides, the many uncertainties about the health risks associated with agrichemical contamination, and the lack of detailed, unbiased information about the quality of the groundwater, it is not surprising that concern, and even fear, is widespread regarding agrichemicals in groundwater. In public meetings dealing with groundwater, the statements and questions listed below are often presented. In many respects, these statements and questions represent reasonable and healthy concern about the status and protection of our drinking water resources. Governmental agencies, agrichemical interests, and the scientific community should be in a position to provide responses to these questions, either by providing answers when answers are available, or by describing efforts that are underway to address these questions. Some of these frequently asked questions are:

1. Cropland is the dominant land use across the largest portion of Ohio's landscape. Almost all of this cropland receives applications of fertilizers and pesticides. Many studies across the United States have documented that fertilizers and pesticides have not only reached groundwater, but have exceeded safe drinking water standards. Even though there have been very few studies of these problems in Ohio, should we not expect that such contamination already exists in much of Ohio?
2. Even if such contamination is currently uncommon in Ohio, certainly traces of agrichemicals are likely to be present. Is it not likely that these traces represent the "tip of the iceberg" and that high concentrations of agricultural chemicals are in the soil and are slowly but inevitably moving toward our groundwater supplies? Are we not already doomed to see things get worse before they get better, even if we were to immediately and completely stop using chemical fertilizers and pesticides?
3. Since groundwater moves so slowly, and in the groundwater environment, nitrate and pesticides may not break down as quickly as near the surface, an aquifer, once contaminated, will remain contaminated for years into the future. Since treating or decontaminating aquifers is so expensive, prevention of aquifer contamination is both environmentally and economically the most prudent alternative. Therefore should we not attempt to reduce fertilizer and pesticide use, so as to avoid current and future costly environmental repairs?
4. Shouldn't conservation tillage be avoided because it demands the use of higher quantities of herbicides and insecticides? Does not conservation tillage increase water infiltration and thereby increase groundwater contamination?

5. Since, during low flows in rivers, much of the water comes from groundwater, pesticide and nitrate contamination in groundwater will also contaminate our surface waters. These same surface waters are used as public water supplies. This provides yet another reason to protect our groundwater.
6. State-of-the-art toxicological studies cannot predict the long term or chronic effects of pesticides on humans. Therefore, the existence of pesticides in our drinking water or foods, no matter how small the concentration, commits us to involuntary participation in human experimentation, of which we want no part. Even if organically grown foods do cost more, we're willing to pay the price so that we can avoid being a part of such experimentation.
7. We are exposed to many different pesticides at low concentrations in our food and drinking water. Even if the individual compounds do not have any effects when tested one at a time, is it not likely that, when present together, they will interact in such a way as to produce adverse health effects? Shouldn't we be concerned about this type of synergistic effect?
8. Even if the pesticides themselves have only low toxicities, their breakdown products can be more toxic and more persistent than the parent compounds. The breakdown products receive even less testing than the parent compounds. Even for the parent compounds, complete toxicological data are available for only a small percentage of the many pesticides which are used in today's agriculture.

All of these issues could be better addressed from the perspective provided by more complete and reliable information on the quality of our groundwater, and specifically our private water supplies.

AN APPROACH FOR ASSESSING STATEWIDE AGRICHEMICAL CONTAMINATION OF GROUNDWATER

Because of the concerns listed above, many users of private water systems are interested in the safety of their drinking water. We saw an opportunity to simultaneously provide a public service to these individuals, and generate much-needed information about Ohio's private water supplies, by operating a private well survey. The approach we have used, in cooperation with county agricultural organizations across Ohio, is to offer a low cost, subsidized water testing service to individuals, with the understanding that the resulting data would not only be provided to the individual participant, but also would be incorporated into a data base for use in assessing the extent and characteristics of agrichemical contamination of private water systems. Since most of the private water systems utilize groundwater, the resulting data also shed light on groundwater quality. Subsidies for the program were provided by the State of Ohio, agrichemical and detergent industries, and private foundations.

The data and information provided on the following pages reflect the results of this approach.

PROGRAM METHODS

STATEWIDE NITRATE SURVEY

Background

The private water supply testing program grew out of occasional requests from local community members to test their well water for nitrate. These initial results were quite alarming since a high proportion of the wells had high nitrate concentrations. However, we recognized that the requests were from people who suspected that they had a nitrate problem, and hence the results probably comprised a biased sample. We decided to offer low cost nitrate testing to any interested private water supply owner on a county-wide basis, in order to gain a more accurate or unbiased perspective on the extent of nitrate contamination. As part of the work program under a grant that the Water Quality Laboratory (WQL) received in 1986 from the State of Ohio, we proposed to test private well samples in three northwestern Ohio counties. Word of the well testing program quickly spread to surrounding counties and the program soon grew beyond its intended three-county extent. The Ohio Farm Bureau played a pivotal role in expanding the program from a local to a statewide program.

The well testing program was initially advertised through word of mouth from one county to the next and through the WQL's environmental extension programs. We were often called upon to describe the program prior to testing or to present the results following testing within a particular county. By the middle of 1988 more than half of Ohio's counties had participated in the nitrate testing program, and we decided to send a letter to the Soil and Water Conservation District (SWCD) office in counties that had not yet participated, advising them of the program and how to get involved. The great popularity of the program confirms that people are very concerned about the quality of their water and want to learn more about the threats to groundwater.

Sample collection

In every county, a local sponsoring agency (farm bureau, health department, extension agency, SWCD office, or some combination of groups) would contact the lab to schedule a testing time. The WQL provided sample containers and instruction/information sheets to be distributed to residents at central locations throughout the county. The instruction/information sheet is reproduced in Figure 2. The sponsoring organization provided the necessary local advertising and served as a collection center for samples. The cost was \$1.00 for each sample. The low cost made participation in the program available to a large proportion of rural residents and fostered large scale participation. The actual per sample cost for the program was much higher, with most of the cost subsidized by the state grant.

Individuals generally had several days (or even weeks) to pick up an empty sample container, but all residents of a given county were to actually collect their samples on the same day and return them to the designated collection point. Samples were then picked up by WQL staff on the same day or were otherwise delivered as quickly as possible to the lab. Samples were kept refrigerated during any storage time between collection and analysis except while in transit.

Analytical methods

The analytical methods used in this study for nitrate and related nutrients are listed in Table 1. All of the samples were analyzed for nitrate+nitrite, using autoanalyzer systems, and for specific conductance, using manual techniques. Not all of the samples were analyzed for the remaining parameters listed in Table 1. For most of the initial 6,000 samples, a 5 channel autoanalyzer system was used that provided analyses of chloride, ammonia, soluble reactive phosphorus and silicate, in addition to nitrate+nitrite. The data from all 5 channels are in computer files and in hard copy, but only the nitrate+nitrite and specific conductance data are currently incorporated into the private well data files. A small number of the initial 6,000 samples were analyzed on a single channel system that provided only nitrate+nitrite analysis. The last 10,000 samples were analyzed on newer autoanalyzer systems (Technicon TRAAC's 800). These systems not only provided results for all of the parameters listed in Table 1, but also enabled direct transfer of all of the analytical data into the private well data files.

While the cadmium reduction method that we used for analysis of nitrate+nitrite yields a combined result for both nitrate and nitrite, separate analyses of nitrite in 10,086 of the private water system samples indicated that the nitrite concentrations were negligible. The average nitrite-nitrogen concentration was 0.021 mg/L. Given the low nitrite concentrations in these samples, for practical purposes the nitrate+nitrite results are equivalent to nitrate concentrations. For convenience, we will simply refer to the results of our nitrate+nitrite analyses as nitrate concentrations. It should also be noted that all of the nitrate concentrations are presented in terms of the corresponding nitrogen concentration (N) rather than as nitrate concentrations (NO₃).

The additional analyses listed in Table 1 were included in the program because these parameters are potentially of value in assessing sources of nitrate contamination, in characterizing or identifying aquifers, and in serving as indicators of potential groundwater contamination from landfills, brine disposal, or road salt. Secondary drinking water standards have been recommended by the EPA for chloride, sulfate, and total dissolved solids, which can be estimated by specific conductivity.⁹ Analyses of data on these other parameters will be included in the technical reports on this program.

The WQL is certified by the Ohio EPA/Ohio Dept. of Health for analyzing nitrate in public water supplies and this certification was in force throughout the duration of the groundwater studies. The analytical procedures and quality control program of the WQL have been approved by both the U. S. EPA and the U. S. Geological Survey for research and monitoring programs. Details of the quality control procedures and analytical system performance are presented in the technical reports for this program. Data on storage/stability of well water samples for nitrate are also presented in the technical reports. Changes in nitrate concentrations in well water during storage were insignificant.

Reporting of results

Individual well-owners received letters giving results for all of the analyses performed on their samples. As a minimum, they received the results for the nitrate+nitrite analysis and the specific conductance, within a few weeks of sample collection. For the last 10,000 samples, letters that included the results of all 8 analyses were sent to each participant. An interpretation sheet to help participants relate the concentrations of various parameters to health concerns was included with the results. Individuals who had any results exceeding accepted standards were encouraged to seek local help and guidance in correcting the

SURVEY OF NITRATE IN PRIVATE WELLS

Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College, Tiffin, Ohio 44883

Instructions

1. When to collect: To minimize storage time, collect the sample shortly before you plan to deliver it to the designated collection point.
2. Without detaching the labels, fill out the Nitrate Survey Label and the Sample Bottle Label, using a No. 2 pencil. **DO NOT REMOVE LABEL SHEET FROM SURVEY.**
3. Fill out the bottom of this form, including the sections on sampling date, well location, use of the well, and supplementary information.
4. Remove the Sample Bottle Label from its backing and place it on the Sample Bottle.
5. Choose a cold water faucet that is located as close to the well as possible, preferably one without any type of water treatment (softening, etc.) between it and the well.
6. Run the cold water tap for 3 minutes. Rinse the bottle and cap, fill the bottle 3/4 full, and cap the bottle. Refrigerate the sample until delivery to the collection point.
7. Return this form with the label attached, along with the sample bottle, to the collection point.

Do not remove label sheet from survey

NITRATE SURVEY

27014

NAME: -----

ADDRESS: -----

----- ZIP -----

BOTTLE LABEL

27014

NAME: -----

DATE ----- TIME -----

Sampling Date

_____ month _____ day _____ year

Well Location

County _____ Township _____ Section _____

(if known)

Street Address _____

Location on Property _____

(if you have more than one well, indicate which well was used for this sample)

Use of the well:

(check all that apply)

Drinking Water _____ Livestock _____

Irrigation _____ Other _____

PLEASE SEE OTHER SIDE

Figure 2. Survey and instruction sheet which accompanied the sample bottles.

Supplementary Information

- 1. Location of faucet used for sample (e.g. kitchen sink) _____
- 2. Type of water treatment between well and faucet _____
- 3. Type of treatment of drinking water _____
- 4. Does well casing extend above grade? Yes _____ No _____
- 5. Is there a septic tank within 200 feet of the well? Yes _____ No _____
- 6. Is there a feedlot or barnyard within 200 feet of the well? Yes _____ No _____
- 7. Is there cropland within 200 feet of the well? Yes _____ No _____
- 8. Well depth (feet), if known _____
- 9. Depth (feet) to bedrock, if known _____
- 10. What year was the well drilled? _____
- 11. Well Log Number (if known) _____

Figure 2. Survey and instruction sheet, page 2.

Table 1. Analytical methods used for the analysis of inorganic chemicals in water samples from private water systems.

PARAMETER	ANALYTICAL METHOD	REFERENCE*
1. nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen	automated, cadmium reduction, diazo couple	Technicon Industrial Method #824-87T EPA Method 353.2
2. nitrite-nitrogen	automated, diazo couple	Technicon Industrial Method #824-87T EPA Method 353.2
3. ammonia-nitrogen	automated, alkaline phenol	Technicon Industrial Method #780-86T EPA Method 350.2
4. chloride	automated, mercuric thiocyanate	Technicon Industrial Method #783-86T EPA Method 325.2
5. sulfate	automated, methylthymol blue	Technicon Industrial Method #847-87T "Standard Methods" 14th Ed. p. 628
6. soluble reactive phosphorus	automated, ascorbic acid/molybdate	Technicon Industrial Method #781-86T EPA Method 365.1
7. silicate	automated molybdate reactive/ascorbic acid	Technicon Industrial Method #785-86T U.S. Geological Survey, pp. 821-825
8. specific conductance	manual, temperature compensated meter	EPA Method 120.1

*The references cited in addition to the Technicon Industrial Methods represent the original methods upon which the Technicon Method is based. The EPA methods are all presented in Methods for Chemical Analysis of Water and Wastes, U. S. Environmental Protection Agency, EPA 600/4-79-020, March 1979. "Standard Methods" refers to Standard Method for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, 14 th Ed., 1975. The U. S. Geological Survey method is taken from Methods for the Analysis of Inorganic Substances in Water and Fluvial Sediments, U. S. Geological Survey, (I-2700-78). All of the above methods have been adjusted to maximize system performance for the concentration ranges typical of water samples from private water systems.

problem. Copies of an Ohio Cooperative Extension Service brochure on nitrate in drinking water were sent to many of the residents whose wells exceeded the nitrate standard.¹⁰ Residents whose water supplies greatly exceeded the nitrate standard or a health advisory level for herbicides were contacted by phone.

All analytical results from this study are kept strictly confidential in the sense that names and addresses of participants are not released by the WQL, particularly in conjunction with analytical results. A condition of participation in the program for both sponsoring organizations and individuals was that the WQL could use the data to assess the extent, geographical patterns, and characteristics of nitrate contamination. Our use of that data is to advance an understanding of the nature and extent of nitrate and pesticide contamination in private water supplies and to support the development of appropriate and effective policies to protect groundwater resources.

Mapping of sampling locations

Each county that participated in the well testing program provided the WQL with a large county highway map marked with the location of each well tested. Using a large digitizing board, we were able to enter the latitude and longitude of each well tested into the computer and generate maps of well locations and corresponding nitrate concentrations, such as those presented in Part 2 of this atlas. We are also able to produce color slides of these maps. These maps will allow us to compare our results with other maps that predict groundwater vulnerability to contamination, based on soils, geological features, and land use, such as the county-level DRASTIC pollution potential maps currently being prepared by the Division of Water of the Ohio Department of Natural Resources. The accuracy of the sampling locations, as mapped in this study, undoubtedly varies greatly from county to county as well as within counties. The maps are intended to give general locations of the testing program that can be compared to general landscape and aquifer features.

Information management for the nitrate study

In any large scale monitoring project of this type, data management is critical to conversion of the numbers into useful and relevant information. The data flow and management system used for the statewide nitrate survey is shown in Figure 3. Manual entries into the computer system include the initial sample log-in, the conductivity analyses and the data from the participant information sheet. Data transfer from the autoanalyzers and the digitizer is automated. Computer programs have been developed to provide the various outputs, examples of which occur throughout this atlas. With the exception of names and addresses, data from the files can be transferred to potential users via a variety of formats and media.

VARIABILITY OF NITRATE IN PRIVATE WELLS

Background

A question that kept arising as local organizations called to schedule a nitrate testing time for their respective county was "When is the best time to test for nitrates?" Most of them felt that springtime would yield the highest nitrate values, either very early during the groundwater recharge period or later, immediately following fertilizer applications. Yet there was apparently little evidence to support this line of thought. Despite the feeling that spring would be the season to test for nitrates, many counties purposely avoided spring testing because they felt farming activity would reduce participation in the program.

Figure 3. Information management system used for state nitrate survey.

Sampling Procedures

We decided to launch a year-round testing program in April of 1988 to see if any seasonal patterns of nitrate contamination could be detected. Individuals who had already had their wells tested in the larger program were selected from the 31 counties that had participated by that time. Individuals were selected based on the nitrate concentrations in their water sample and on their location. We tried to select a person in every township within the county. A total of 179 people agreed to send us a water sample on the first and third Monday of the month, from April 1988 to April 1989 (24 samples). Each of these people also received a pesticide scan of their water. All of these analyses (1 pesticide scan and 24 nitrate tests) were conducted free of charge, and all necessary sample materials and postage were provided at no cost. Participants received quarterly letters summarizing their results.

The year-round nitrate testing began on April 18, 1988 and concluded on April 3, 1989. Participants were instructed to always use the same water source and collection location for the entire year and to notify us of any changes. Several people experienced difficulty with wells drying up during the course of the year, due to the extreme drought during the summer of 1988. Individuals were to collect their samples on the morning of the first and third Mondays of each month and send the sample back to our lab on the same day, using first class mail. We provided all necessary packing material (bottle, styrofoam box, and cardboard outer box) as well as prepaid postage stickers and return address labels.

The people selected to send water twice a month constituted a sample which was deliberately biased toward high nitrate levels, to allow us to focus on variability patterns in

nitrate levels throughout the year. The distribution of samples among concentration ranges is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Biases intentionally introduced into the nitrate variability study and the pesticide survey, to emphasize wells with higher nitrate concentrations. The nitrate concentration range for a participant in the variability study or the pesticide study was determined by the concentration in the nitrate sample contributed by that participant to the statewide nitrate study. Percentages for the statewide survey as of January 1988 are included to indicate the population from which the variability study participants were drawn. Percentages listed for the pesticide study are for the second round, done in 1989. Percentages for the first round pesticide survey are the same as for the variability study.

Nitrate Concentration Range (mg/L)	Percent of wells falling into the concentration range in:			
	Statewide Nitrate (January 1988)	Variability Study	Pesticide Study II	Statewide Nitrate (Complete)
<0.3 - 0.9	15	19	68.2	
0.3 - <3.0	10.0	9	13	18.5
3.0 - <10.0	7.5	40	38	10.4
10.0 and greater	2.5	36	30	2.9

PESTICIDES IN PRIVATE WELLS

Sampling procedures

Each of the 179 participants in the year-round variability study also had their wells tested for 7 herbicides commonly used in this region of the country. An additional 90 persons were selected and asked to submit a water sample for a one time pesticide test. They did not continue to take part in the year-round nitrate program. This group of 90 was selected in the same manner and at the same time as the year-round participants, and also was composed of private water systems with a variety of nitrate concentrations, biased toward systems with high nitrate concentrations. We ended up with a sample size of 259 well owners who submitted samples for pesticide testing in March of 1988. Each participant also received a slightly more detailed instruction/information sheet than was used for the routine nitrate tests. This instruction sheet served for both the pesticide study and the nitrate variability study.

In March of 1989 we decided to do a second round of pesticide testing, selecting people who had taken part in the nitrate testing program during the year since the last pesticide testing. A total of 351 people from 49 additional counties agreed to take part in this test and were sent sample jars and instructions. Again, the sample selection was biased toward private water systems with high nitrate samples and we attempted to sample from each township in a given county. The distribution of these participants' water systems by nitrate level is shown in Table 2. The results from both years of the pesticide program are combined and presented in the results section.

Analytical methods

Samples were analyzed for pesticides using a multi-residue scanning technique. The technique uses gas chromatography with a megabore capillary column (DB5) and a nitrogen-phosphorus detector. Samples are first extracted with methylene chloride, concentrated with a Kuderna-Danish apparatus, and transferred to 2-propanol for subsequent analysis. This technique is very similar to EPA Method 507, "Determination of Nitrogen- and Phosphorus-Containing Pesticides in Ground Water by Gas Chromatography with a Nitrogen-Phosphorus Detector." The data system for the gas chromatograph is directly linked to the WQL's computer and the report for each sample is automatically transferred to the computer. Details of the analytical procedures and associated quality control data are presented in the technical report for this program.

The megabore column has the advantage of providing lower detection limits than standard capillary columns but it has the disadvantage of not providing as good a separation of several compounds. Fortunately, the herbicides used in the largest quantities in Ohio are resolved reasonably well by this column. The analytical system was calibrated for the seven herbicides shown in Table 3. These herbicides comprise a large proportion of the total herbicide use in Ohio and include most of the herbicides which are frequently detected in groundwater studies. Also, all 7 of these herbicides are classified as leachers by the U. S. EPA, based on their chemical and physical properties, and consequently are considered to have high potential for contaminating groundwater.¹¹

Table 3. Herbicides included in the pesticide study and their use in Ohio. Quantities used listed in tons, and expressed as a percent of total herbicide applications.

Herbicide	Common Name	1982 Quantity used in Ohio*	Percent of total use	1986 Quantity used in L. Erie Basin**	Percent of total use
Alachlor	Lasso	3,454.0	26	1,450.9	31
Atrazine	AAtrex	2,658.2	20	862.3	18
Cyanazine	Bladex	997.7	8	300.7	6
Linuron	Linex	402.5	3	146.3	3
Metolachlor	Dual	2,221.3	17	986.9	21
Metribuzin	Lexone, Sencor	488.4	4	281.1	6
Simazine	Princep	155.0	1	27.3	<1
Total Herbicide Use		13,300		4,760	

*Waldron, A.C. 1984. Pesticide Use on Major Field Crops in Ohio - 1982. Columbus, Ohio: Ohio State University, Cooperative Extension Service. Bulletin 715. 72 p.

**Waldron, A.C. 1988. Surveying Application of Potential Agricultural Pollutants in the Lake Erie Basin of Ohio: Pesticide Use on Major Crops. Columbus, Ohio: Ohio State University, Cooperative Extension Service. Bulletin 787. 209 p.

In contrast with the major herbicides, the major insecticides co-elute with one another, or with other less used herbicides, on the megabore column. For example, terbufos (Counter) and fonofos (Dyfonate) co-elute under our operating conditions on this column. Most of the time, no peaks are present at the retention time for the various insecticides and consequently the systems document the absence of these compounds at their respective detection limits. However, when a peak is present in the position of the insecticides, we are not sure which compound it represents and consequently we are also unsure of its concentration. With respect to insecticides, our procedure represents a sensitive screening technique, that can be used to identify samples for subsequent analysis by techniques that allow more specific identification of individual compounds. In this atlas, presentation of the results will be limited to the herbicides which are specifically identified by this system. Discussion of results for insecticide detections, which were limited to a very small number of samples with low apparent concentrations, will be deferred to the technical report.

PROGRAM LIMITATIONS

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY CONTENT

Before using the information presented in the following sections of the atlas, several important limitations of this study should be noted. These limitations are listed on the fourth page of each county summary. Some of them have already been described in earlier sections of this report, but, nevertheless, bear repeating. These limitations are:

1. This report summarizes the results of nitrate tests in private wells whose owners voluntarily responded to well testing programs offered by local organizations in cooperation with the Heidelberg College Water Quality Laboratory. The wells tested were not randomly selected and do not necessarily represent an unbiased sample of all of the private wells in the county or state.

Comment: In many sampling programs, statistical techniques are used so that reliable information regarding the "population" can be derived from a minimum sampling effort. Since a major objective of this program was to provide specific information to individuals regarding the status of their own water supply, statistical techniques were not applied. Because so many individuals were interested in the status of their own water supply, we often ended up with very large sample sizes. We trust that the large sample size will help compensate for the lack of a statistically developed sampling procedure.

2. This is a survey of nitrate concentrations in private wells and not a groundwater survey. Contamination in private wells can result from faulty well construction or maintenance that allows contaminated surface water to directly enter the well. Thus, contamination of a well does not necessarily reflect contamination of local or regional aquifers through recharge pathways and/or associated groundwater movement.

Comment: While the presence of contamination in a private water supply drawn from a water well does not necessarily indicate groundwater contamination, the converse is not true. The absence of contamination in an untreated private water supply withdrawn from a water well does mean that the aquifer tapped by the well also lacks contamination. Knowing which aquifers lack contamination can be very useful in developing groundwater protection strategies.

3. Nitrate contamination can come from a variety of sources, including fertilizers, nitrogen fixed by leguminous plants, livestock manure, feedlots, septic tanks, and land application of municipal and industrial wastes. This study does not directly indicate the sources of nitrate contamination that may be present.

Comment: A variety of techniques are available to help distinguish the source of nitrate present in private wells. Sometimes only one kind of source is present in the vicinity of the well. The presence of detergent ingredients such as whiteners or surfactants, high sodium concentrations and coliform bacteria suggests septic tanks as the source of contamination. Nitrogen isotope ratio techniques can be used to distinguish between fertilizer and manure sources.

4. Nitrate concentrations in individual wells can vary seasonally and in response to shorter term weather and rainfall conditions. Observed variations of nitrate concentrations in individual wells during a single year often exceed 5 mg/L. Until a better understanding of

such variability is developed, the results of single tests of well water should be interpreted conservatively. (This "limitation" is elaborated in the results of the variability study presented in the next section.)

STUDY EXCLUSIONS

This atlas does **not** contain information or discussion of the topics listed below. These topics have been the subjects of numerous publications. In Table 4, several useful publications are listed that address them. These topics are:

1. The data bases and research efforts which support the establishment of safe drinking water standards for nitrate and pesticides in drinking water.

Comment: While we do not discuss the setting of safe drinking water standards, in the last section of the report we do discuss the health risks posed by agrichemicals, given the exposure data presented in this report and current U. S. EPA interpretations of the drinking water standards.

2. Point-of-use treatment systems to remove nitrate or pesticides from water supplies.
3. Farming techniques that could reduce potential contamination of groundwater.

This atlas focuses on the concentrations of nitrate and pesticides in private water supplies of Ohio. We believe an understanding of these concentration patterns provides an essential perspective from which to assess health risks from nitrate and pesticides, to target groundwater protection programs, to determine the need for point-of-use treatment systems, and to determine the extent to which prevention of future groundwater contamination warrants changes in current agricultural practices.

Table 4. Sources of information about topics not covered in the atlas, but of related interest.

-
- 1) Concern, Inc. 1986. Drinking Water: A Community Action Guide.
CONCERN, Inc.
1794 Columbia Road, NW
Washington, D.C. 20009
202-328-8160 \$3.00 per booklet - special bulk rates available
 - 2) Council for Agricultural Science and Technology. 1983. The Double-Edged Sword of Nitrogen Fertilizer. ISSN 0194-4096
CAST Headquarters Office
P.O. Box 1550, Iowa State University Station
Ames, Iowa 50010-1550
515-292-2125
 - 3) Council for Agricultural Science and Technology. 1985. Agriculture and Groundwater Quality. Report No. 103 ISSN 0194-4088 Same address as above.
 - 4) Freshwater Foundation. 1986. Pesticides and Groundwater: A Health Concern for the Midwest.
Freshwater Foundation
2500 Shadywood Road Box 90
Navarre, MN 55392
612-471-8407 \$.50 each - special bulk rates available.
 - 5) Freshwater Foundation. 1988. Nitrates & Groundwater: A Public Health Concern.
Same address and price as above.
 - 6) League of Women Voters Education Fund. 1987. Safety on Tap: A Citizen's Drinking Water Handbook.
League of Women Voters of the U.S.
1730 M Street
NW Washington, DC 20036
202-429-1965
Pub. # 840 ISBN 0-89959-402-6 \$7.95 each - quantity discounts available
 - 7) Mancl, Karen M. 1987. Nitrate in Drinking Water. The Ohio State University,
Ohio Cooperative Extension Service, Columbus, Ohio. Bulletin 744. Agdex 750.
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PROGRAM RESULTS

STATEWIDE NITRATE SURVEY

Participation in the nitrate testing program

The map in Figure 4 summarizes the participation in the nitrate testing program. Programs were set up by local organizations in a total of 76 counties. A total of 16,166 samples were received for analysis. It is estimated that there are about 700,000 private wells in Ohio. If so, this program tested about 2.3% of the state's wells. In Figure 4, the number of samples received from each county is listed. Since the number of private wells in Ohio counties varies greatly, the number of tested wells per county is also expressed as a percentage of the number of well logs on file with the Ohio Department of Natural Resources. Since there are only about 450,000 well logs on file for the state, the number of well logs per county underestimates the total number of wells per county. Therefore the county percentages overestimate the actual percentage of wells in each county that were tested. They are included to emphasize that the proportions of wells sampled in various counties differed substantially from one another.

The county with the largest participation was Knox County, where 738 wells were tested. That number of wells was equivalent to 20% of the registered wells in the county. For 59 of the 76 counties, 100 or more samples were submitted per county.

It should be noted again that no effort was made to obtain a random sample of the wells in any county. Participation in the program was voluntary. The sponsoring organizations used a variety of methods to advertise the availability of the testing program, often including radio, television, newspapers, and newsletters. To facilitate pick-up and return of the sample bottles, agribusiness outlets and grocery stores were often used, in addition to county SWCD offices, as distribution sites. Bias associated with economic status of participants should have been minimized by the low cost for the testing service (\$1.00 per sample).

Statewide Results

The nitrate concentration ranges for all of the samples tested are shown in Figure 5. Data are summarized for all of the samples received (16,166), for all of the samples which were used by participants as drinking water (14,478 samples), and for all of the samples used to water livestock (3,890 samples). For the entire data set, the drinking water standard of 10 mg/L nitrate-nitrogen was equaled or exceeded in 472 samples, or 2.9% of the samples tested. The concentrations in 11,063 wells or 68.2% were less than 0.3 mg/L. Concentrations between 0.3 and less than 3.0 mg/L occurred in 2,957 or 18.5% of the samples and concentrations between 3.0 and less than 10.0 mg/L occurred in 1,674 samples or 10.4% of the samples tested. The average concentration for all of the samples tested was 1.32 mg/L.

For water systems that were used for drinking water, nitrate concentrations were slightly lower, with only 2.7% exceeding the drinking water standard. Water used for livestock had a noticeably higher proportion (4.7%) in excess of 10 mg/L nitrate-nitrogen. It should be noted that the nitrate-nitrogen standard in Ohio for livestock is 100 mg/L.

Figure 4. Nitrate samples analyzed in participating counties throughout Ohio.

Figure 5. Nitrate concentrations in private water supplies of Ohio, including breakdowns for all samples tested, for supplies used for drinking water, and for supplies used for livestock.

Given the large number of samples tested in this survey, we believe that the proportions of nitrate in each concentration range and the statewide average provide a good estimate of the extent of nitrate contamination in Ohio's private water systems. To examine the extent of bias possibly introduced into this average by the widely varying percentages of wells tested among Ohio counties, we calculated a weighted average nitrate concentration wherein the average concentration for each county was weighted by the number of registered wells in that county. The resulting weighted average concentration for all of the counties was 1.25 mg/L instead of the 1.32 mg/L provided by the unweighted statewide average. This suggests that we tested proportionally more wells from counties with higher than average nitrate concentrations than we did from counties with low nitrate concentrations. This "adjustment" of the statewide average assumes that the ratio of actual private water systems to registered well logs is the same in all counties. It is doubtful that this assumption is true and consequently the value of 1.25 mg/L may be no more accurate than the unweighted average of 1.32 mg/L. Fortunately the two values are very close, and, for practical purposes, are not significantly different.

Nitrite-nitrogen concentrations

The concentrations noted above represent the combined concentrations of nitrogen as both nitrate and nitrite. The U. S. EPA has set drinking water standards of 10 mg/L for both nitrate-nitrogen and nitrate+nitrite-nitrogen.⁹ The standard for nitrite-nitrogen is 1 mg/L,

since nitrite is considered to be more toxic than nitrate.⁹ In the 10,086 samples from the private water systems where we had independent measurements of both nitrate+nitrite and nitrite, the nitrite-nitrogen concentrations averaged 0.021 mg/L. In only 9 samples was the nitrite-nitrogen concentration greater than 1 mg/L. Since the nitrite concentrations are so low, the combined nitrate+nitrite concentrations can be considered to represent the nitrate concentration in the samples. As noted in the methods section, rather than constantly refer to nitrate+nitrite concentrations throughout this report, we will simply refer to the nitrate+nitrite values as nitrate concentrations.

Reporting format: Nitrate-nitrogen versus nitrate

In the United States, and in most other countries, the drinking water standard for nitrate is set at 10 milligrams per liter (mg/L), when expressed in terms of the nitrogen present (i.e., as N). The comparable concentration, when expressed as nitrate (NO₃), is 45 mg/L. Throughout this atlas, the concentrations of nitrate are expressed as nitrate-nitrogen and the applicable standard is 10 mg/L.

General interpretation of nitrate concentration ranges

In some geographical areas, nitrate in excess of the drinking water standard can occur from natural sources. However, in most areas, nitrate in excess of 10 mg/L is a consequence of human activities. The U. S. Geological Survey suggests the following interpretation of various nitrate-nitrogen concentrations:¹²

- less than 0.2 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.21 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- more than 10 mg/L - Exceeds maximum contaminant level for drinking water as set by the U. S. EPA.

In this report, we have grouped the results into similar concentration ranges except that we have used a concentration of 0.3 instead of 0.2 mg/L as the level reflecting natural background concentrations with no significant contamination from human activities. For our entire data set of 16,166 samples, 65.2% have concentrations less than 0.2 mg/L while 68.2% have concentrations less than 0.3%. Only 3.0% of the samples had concentrations between 0.2 and 0.3 mg/L. It is clear that most of the low nitrate private water systems have nitrate concentrations less than 0.2 mg/L. In some other national studies, 3.0 mg/L rather than 0.3 mg/L is considered the cutoff between natural background levels and human impacted levels of nitrate in groundwater.⁷

Nitrate concentrations in Ohio in relation to other states

In the summary to the National Statistical Assessment of Rural Water Conditions¹³, nitrate-N concentrations in excess of 10 mg/L were found to be present in 2.7% of the households. These results were based on a total of 2,654 households selected from 400 counties across the United States. Regionally, the proportion which exceeded that level was 0.3% in the Northeast. In the North Central Region, including Ohio, 5.8% of the private wells exceeded 10 mg/L. The percentage of Ohio wells exceeding the drinking water

standard in our study was identical to the national percentage, but significantly less than the percentage for states in the North Central Region.

In a 1984 evaluation of nationwide groundwater nitrate data available in U. S. Geological Survey data files collected during a 25 year period, concentrations of 10 mg/L were exceeded in 6.4% of the 123,656 records available.¹² For Ohio, the USGS reported data on 339 samples, of which 2.6% exceeded 10 mg/L and 61.7% were less than 0.2 mg/L. The USGS results for Ohio are very similar to those of this study.

Assessment of USGS nitrate data by the U. S. Department of Agriculture indicated that for 60 U. S. counties, 25% or more of the wells exceeded 10 mg/L.⁷ The highest percentage of wells in excess of the drinking water standard for Ohio counties was 11%, which occurred in both Highland and Warren counties.

Studies in Iowa have indicated that 28% of the wells less than 100 ft in depth had nitrate in excess of 10 mg/L.¹⁴ For Ohio, 3.6% of the wells less than 100 ft deep had nitrate concentration in excess of 10 mg/L. It would appear that nitrate concentrations in Ohio's private water systems are much lower than in systems in Iowa. The extent to which these differences reflect differences in groundwater pollution vulnerability between the two states or differences in nitrogen management or some combination of these and other factors remains to be seen.

In general, it is difficult to compare data from one state to another because most studies are local or regional rather than statewide and most focus on areas of high vulnerability to nitrate (or pesticide) contamination. It is perhaps more relevant to examine specific areas within states and to respond with locally appropriate programs than to compare statewide averages.

Geographical variations in nitrate concentrations among Ohio counties

There were large variations in the extent of nitrate contamination among Ohio counties, with some counties showing very little nitrate contamination and others showing much more. In Table 5 the nitrate data for the individual participating counties is summarized. Table 5 includes, for each county, the number of wells tested, the number falling within each of the four nitrate concentration ranges, the average nitrate concentration, and the rank of the average nitrate concentration, from lowest to highest. Highland County was ranked 76 and had the highest average nitrate concentration (3.07 mg/L). Auglaize County was ranked 1 and had the lowest average nitrate concentration (0.017 mg/L).

In Figure 6, the pattern of nitrate contamination across the state is shown. In this map, counties are divided into three categories relative to the percentage of wells having nitrate concentrations greater than 3.0 mg/L. The categories are: counties with less than 10% of the samples having concentrations greater than 3.0 mg/L, counties with between 10% and 20% of the samples having nitrate concentrations greater than 3.0 mg/L, and counties with more than 20% of the samples with nitrate concentrations greater than 3.0 mg/L. From this map, it is evident that the northwestern quarter of Ohio has lower levels of nitrate contamination than most other areas of Ohio. This is noteworthy because this same section of the state has the most intensive agricultural land use, in terms of row crop agriculture. Nitrate contamination is rather common in the forested areas of southeastern Ohio, as well as in the agricultural and forested areas of southwestern Ohio.

Table 5. Summary of nitrate screening program for private wells in selected Ohio Counties.
Data from Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College, Tiffin, Ohio, April 1, 1989.

County	Total Samples	Nitrate + nitrite nitrogen concentration, mg/L as N				-Overall-	
		(1) <0.3	(2) 0.3 - <3.0	(3) 3.0 - <10	(4) 10 or more	Avg. Nitrate	Rank Order
Adams	84	36	26	19	3	2.44	66
Allen	128	121	4	1	2	0.39	14
Ashland	438	276	89	55	18	1.72	50
Ashtabula	92	79	10	2	1	0.53	18
Auglaize	112	112	0	0	0	0.02	1
Belmont	84	17	43	24	0	2.25	60
Butler	493	152	202	108	31	2.94	75
Carroll	109	72	23	14	0	1.00	35
Champaign	163	104	19	34	6	2.04	58
Clark	158	114	20	20	4	1.29	40
Clermont	85	20	56	8	1	1.63	49
Clinton	189	122	39	23	5	1.60	47
Columbiana	547	410	92	38	7	0.76	27
Coshocton	189	87	56	38	8	2.42	63
Crawford	114	84	12	14	4	1.52	45
Cuyahoga	141	116	22	3	0	0.31	11
Defiance	237	218	14	2	3	0.30	10
Delaware	159	100	32	20	7	1.96	56
Erie	223	127	44	37	15	2.36	62
Fairfield	510	309	121	68	12	1.51	44
Fayette	80	70	3	6	1	0.69	22
Franklin	266	229	28	9	0	0.32	12
Fulton	167	118	15	17	17	2.32	61
Gallia	6	3	1	2	0	1.90	53
Geauga	132	75	39	18	0	1.07	37
Greene	271	163	36	57	15	2.42	64
Guernsey	109	63	34	11	1	1.00	34
Hamilton	181	47	113	15	6	1.56	46
Hancock	226	199	15	8	4	0.61	19
Harrison	126	70	44	12	0	0.93	30
Henry	82	68	10	2	2	0.74	26
Highland	162	78	36	30	18	3.07	76
Holmes	512	278	146	71	17	1.62	48
Huron	135	79	23	28	5	2.43	65
Jefferson	260	139	96	21	4	1.04	36
Knox	738	416	195	115	12	1.46	42
Lake	63	27	21	12	3	2.00	57
Licking	464	288	129	39	8	1.09	38
Logan	86	74	6	5	1	0.61	20
Lorain	26	16	7	3	0	0.71	24

Table 5. (Continued).

County	Total Samples	Nitrate + nitrite nitrogen concentration, mg/L as N				-Overall-	
		(1) <0.3	(2) 0.3 - <3.0	(3) 3.0 - <10	(4) 10 or more	Avg. Nitrate	Rank Order
Lucas	183	152	19	9	3	0.65	21
Madison	109	100	4	4	1	0.38	13
Mahoning	417	360	43	10	4	0.40	15
Marion	68	65	1	1	1	0.22	9
Medina	182	136	29	13	4	0.93	31
Meigs	13	8	2	2	1	2.83	73
Mercer	101	96	4	1	0	0.11	4
Miami	262	176	28	37	21	2.52	68
Monroe	39	11	18	6	4	2.80	72
Montgomery	248	167	37	34	10	1.80	52
Morgan	184	46	85	48	5	2.56	69
Morrow	70	60	7	1	2	0.80	28
Muskingum	474	235	145	72	22	2.12	59
Ottawa	184	171	6	7	0	0.22	8
Paulding	331	321	8	2	0	0.06	2
Perry	156	70	61	23	2	1.47	43
Pickaway	171	130	19	13	9	1.31	41
Portage	91	53	11	19	8	2.72	71
Preble	119	75	22	18	4	1.90	54
Putnam	283	271	8	2	2	0.20	6
Richland	125	72	42	10	1	0.99	32
Ross	175	94	31	37	13	2.67	70
Sandusky	183	155	15	10	3	0.71	23
Seneca	261	218	23	16	4	0.72	25
Shelby	279	259	13	6	1	0.21	7
Stark	564	485	45	29	5	0.53	17
Trumbull	287	249	25	10	3	0.46	16
Tuscarawas	400	246	72	60	22	1.95	55
Union	44	38	2	1	3	1.27	39
Van Wert	509	484	20	4	1	0.17	5
Warren	168	64	59	26	19	2.84	74
Washington	180	75	70	33	2	1.78	51
Wayne	398	224	68	75	31	2.47	67
Williams	158	156	0	2	0	0.10	3
Wood	81	67	8	3	3	0.99	33
Wyandot	238	207	13	11	7	0.82	29
others	84	46	13	15	10		
TOTALS	16,166	11,018	2,997	1,679	472	1.32	

When counties are mapped relative to the percentage of samples having nitrate concentrations greater than 0.3 mg/L, the pattern shown in Figure 7 emerges. In Figure 7, the counties are again divided into three classes, those with less than 10%, those with between 10% and 30%, and those with more than 30% of the samples having nitrate concentrations greater than 0.3 mg/L. Note that for the classification relative to 0.3 mg/L, the percentages dividing the counties into three classes were shifted to higher values, i.e. for the class with the highest percentage greater than 0.3 mg/L, 30% or more was used, while the similar class for the percentage greater than 3.0 mg/L, 20% or more was used. Again the agricultural counties in northwestern Ohio stand out as having the least amount of contamination.

A final map showing the geographical pattern of nitrate contamination in Ohio is shown in Figure 8. In this figure the counties are grouped into quartiles, based on a ranking of their average nitrate concentrations. The general pattern of contamination remains the same.

General land use patterns in Ohio are shown in Figure 9. Comparisons of Figure 9 with the statewide nitrate patterns in Figures 6-8 indicate the lack of correlation between the portions of Ohio's landscape dominated by agricultural land use and the portions having higher nitrate concentrations. There is more correlation between nitrate concentrations across Ohio and the groundwater resources map in Figure 10, which indicates the yields from individual drilled wells from various aquifers across Ohio. The nitrate concentrations are higher in those portions of the state having unconsolidated aquifers, as shown in Figure 11. The bedrock aquifer of Devonian and Silurian Limestones and Dolomites (number 6 on the map in Figure 11) corresponds rather closely with the portion of the state having the least amount of nitrate contamination. Those portions of Ohio containing the various unconsolidated river valley aquifer systems have the highest levels of nitrate contamination and these areas include landscapes dominated by both forested and agricultural land use (Figure 9).

Correlations between county average nitrate concentrations and county DRASTIC scores

A fundamental concept in addressing groundwater pollution studies and management is to recognize that vulnerability of aquifers to pollution varies greatly with geographical location. In order to assess the vulnerability to pollution of aquifers at a particular location, models have been developed that consider the various factors that affect aquifer vulnerability and integrate them into some type of composite vulnerability index. Application of the models across the landscape can then be used to map the relative vulnerability of various locations. These techniques are being applied to large areas, such as the United States as a whole, to individual counties, or to segments of counties, in each case providing pictures of relative vulnerability within the region of application.

One model that is receiving widespread use in mapping aquifer vulnerability is the DRASTIC model developed by the National Water Well Association.¹⁵ The acronym "DRASTIC" stands for 7 factors that affect vulnerability: D = depth to the water table; R = net recharge; A = aquifer media; S = soil media; T = topography; I = impact of the vadose zone; and C = hydraulic conductivity. This model has been applied at a national level as a part of the statistical design of a national pesticide monitoring program.¹¹ When applying the DRASTIC model for assessing vulnerability to pesticide contamination, the weighting of several factors is shifted. The resulting pesticide DRASTIC index was estimated for each county in the United States.¹⁶ These same county level DRASTIC indices have also been used to provide a national perspective on the magnitude and costs of groundwater contamination from pesticides and nitrate.⁷ In Ohio, DRASTIC pollution potential maps are

Figure 6. Statewide pattern of nitrate contamination based on proportions of county wells with nitrate concentrations exceeding 3.0 mg/L.

Figure 7. Statewide pattern of nitrate contamination based on proportions of county wells with nitrate concentrations exceeding 0.3 mg/L.

Figure 8. Statewide pattern of nitrate contamination based on county average nitrate concentrations ranked by quartiles.

Figure 9. Dominant land use by major land resource areas.

Figure 10. Groundwater resources in Ohio..

being developed for individual counties for use in a variety of groundwater management and protection applications.¹⁷

Using the county level pesticide DRASTIC indices for Ohio, as developed in the above national study for assessing vulnerability to pesticide contamination, the pattern of relative vulnerability of Ohio counties to pesticide pollution is shown in Figure 12. For this figure, the county DRASTIC scores were divided into quartiles (i.e., the lowest quarter of the scores, the next lowest quarter, the third lowest quarter, and the highest quarter), limiting the counties to the 76 for which we have nitrate data. The DRASTIC index is set up such that the higher the score, the more vulnerable the aquifer to pollution. Comparison of the state map of DRASTIC scores (Figure 12) with the state map in which the county average nitrate concentrations were divided into quartiles (Figure 8), indicates rather similar overall patterns in the state. Pesticide DRASTIC scores for Ohio counties do, in a general way, correlate with county average nitrate concentrations. We would expect that DRASTIC ratings tailored directly to nitrate assessments would improve the relationship, but such scores were unavailable.

In Figure 13, the county average nitrate concentrations are plotted in relation to the county-level pesticide DRASTIC scores. While much scatter is evident, the correlation is surprisingly good ($r = .55$). Many factors would tend to lower the correlation (i.e., increase the relative scatter). Some of the important factors are listed below:

1. The DRASTIC scores are for pesticides, while the concentrations are nitrate values. The two groups of pollutants can be expected to behave in similar, but not identical ways.
2. DRASTIC is intended only to estimate relative vulnerability to groundwater contamination, not actual extent of contamination. For contamination to actually occur, sources of the contamination would also have to be available, and active for long enough for the potential contamination to be achieved. Since we are comparing potential pollution with actual pollution in this plot, we should not expect perfect correspondence.
3. County average nitrate concentrations for private water systems do not necessarily reflect county average groundwater concentrations of nitrate. Not all private water systems utilize groundwater. Probably more important is the fact that private water systems using groundwater can be contaminated directly by surface water, as a consequence of faulty construction or faulty maintenance of the well system. These factors, which are attributes of wells rather than the aquifers they tap, are not taken into account in the DRASTIC model.
4. Ohio has a more limited range of both DRASTIC scores and nitrate concentrations than are found in the nation as a whole. If the scatter is independent of the range of values, Ohio's limited range of values leads to a plot in which the scatter is large, compared to what would be expected from a nationwide plot.

While visual comparison of the quartile ranges of county average nitrate concentrations (Figure 8) and quartile ranges of DRASTIC scores (Figure 12) shows a general similarity in patterns, visual quantification of similarities and differences is difficult. In Figure 14 the similarities and differences between the two maps are directly plotted. In Figure 14, the 29 counties for which the quartile rankings for nitrate and DRASTIC were identical are plotted without a fill pattern (i.e., they are blank). For the 20 counties where the nitrate quartile was

Figure 11. Major aquifer systems in Ohio. This generalized map shows many of Ohio's major aquifer systems. Information for this map was obtained from ODNR-Geologic Survey and ODNR-Division of Water. Consolidated Aquifers are indicated by numbers, and unconsolidated aquifers are indicated by letters.

BEDROCK (CONSOLIDATED) AQUIFER SYSTEMS

Bedrock aquifers in Ohio consist of shales, sandstones, limestones, dolomites and other consolidated rock formations. Shale and sandstone aquifers generally yield meager amounts of highly mineralized ground water. Limestone, dolomite and thick sandstone aquifers provide fair to excellent supplies of ground water.

Many of Ohio's bedrock aquifers are covered by thick glacial till deposits which consist of a heterogeneous mixture of clay, silt, sand, and gravel. Where the overlying till deposit is thick and comprised primarily of clay, the bedrock aquifer is well protected from the effects of pollution. If the glacial till is thin, absent or consists of coarse sands and gravels, shallow bedrock aquifers are relatively unprotected from pollution.

Major Bedrock Aquifer Systems in Ohio

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1 - Pennsylvanian and Permian Formations | 5 - Devonian Shales (Ohio Formation) |
| 2 - Lower Pennsylvanian and Mississippian Sandstones and Shales (Cuyahoga, Berea, Massillon and Sharon Formations) | 6 - Devonian and Silurian Limestones and Dolomites |
| 3 - Lower Mississippian Shales and Sandstones | 7 - Ordovician Shales and Limestones |
| 4 - Devonian and Mississippian Shales | |

UNCONSOLIDATED AQUIFER SYSTEMS

Unconsolidated aquifers in Ohio are comprised of sand and gravel, deposited as a result of the glaciers that once crossed Ohio. Buried valley aquifers are remnants of channels cut into the bedrock by rivers which flowed prior to or between periods of glaciation. These valleys subsequently were filled with coarse sand and gravel deposits, forming thick permeable layers and are some of the best sources of ground water in Ohio.

Most buried valley aquifers are highly susceptible to pollution. They are often shallow with little or no impermeable clay cover to protect them from surface and near-surface sources of pollution. They are easily recharged or replenished from surface water such as a lake or river. As this surface water enters the aquifer, any pollutants in the water will also enter, contaminating the ground water. Because of the highly permeable nature of sands and gravels, pollutants are easily transmitted throughout the aquifer.

Major Unconsolidated Aquifer Systems in Ohio

- | | |
|--|--|
| A - Ohio River Valley Aquifer System | G - Muskingum River Valley Aquifer System |
| B - Mad-Great Miami R. Valley Aquifer System | H - Tuscarawas River Valley Aquifer System |
| C - Mill Creek Valley Aquifer System | I - Killbuck Creek Valley Aquifer System |
| D - Little Miami River Valley Aquifer System | J - Licking-Kokosing River Valley Aquifer System |
| E - Scioto River Valley Aquifer System | K - Pre-Glacial Teays Buried Valley System |
| F - Hocking River Valley Aquifer System | L - Northwest Buried Outwash & Till Plain |

Figure 12. Statewide pattern of vulnerability to groundwater contamination, based on county-level pesticide DRASTIC scores ranked by quartiles.

Figure 13. Relationship between county average nitrate concentrations and county average DRASTIC scores for 76 Ohio counties.

one quartile higher than the DRASTIC quartile, a light banded diagonal fill pattern was used. For 4 counties, the nitrate quartile was two quartiles higher than the DRASTIC quartile and these counties are indicated by a bold diagonal fill pattern.

Counties with nitrate quartiles lower than DRASTIC quartiles by one quartile, two quartiles, and three quartiles are also shown in Figure 14, as indicated in the legend. In only 9 counties did the quartile rankings differ by more than one quartile. Stark County is the only county for which the quartile rankings differed by 3 quartiles. Stark County was in the lowest quartile in terms of average nitrate concentration but in the highest quartile for DRASTIC scores. The average well depth in Stark County is 96 ft, giving it the third deepest average depth of all 76 counties tested. As will be presented later, well depth is a very important factor in nitrate concentrations. In Warren and Highland counties, where nitrate quartiles were two quartiles higher than DRASTIC quartiles, average well depths were 29 ft (4th most shallow) and 43 ft (22nd most shallow), respectively. The high nitrate concentrations for these counties, relative to DRASTIC scores, may be due to the shallowness of the wells.

In Figure 13, it is evident that the direction of deviation, i.e., higher or lower nitrate than DRASTIC, does not show any pronounced geographical pattern. Counties with relatively higher or lower nitrate quartiles are found in all parts of the state. If counties of northwestern Ohio had consistently higher nitrate quartiles than DRASTIC quartiles, and the reverse was true for southeastern Ohio, then the deviations might have been explained by the heavy fertilizer use in northwestern Ohio and the much smaller fertilizer use in southeastern Ohio. Given the absence of this type of pattern, the inclusion of county fertilizer use data will likely do very little to improve the correlation between average nitrate concentrations and average DRASTIC scores.

Geographical variations within Ohio counties

Just as there are large variations in nitrate concentrations in various regions of Ohio, there are also variations in nitrate concentrations within individual counties. In Part 2 of this

Figure 14. Statewide pattern of deviation between quartile ranking of county average nitrate levels and county average DRASTIC scores.

atlas, maps are included that show the locations of sampled private water systems and their associated nitrate concentrations for 73 of the 76 participating counties. Figures 15 and 16 provide examples of these maps. In Figure 15, the pattern of nitrate contamination in Tuscarawas County is illustrated. A band of wells with high nitrate concentrations is clearly evident along the Tuscarawas River Valley Aquifer System (Figures 10 and 11). In Knox County (Figure 16), wells with high nitrate concentrations are most prevalent in a broad band running from northwest to southeast in the county. Local officials in Knox County suggested that this region represented, "shallower wells located over the large aquifer from Fredricktown through Mount Vernon. This would make sense with the gravelly soil types and intensive agriculture found in this area."¹⁸ It is anticipated that much of the pattern evident in the county nitrate maps will reflect the patterns of soils and various features of individual counties. In particular, it is anticipated that the nitrate patterns will be reflected in county groundwater resources maps and in detailed county DRASTIC pollution potential maps, both of which are either available or being prepared by the Division of Water of the Ohio Department of Natural Resources.

It is also anticipated that the county maps included in Part 2 of this atlas will be useful in the development of well-head protection programs, in the planning for rural sewer districts, and in the selection of areas for more detailed studies of the sources and characteristics of private well contamination by nitrates in Ohio. County residents could also use these maps in support of decisions regarding investment in the testing of their own wells.

Relationships between well nitrate concentrations and well characteristics

Data from the information sheets (Figure 2) submitted along with each sample are summarized in Table 6 for the statewide data and for individual counties in Part 2 of this atlas. Well owners were asked to indicate the year the well was installed, the depth of the well, whether or not a well casing extended above grade, proximity of the supply to septic tanks, feedlots, or cropland, and the use of the well. For each question, the respondent was offered a "don't know" option. In some cases, the total number of responses does not equal 16,166 because questions were not applicable to some specific local situations. While there is undoubtedly some incorrect information on some of the forms, the results nevertheless provide some useful information regarding the relationships between various characteristics of the water supply and the associated nitrate concentrations.

In the following analyses of nitrate concentrations in relation to various characteristics of the private water supply, it should be noted that, in combining data from the entire state, locally important factors can be masked. For example, in areas of high aquifer vulnerability to contamination, well depth could be a very important factor affecting nitrate concentrations. In areas having low aquifer vulnerability, well depth may have very little effect on nitrate concentrations. By combining data from these areas, as is done in this statewide summary, the relationship between well depth and nitrate concentration in vulnerable areas would be masked.

Age of well

With respect to the age of the well, 9,057 responses were received. This represented 56% of the samples tested. We divided the ages of the wells into 4 groups. The smallest group (140 samples) was from supplies installed in the 1800's. The second group (1,493 samples) was from supplies installed between 1900 and 1949. The third and fourth groups were for supplies installed between 1950-1970 and after 1970 and contained 3,624 and 3,800 samples, respectively. The extent of nitrate contamination in the four age groups is

Figure 15. Locations of private water systems sampled in Tuscarawas County, and associated nitrate concentrations.

Figure 16. Locations of private water systems sampled in Knox County, and associated nitrate concentrations.

Table 6. Statewide summary of well characteristics in relationship to nitrate concentration ranges.

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	11,063	2957	1674	472
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	6740	1394	732	191
1800's	49	42	29	20
1900-1949	1056	229	162	46
1950-1970	2713	546	289	76
after 1970	2922	577	252	49
<u>average year drilled</u>	1964	1960	1956	1947
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	7319	1652	926	282
< 50 ft.	1266	535	427	172
50 - 100 ft.	3563	617	329	80
over 100 ft.	2490	500	170	30
SPRINGS	107	241	159	39
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	99	88	66	51
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	9325	2200	1284	354
yes	6261	1220	648	166
no	3064	980	636	188
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	9644	2394	1412	391
yes	6252	1241	787	217
no	3392	1153	625	174
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	9760	2425	1414	397
yes	1873	443	312	124
no	7887	1982	1102	273
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	9758	2423	1414	396
yes	5556	1046	798	285
no	4202	1377	616	111
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	10,330	2570	1481	397
livestock	2551	666	492	181
other	2708	765	425	89

shown in Figure 17. It is evident that nitrate concentrations were much higher in the supplies installed in the 1800's than in the other age groups. There were slight decreases in the extent of contamination as the age of the systems decreased. The percentage of wells exceeding the drinking water standard was 3.1%, 2.1%, and 1.3% of the wells in the second, third and fourth age groups, respectively.

With respect to the four nitrate concentration ranges, the average year installed decreased as the nitrate concentration increased (Table 6). For systems with nitrate greater than 10 mg/L, the average year drilled was 1947. For systems with nitrate concentrations less than 0.3 mg/L, the average year drilled was 1964.

These data indicate that the older the private water system is, the higher its nitrate concentration is likely to be. It should be noted that nitrate in excess of drinking water standards were found in all of the age ranges, but that the percentage of wells in excess of the standard decreased in the newer systems.

Figure 17. Relationship between nitrate concentrations and installation date of private water system.

Well depth

Information on the depth of private water systems was reported by 10,725 participants, i.e. for 66% of the private water systems tested (Table 6). In Figure 18, the results are summarized for four groups of systems. These four groups consisted of springs (546 samples), wells less than 50 ft in depth (2,400 samples), wells between 50 and 100 ft in depth (4,589 samples), and wells greater than 100 ft in depth (3,190 samples). It is clear from the pie charts in Figure 18 that water supplies derived from springs contain the largest proportion of nitrate-contaminated samples. Concentrations greater than 3.0 mg/L were found in 36% of the spring water and concentrations greater than 10 mg/L occurred in 7.1% of the spring water samples.

Figure 18. Relationship between nitrate concentrations and well depth.

A noteworthy feature of these data is the much greater level of contamination in wells less than 50 ft in depth than in wells with depths between 50 and 100 ft. By contrast, there were only slight differences between wells with depths greater than 100 ft and those with depths between 50 and 100 ft. It is clear that as well depth decreases, the probability of nitrate contamination increases. Average nitrate concentrations increase within the four groups as the depth decreases. Wells more than 100 ft deep had average nitrate concentrations of 0.64 mg/L, wells between 50 and 100 ft in depth had average nitrate concentrations of 0.88 mg/L, wells less than 50 ft had average concentrations of 2.57 mg/L, and springs had an average nitrate concentration of 3.42 mg/L.

It is also the case that average well depth by county explains very little of the variation in average nitrate concentrations by county. In Figure 19, the average nitrate concentration for counties is plotted as a function of the average well depth for counties. While the trend line for the relationship is negative, i.e., average nitrate concentrations are higher in counties with shallower average well depths, the correlation is very small ($r = -0.22$). It is clear that nitrate concentrations can vary widely among counties with wells having the same average depth. Likewise, similar average nitrate concentrations can be found in counties with widely varying average depths.

Figure 19. Relationship between county average well depth and county average nitrate concentration.

Well depth is particularly important in counties with high average nitrate concentrations. In Figure 20, the relationships between well depth and nitrate concentrations are shown for three groups of counties, including high nitrate counties of southwestern Ohio (Butler, Ross and Warren), high nitrate counties of southeastern Ohio (Morgan and Muskingum), and low nitrate counties of northwestern Ohio (Paulding, Putnam and Van Wert). These data illustrate that in high nitrate counties, wells less than 50 ft in depth are particularly prone to high nitrate concentrations while in low nitrate counties, wells less than 50 ft have very little contamination. The above results suggest that, while well depth is obviously an important factor in relation to nitrate concentrations in private water systems, it is of secondary importance to other factors, such as aquifer vulnerability.

Well casing

To the question of whether or not their well casing extended above grade, 13,163 or 81% of the participants responded. Of the respondents, 63% indicated that their water system had a well casing that extended above grade and 37% indicated that, for their system, a well casing did not extend above grade. The relative amounts of nitrate contamination in the two groups of wells is illustrated in Figure 21. As would be expected, there is slightly less contamination in the wells having a casing that extends above grade than in the other group of wells. The difference between the two groups is, however, small.

Proximity to septic tanks, cropland, and feedlots

Septic tanks, cropland, and feedlots all represent potential sources of nitrate contamination for groundwater and wells. The information sheets returned by participants

Figure 20. Comparison of relationships between well depth and nitrate concentrations for counties with high and low nitrate concentrations.

Figure 21. Relationships between nitrate concentrations and the presence or absence of a well casing extending above grade.

included questions about the proximity of the wells to these three potential nitrate sources. The responses to these questions are shown in Table 6 for the statewide data, and for individual counties in Part 2 of this atlas.

There were 13,841 responses to the question about the presence of a septic tank within 200 ft of the well. Of the respondents, 8,497 (61%) replied "yes" and 5,344 (39%) replied "no." Surprisingly, there were slightly higher concentrations of nitrate in supplies not noted as having septic tanks within 200 ft of the well than there were for supplies with septic tanks within 200 ft (Figure 22). Given the large number of responses suggesting no septic tank within 200 ft of the well, it is possible that this group of responses included situations where the extent of treatment was actually less than that provided by a septic tank and accompanying leaching field. However, it is likely that this question was misinterpreted by many residents. Private water system rules in Ohio specify that a well must be sited at least 50 ft from a septic tank or leaching field. It is possible that residents who knew that their well location met specifications, assumed that their wells were 200 ft from their septic tank. Also, no option was provided for respondents to indicate the presence of a rural sewer district. This, and other features of the questionnaire, will be revised for future studies.

There were 13,991 responses regarding the presence of cropland within 200 ft of the well. "Yes" responses were received from 7,685 (55%) of the respondents and "no" responses from 6306 (45%). Those wells in the vicinity of cropland had a higher percentage of wells with concentrations greater than 10 mg/L (3.7% versus 1.8%). However, wells in the vicinity of cropland also had a higher percentage of wells with nitrate less than 0.3 mg/L (72.3% versus 66.6%) (Figure 23).

Regarding the presence of feedlots within 200 ft of the well, there were 13,996 responses of which 2,752 (19.7%) were "yes" and 11,244 (80.2%) were "no." The nitrate concentrations associated with the two groups of wells are shown in Figure 24. The percentage of wells with nitrate in excess of 10 mg/L was higher for those private water systems in the proximity of feedlots than for those not near feedlots (4.51% versus 2.43%). The percentage of wells with nitrate less than 0.3 mg/L was also slightly lower for systems in the vicinity of feedlots than for those not in such proximity (68.1% versus 70.1%).

Figure 22. Relationship between nitrate concentrations and proximity to septic tanks.

Figure 23. Relationship between nitrate concentrations and proximity to cropland.

Figure 24. Relationship between nitrate concentrations and proximity to feedlots.

Proximity to septic tanks, cropland, and feedlots, as reported by participants in this study, did not have strong effects on the nitrate concentrations in private water systems. The relatively small differences that were present may have been attributable to associated factors, such as well age or depth, rather than causally connected with proximity to a potential nitrogen source.

VARIABILITY STUDY

Participation in the seasonal variability study

Of the 179 people selected for participation in the study, 152 returned at least 17 of the 24 samples. The data from these 152 wells were analyzed to characterize the variability of the wells.

Seasonal patterns in mean concentrations for the entire sample set

In Figure 25, the mean values of all the samples received for each sampling date are plotted for the 12 month period, beginning on April 4, 1988 and concluding April 3, 1989. The April 4, 1988 nitrate sampling was associated with the pesticide sampling program. The mean nitrate concentrations fluctuated as they trended downward between April 4, and August 1, 1988, and upward from November 11, 1988 through April 3, 1989. The average concentration was about 1 mg/L higher at the end of the study than at the beginning and the range for the mean values was more than 2.5 mg/L. We do not believe that the higher mean concentration at the end of the 12 month study reflects a trend of increasing nitrate concentrations in Ohio's private water system. Instead, if the differences are even significant statistically, they most likely represent the effects of weather conditions and especially the drought of 1988. As noted earlier, most of the private water systems with high nitrate concentrations are shallow. The variability described in the next section suggests that many of these water systems are rather closely connected to surface water, either directly through contamination by surface water, or indirectly through drawing upon shallow aquifers that are closely tied to surface water or soil water levels. During the late fall, winter, and early spring, many rivers of Ohio had the highest nitrate concentrations that have ever been observed for those seasons of the year. These high surface water concentrations have been attributed to poor crop growth and associated low nitrogen uptake by plants because of the drought of 1988. If the shallow aquifers reflect the influx of surface waters relatively quickly, increases in nitrate concentrations in private wells might also be expected.

When the nitrate data were arranged into groups based on the annual average concentration in each well, the patterns of variation in the groups were all different, and all were different from the pattern shown by the entire set of data. Furthermore, none matched the "expected" pattern of higher nitrate concentrations in the spring. Possibly the drought masked the expected pattern.

Variability in individual wells

The dominant characteristic of the variability in these wells was a lack of pattern. Concentrations fluctuated quite strongly in many wells, whereas a few maintained relatively constant concentrations. Wells in the same county and even the same township showed different patterns of change over time. No patterns of seasonal change could be detected in the face of the strong non-systematic fluctuations. Within this group of wells, differences in concentration between weeks were not statistically significant. Similarly, well depth and well type had no statistically significant impact on either average (median) concentration or

Figure 25. Average nitrate concentration on each sampling date in the seasonal variability study.

the range of concentrations seen over the year. The only consistent pattern found was a dip in concentrations in most wells on the August 1 sampling date. The two weeks preceding this date were characterized by widespread rainfall in amounts from 1 to 3 inches. Apparently this rainfall is reflected in the nitrate concentrations on this date. If so, the wells as a group are responding quickly to precipitation, indicating that they are not very effectively removed from potential sources of pollution from the surface. This behavior is quite different from that which most people would expect of groundwater.

The high variability of the wells is indicated in Figure 26. Here, the median concentration and the range of concentrations in wells are plotted. The wells are arranged in order of increasing median concentration, and the upper third of wells by median concentration are shown, as are the lower third by median concentration. The figure shows that the range of concentrations in a well tends to increase as the median concentration does. However, wells with a given median concentration can have widely differing amounts of variability of concentration, as shown by the ranges.

This pattern of high variability and little comparability between wells has important bearing on the significance which can be attached to a single well sample analysis, and on the concern for detecting trends in well water quality. In the group of wells studied, a single analysis with a concentration as low as 6 mg/L indicated a 50% chance that the well would exceed 10 mg/L at least once during the year. Some wells which exceeded 10 mg/L once during the year had median concentrations as low as 2 mg/L, and more than 10% of the wells which exceeded 10 mg/L at least once failed to show any nitrate at all at some other time of year. With this level of variability, one sample is not sufficient to provide assurance that a well is uncontaminated. If the first sample shows some contamination, a number of further samples may be needed to determine the range and typical level of concentration.

Similarly, programs which have as their goal the detection of trends in well water quality will not be successful unless frequent sampling is carried out for at least several years. There is a general relationship between the variability of a well's concentrations, and the frequency of sampling required to detect a trend of a given magnitude in a given length of time. The details are beyond the scope of this report, but high variability implies high sampling frequency. Programs which seek to track well water quality will probably require more samples, and therefore be more expensive than anticipated, because of these high levels of variability.

Figure 26. Range of nitrate concentrations in individual private water systems, with systems ranked in order of median nitrate concentrations. Data are presented for the lower third and upper third of the median values.

HERBICIDE SURVEY

Participation in the herbicide survey

A total of 610 samples were tested for 7 herbicides, including 259 samples in 1988 and 351 samples in 1989. In Figure 27, the numbers of samples collected in the participating counties is illustrated, along with the number of systems with detectable herbicide concentrations and the number of systems with pesticide concentrations in excess of a health advisory level.

As noted in the methods section, these 610 samples were not randomly selected but instead were selected to over-represent wells with high nitrate concentrations. The results which follow do indicate that detectable residues of atrazine are more common in samples containing nitrates in excess of 3.0 mg/L than in those with lower nitrate concentrations. The statewide nitrate results have been used to estimate statewide atrazine exposures from the atrazine detections found within the 610 samples.

In the methods section for pesticides, it was also noted that the analytical procedure is very sensitive to several insecticides but it fails to adequately separate them from one another. In a small number of samples, small peaks were observed in the location of insecticides, but they could not be specifically identified. Discussion of the pesticide data with respect to insecticides is therefore deferred to the technical report.

Summary of results

The specific herbicides detected in the private water systems are summarized in Table 7. In this table, the detections of each herbicide are broken down into four concentration ranges: 0.05 - < 0.20 µg/L, 0.20 - < 1.0 µg/L, 1.0 - < health advisory level (HA), and HA. Herbicide concentrations are reported in units of micrograms/liter (µg/L), which is the same as parts per billion (ppb). All concentrations presented in the text have been corrected for recoveries less than 100%, as indicated by spike recovery data. The lifetime health advisory level for each herbicide, as proposed by the U.S. EPA, Office of Drinking Water, is also listed.¹⁹ The EPA defines a lifetime health advisory level as a nonregulatory concentration in drinking water at which adverse health effects would not be anticipated to occur over a lifetime of exposure at that level. The health advisories contain a margin of safety to protect sensitive members of the population. For atrazine and alachlor, maximum contaminant levels (MCL's), which will become enforceable standards, have been proposed by the EPA at concentrations equal to their respective HA levels.⁹

The data in Table 7 illustrate a number of characteristics of pesticide occurrence in private water systems that appear to be rather common in the corn belt. Atrazine has a combination of mobility, persistence and high use rates that make it the most frequently detected pesticide in groundwater in the Midwest.^{20,21} Among the private systems surveyed, atrazine was detected in 56 supplies or 9.2% of the water systems tested, using a detection limit of 0.05 µg/L. The frequency of detections is closely tied to the detection limit used with the analytical system. With a detection limit of 0.2 µg/L, atrazine would have been detected in 4.3% of the samples and with a detection limit of 1.0 µg/L, it would have been detected in only 0.8%.

Alachlor, the herbicide used in the largest quantities in Ohio, was only found in 19 of 610 supplies. Six of the 19 alachlor detections were at concentrations greater than 1 µg/L. The absence of large numbers of sites with low alachlor concentrations (relative to low level atrazine detections) is common to midwestern groundwater surveys, and is most likely

Figure 27. Summary of herbicide analyses per county, herbicide detections per county, and samples exceeding lifetime health advisories per county.

Table 7. The herbicides detected in the private water systems tested. Detections listed by range, and listed with Health Advisory. 610 wells tested. Concentrations given in µg/L.

Pesticide	HA*	< 0.05 (ND)	0.05 - < 0.20	0.20 - < 1.0	1.0 (<HA)	HA
Alachlor	2	591	10	3	2	4
Atrazine	3	554	30	21	2	3
Cyanazine	10	596	10	4	0	0
Linuron	NONE	590	5	9	6	0
Metribuzin	200	579	28	2	1	0
Metolachlor N = 351	100	340	3	6	2	0
Simazine N = 259	4	252	2	3	2	0
Total detections by range			88	48	15	7

ND - not detected (detection limit = 0.05 µg/L)

HA - health advisory or maximum contaminant level*

*Barrett and Williams 1989, (Ref. 20)

linked to the much lower persistence of alachlor. This behavior of alachlor in groundwater based systems parallels its behavior in rivers, where, following rather high concentrations during runoff events after pesticide application, its concentrations drop below detection limits for most of the year.²²

Metribuzin was detected in 31 samples, 28 of which were in the 0.05 - 0.2 µg/L concentration range. Metribuzin's behavior appears to be more like that of atrazine, but possibly because its use in Ohio is only about 20% that of atrazine, its concentrations are similarly lower. The occurrence patterns for cyanazine and metolachlor were similar to those of alachlor. Linuron detections represent an anomaly within the data set. In the technical report evidence is presented suggesting that the linuron data in Table 7 may contain false positive values.

The 158 herbicide detections occurred within 114 individual private water systems. Multiple herbicides were detected in 28 of the systems. It should be noted that analyses in which the detection limits are reduced to such low levels are subject to "false positives" which could result in significant overestimation of the number of detections. A discussion of data from the blanks and spiked samples is presented in the technical report for this project. In these types of analyses, false positives are more likely than false negatives, so we are more likely to be overestimating occurrences than underestimating occurrences.

Herbicide concentrations in relation to nitrate concentrations

In Table 8, the herbicide concentrations are grouped by the ranges of the initial nitrate concentrations in the same wells. For each herbicide, the number of detections is listed for each range of nitrate concentrations, and the number of detections is also expressed as a percentage of the total wells sampled in that nitrate range. There were 131 samples from wells that had nitrate concentrations less than 0.3 mg/L. Atrazine was detected in 4 of these wells (i.e., in 3.0% of the 131 wells). The average and range for the 4 atrazine detections is also listed for each nitrate concentration range. As the nitrate concentration increased, the percentage of atrazine detections also increased. Atrazine was detected in 4% of the samples with nitrate in the 0.3 - <3.0 mg/L range, in 11% of the samples with nitrates in the 3.0 - <10 mg/L range, and in 13% of the samples with nitrates 10 mg/L.

To roughly estimate the percentages of private systems in Ohio with detectable atrazine concentrations, the percentages of atrazine detections in each nitrate concentration range can be combined with the statewide percentages of systems in each nitrate range. Such a calculation yields a "weighted" statewide percentage of atrazine detections of about 4.3%. As noted above, we are more likely to be overestimating rather than underestimating the occurrences of pesticides in these samples. It should also be noted that these projections are based on a relatively small number of samples and that statistical sampling procedures were not employed.

Only about 9% of the atrazine detections exceeded 1 µg/L and only 5% exceeded the Health Advisory level. Since there was no clear cut relationship between the average atrazine concentration and the nitrate concentration range, we can extrapolate even further and suggest that about 0.4% of the private water systems statewide would have atrazine in excess of 1 µg/L and 0.2% would have atrazine in excess of the HA level.

That pesticides are uncommon in Ohio private wells is supported by recent studies by Monsanto Chemical Company and the U. S. EPA. In 13 rural wells from Fayette County that were sampled twice (July 1985 and October 1985) by Monsanto as part of a national study, no detections of alachlor, atrazine, metolachlor, or trifluralin were observed using

Table 8. Pesticide detections shown by nitrate concentration range. 610 wells tested.

	Nitrate + nitrite nitrogen concentration, mg/L as N			
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10.0	10.0 or more
	131 samples 19 detects 5 multiple	78 samples 10 detects 1 multiple	222 samples 49 detects 13 multiple	179 samples 36 detects 9 multiple
Alachlor				
# of detects (%)	6 (5%)	none	8 (4%)	5 (3%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)	0.10		1.41	2.80
range	0.05 - 0.20		0.07 - 6.12	0.07 - 9.53
Atrazine				
# of detects (%)	4 (3%)	3 (4%)	24 (11%)	24 (13%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)	0.38	0.15	0.84	0.28
range	0.06 - 0.81	0.05 - 0.32	0.06 - 7.22	0.05 - 1.88
Cyanazine				
# of detects (%)	2 (2%)	1 (1%)	7 (3%)	4 (2%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)	0.52	0.08	0.15	0.26
range	0.09 - 0.43	no range	0.06 - 0.39	0.08 - 0.77
Metribuzin				
# of detects (%)	5 (4%)	4 (5%)	13 (6%)	8 (4%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)	0.08	0.06	0.11	0.34
range	0.05 - 0.15	0.05 - 0.07	0.05 - 0.27	0.06 - 2.03
Metolachlor				
n = 351				
# of detects (%)	5 (4%)	none	7 (3%)	3 (2%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)	0.25		0.54	2.23
range	0.06 - 0.57		0.05 - 2.02	0.18 - 6.03
Simazine				
n = 259				
# of detects (%)	none	none	2 (1%)	5 (3%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)			0.59	0.55
range			0.17 - 1.02	0.08 - 1.81
Linuron				
# of detects (%)	4 (3%)	2 (3%)	9 (4%)	5 (3%)
avg. of detects (µg/L)	0.96	0.21	1.69	2.39
range	0.27 - 1.37	0.10 - 0.33	0.07 - 12.15	0.23 - 8.96

detection limits of 0.2 µg/L.²³ Likewise, preliminary results from 40 private wells from Ohio that were included in U.S. EPA's National Pesticide Survey showed no indications of pesticides in groundwater.²⁴ The detection limits for the EPA study were not available.

Characteristics of systems with high herbicide concentrations

In Table 9, additional information is provided for those systems where herbicides in excess of 1 µg/L were found. This set of systems includes a large proportion of dug wells and springs. All of the wells containing herbicides with concentrations in excess of 1 µg/L also contained nitrate in excess of 3 mg/L, with the exception of two low nitrate samples where linuron was detected at just over 1 µg/L. Of the six systems that contained residues in excess of health advisory levels, two were dug wells and three were springs. Of the 610 systems included in the pesticide survey, 132 (22%) were dug wells and 56 (9.2%) were springs. In the statewide survey of nitrates, dug wells made up approximately 3% or more of the 16,166 samples and springs made up approximately 3.4% of the samples.

In general the pattern of pesticide contamination in wells that is emerging around the Midwest is that, with the exception of highly vulnerable settings, herbicide levels in excess of 1 µg/L rarely occur in association with field application of pesticides. One situation frequently accounting for herbicide concentrations in excess of 1 µg/L in private water systems is associated with the mishandling of pesticides in the direct vicinity of a well. A second situation involves the potential for surface runoff water to contaminate the private water system. The fact that five of the six systems where we observed herbicides in excess of health advisory levels were dug wells or springs very likely reflects the particular vulnerability of these types of systems to surface water contamination.

The Ohio Department of Agriculture recently conducted a survey of pesticide concentrations in water from wells located in the vicinity of agricultural chemical facilities and distributorships.²⁵ The program included sampling of 147 facilities during May and June of 1988. Pesticide detections occurred at 11 of the facilities, with multiple detections at 8 facilities. Metolachlor was found at 10 sites with concentrations ranging from 1.4 - 121 µg/L. Alachlor was detected at 7 sites, with concentrations ranging from 3.4 - 49 µg/L and atrazine at 4 sites with concentrations ranging from 2.3 - 35.5 µg/L. Other pesticides were found in single sites and included cyanazine, metribuzin, simazine and terbufos. The analytical detection limits used in this survey were approximately 1 µg/L. Had lower detection limits been used, it is likely that the percentage of detections would have increased.

Comparisons of herbicide contamination between groundwater and surface water supplies

In Ohio, the largest exposures to herbicides from drinking water do not arise from private water supplies but instead are associated with those public water supplies that directly withdraw water from streams and rivers draining cropland regions. For atrazine, the annual average concentration of pesticides in these rivers can approach the lifetime health advisory levels.²² Other herbicides also are present in rivers but at average concentrations much lower than their lifetime health advisory levels. Since the occurrence of herbicides in rivers is predictable and seasonal, and several treatment options are available, human exposures could be reduced through treatment to remove herbicides at these systems.^{26,27} It should be noted that only a small proportion of public water supplies using surface water directly withdraw water from rivers draining agricultural watersheds. These supplies do include Columbus, a number of cities in northwestern Ohio, and other more or less isolated supplies around the state.

Table 9. Relevant information describing wells with pesticide concentrations exceeding 1.0 µg/L.

Lab ID #	Location (Co/Twp)	(µg/L) Pesticide	(mg/L) Nitrate	Details
P42	Morgan/Union 100 ft in 1959 - cased to 98 ft - in well pit - close to feedlot, septic & crops	Ala = 1.0	9.52	Drilled
N184	Fulton/Fulton Brick laid in well pit - close to feedlot & crops	Ala = 6.1 Atr = 7.2 Sim = 1.0	8.37	Dug - 12 ft
N211	Medina/Westfield Close to feedlot & crops	Ala = 2.6	6.40	Spring
N222	Miami/Concord Close to septic & crops	Ala = 1.8 Atr = 1.8 Lin = 9.0 Mtr = 2.0 Sim = 1.8	13.36	Dug - 26 ft
70	Fayette/Paint Close to feedlot, septic & crops	Atr = 1.3	5.75	Dug
91	Greene/Sugarcreek 90 ft in 1970, close to crops	Lin = 1.2	0	Drilled
111	Holmes/Richland Not close to anything	Atr = 3.67	6.73	Spring
120	Jefferson/Mt. Pleasant Close to feedlot, septic & crops	Ala = 2.43	12.07	Spring
168	Highland/Salem Dug 1898, cased later - geothermal heat extraction system that uses large amounts of water - sprays on lawn (constant recharge) - in well pit - close to feedlot	Ala = 9.5	11.23	Dug - 49 ft
180	Lake/Painesville In well pit - close to septic	Lin = 1.0 others <1.0	4.37	Dug - 1961

Table 9. (Continued).

Lab ID #	Location (Co/Twp)	($\mu\text{g/L}$) Pesticide	(mg/L) Nitrate	Details
201	Morrow/Westfield Dug 1888 - close to septic	Met = 6.0	21.81	Dug - 17 ft
260	Madison/Pleasant In well pit - close to septic & crops	Lin = 1.4	0.06	Drilled
266	Muskingum/Blue Rock 50 ft in 1959 - close to septic & crops	Lin = 12.14	8.42	Drilled
319	Preble/Twin Casing above grade - close to feedlot, septic & crops	Atr = 4.09	7.89	Drilled - 45 ft
336	Warren/Carlisle Village 40 ft in 1956 - in well pit - not close to anything	Met = 2.0	5.57	Drilled
355	Stark/Washington Close to septic	Lin = 1.69 others <1.0	11.12	Drilled

Ala = Alachlor
Atr = Atrazine
Lin = Linuron
Met = Metolachor
Mtr = Metribuzin
Sim = Simazine

SUMMARY

NITRATE IN PRIVATE WATER SUPPLIES OF OHIO

1. Approximately 68% of the 16,166 private water systems tested in Ohio between November 1986 and April 1989 showed no trace of nitrate, i.e., the nitrate-nitrogen concentrations were less than 0.3 mg/L.
2. The drinking water standard of 10 mg/L was exceeded in 2.9% of the private systems sampled and in 2.7% of the systems used for drinking water. On a statewide basis, this percentage extrapolates to about 18,900 residences and 54,000 residents who are using water that exceeds safe drinking water standards for nitrate. Since that standard is specifically related to infants less than three months in age, the actual number of Ohioans at risk is much smaller.
3. There are large variations in the frequencies of nitrate contamination across Ohio, with the northwestern portions of the state having the least nitrate contamination and the southern and east central portions of the state having the largest amount of contamination.
4. Nitrate contamination in private water systems does not correlate with the pattern of row crop agriculture in Ohio. The low nitrate counties of northwestern Ohio have the most intensive row crop agriculture, while the high nitrate counties include regions dominated by either forestry or agriculture.
5. Within counties having high nitrate contamination, the degree of contamination varies, apparently in relation to factors associated with the vulnerability of aquifers.
6. Older wells are more prone to nitrate contamination than newer wells.
7. Springs and wells less than 50 ft in depth are much more likely to be contaminated with nitrate than are wells greater than 50 ft in depth. Wells less than 50 ft in depth show little contamination in low nitrate counties but high degrees of contamination in high nitrate counties.
8. Wells with casing extending above grade had slightly less contamination than wells without casing extending above grade.
9. Wells in the proximity of feedlots and cropland had higher percentages exceeding the drinking water standard but similar overall percentages of nitrate contamination to wells not in the proximity of cropland and feedlots.

TEMPORAL VARIABILITY IN NITRATE CONTAMINATION

1. Nitrate concentrations in nitrate contaminated wells showed large amounts of variation over a 12 month period. A wide variety of "patterns" of nitrate variability were evident in the data.
2. Some wells had nitrate concentrations in excess of the standard for parts of the year and were considerably under the standard at other times. This large amount of variability suggests that residents whose wells show any evidence of nitrate concentration may want to

have their wells checked rather frequently until the extent of variability is determined. This would be particularly appropriate if the water were to be used for infants.

3. The extensive variability in nitrate levels in wells complicates the task of determining trends in water quality.

HERBICIDE CONTAMINATION IN PRIVATE WATER SYSTEMS

1. The frequency of detections of herbicide residues in private water systems depends on the detection limits used in the analyses. In the set of 610 private water samples that we analyzed, the percentage of atrazine detections would have been 0.82% if we had used a 1.0 $\mu\text{g/L}$ detection limit and 4.3% if we had used a 0.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ detection limit. With the 0.05 $\mu\text{g/L}$ detection limit that we did use, we detected atrazine residues in 9.2 % of the samples. We can expect that the percent of detections would have been higher if we had used a lower detection limit.

2. Extrapolating our results to a state-wide basis, and accounting for the biases of our study population, we estimate that atrazine in excess of 0.05 $\mu\text{g/L}$ occurs in 4.3% of the private water systems in Ohio. In a similar fashion, we estimate that 0.38% of Ohio's private water systems contain atrazine in concentrations in excess of 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

3. Of the five private water systems containing atrazine at concentrations greater than 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$, three were shallow dug wells and one was a spring. Only one was from a drilled well.

4. Three of the five private water systems with atrazine in excess of 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ also exceeded the lifetime health advisory level of 3 $\mu\text{g/L}$ that has been proposed by the U. S. Environmental Protection Agency. The lifetime health advisory level is a concentration at which a lifetime of consumption at that level would be expected to produce no adverse health effects. Since the HA for atrazine has a 1,000 safety factor built into it from exposure levels which produced no observable chronic effects in test animals, it is unclear what the effect of consumption of water at a concentration two times the HA would be.

PERSPECTIVES ON AGRICULTURAL CONTAMINATION OF OHIO'S PRIVATE WATER SYSTEMS

In the introduction to this atlas, a number of concerns were expressed regarding the extent and characteristics of agricultural contamination of groundwater and the private and public water systems that depend on this resource. In light of the data presented in this atlas, a discussion of some of those concerns is warranted. In this discussion, we will assume that the patterns and characteristics of nitrate and herbicide contamination observed in this study reflect current features of drinking water exposures in Ohio's private water supplies

NITRATE CONTAMINATION

Exposure patterns in private water systems

In about 2.7% of the private water supplies used for drinking water, nitrate concentrations occur in excess of the 10 mg/L drinking water standard. In 69.9% of the supplies, nitrate concentrations are less than 0.3 mg/L, suggesting no nitrate contamination from any kind of human activity or from natural sources. Nitrate contamination is not evenly distributed, but is more prevalent in some regions of the state, some counties within these regions, and even some parts of these counties. Nitrate contamination does not appear to match well with areas of intense agriculture. In areas where contamination is seen, deeper wells tend to have less contamination than shallow ones. In many contaminated wells, nitrate concentrations fluctuate a great deal from sampling period to sampling period. These patterns suggest that most of the contamination is associated with highly changeable water bodies which can become contaminated or uncontaminated quickly.

In Ohio, the much feared scenario of nitrate contamination in deep, slow moving aquifers that have been essentially ruined by overuse of fertilizer nitrogen, would appear to be unsupported by our data. There is little evidence of decreasing concentration with increasing well depth in those regions which tap the deep aquifers, as this scenario would imply. The wide nitrate fluctuations in individual wells also suggests that we are not faced with the much feared "tip-of-the-iceberg" phenomenon. Instead, the patterns of nitrate contamination that currently exist, probably represent the maximum levels of contamination associated with current nitrogen sources.

It should also be pointed out that nitrate contamination appears to be much less severe in Ohio than in many states. National data from the U.S. Geological Survey indicates that in 60 U. S. counties, 25% or more of the private wells exceed the drinking water standard for nitrate.⁷ In Ohio, the two counties with the highest percentage of wells in excess of the drinking water standard had 11% of the supplies above the standard. This relative lack of severe nitrate contamination in Ohio is likely related to the near absence of counties having a high ranking for vulnerability to groundwater contamination. Only two of the 76 Ohio counties in this study rank in the high vulnerability range, using scales reflecting county vulnerabilities across the nation.

Not all of the nitrate contamination present in Ohio's private water supplies can be attributed to agricultural sources, even in agricultural counties. In a recent study in Coshocton County by the Ohio Department of Health, samples with high nitrate concentrations also had high surfactant concentrations, and have been interpreted as reflecting contamination by septic tanks.²⁸ High nitrate concentrations have been traced to septic tanks in many states, and there is no reason to believe that some portion of the nitrate

contamination present in Ohio is not a consequence of septic tank effluent. Where nitrate contamination is a consequence of faulty well construction, a variety of nitrate sources are possible. Such contamination does not reflect generalized pollution of groundwater itself, but instead it reflects surface water contamination problems.

Health risks associated with nitrates in Ohio's private water systems

With an estimated 2,000,000 residents relying on private water systems and about 2.7% of the systems having nitrate concentrations above the safe drinking water standard, approximately 54,000 Ohioans are using water that, without treatment, exceeds the drinking water standard for nitrate. Within that group, it is infants below about 6 months of age who are at risk. The drinking water standard for nitrate-nitrogen is set at 10 mg/L in order to prevent the development of methemoglobinemia (also called the blue baby disease or cyanosis) in infants.²⁹ For infants, this standard represents a 10 day health advisory level. The corresponding 10 day health advisory level for all age groups, other than infants under six months of age, is 111 mg/L. While most infants can apparently tolerate nitrate in water at concentrations much higher than 10 mg/L, other, more susceptible infants can begin to exhibit symptoms at concentrations only slightly higher than 10 mg/L. Also, the occurrence of diarrhea can increase the susceptibility of any infant to methemoglobinemia. For susceptible infants, the current drinking water standard provides a rather small margin of safety. Unlike pesticides, the standards for nitrate are based on rather extensive studies within human populations. Therefore, the large uncertainty factors associated with extrapolations from animals to humans are not included in setting of standards for nitrate. The EPA has set a nitrate lifetime health advisory level for adults of 10 mg/L.²⁹

Concerns have been expressed regarding possible relationships between high nitrate intake and cancer. Discussions of these concerns are also presented in the Health Advisory for nitrate and nitrite available from the Office of Drinking Water of the U. S. Environmental Protection Agency.²⁹ Insufficient evidence is available from animal feeding studies to evaluate the carcinogenic potential of nitrate and nitrite. For adults, dietary intake, rather than drinking water, accounts for the major portion of nitrate entering the body. For infants, drinking water is the major source of nitrates.

Nitrate Risk Management for Ohio's Private Water Supplies

In Ohio, how can we most effectively and efficiently reduce the use of water from nitrate contaminated private water supplies for infants under six months of age? Given the age range of the population at risk, programs could immediately be focused on households with infants under 6 months of age. In those geographical areas prone to high nitrate levels, as revealed in these studies or by models of aquifer vulnerability, nitrate testing could be provided for households with infants in the susceptible age range. Such testing would be particularly appropriate where springs or shallow wells are in use. For those private water systems found to have elevated nitrate concentrations, alternative water sources could be provided until the infant reaches an age no longer deemed susceptible to methemoglobinemia. Such a program may provide the most effective and efficient way to reduce health risks and should be evaluated. Possibly the program could be offered through prenatal care and services.

It is also desirable to initiate programs that would reduce the levels of nitrate in Ohio's private water systems. Such programs can initially be focused on those areas currently exhibiting the highest levels of nitrate contamination. An essential first step in such programs will be the determination of both the sources of the nitrate and the pathway by which the nitrate is entering the private water system. Given the degree of fluctuations in

nitrate concentrations in many of Ohio's contaminated private water systems, rather rapid reductions in nitrate concentrations could follow reductions in nitrate sources. Where agricultural sources are implicated in elevated nitrate concentrations, a variety of "best management practices" are available that could reduce nitrate contamination. These have recently been summarized in the Ohio Nonpoint Source Management Program,³⁰ and by the Soil and Water Conservation Society.³¹

HERBICIDE CONTAMINATION

Exposures in private water systems

Our data, coupled with that of the Ohio Department of Agriculture, suggest that the patterns of herbicide exposure through drinking water from private water systems can be characterized as follows:

1. The highest herbicide concentrations occur in private water supplies located in close proximity to sites where herbicides are stored and handled. At such sites, accidental spills and poor pesticide handling techniques can create "point sources" for local contamination problems. Surveys by the Ohio Department of Agriculture suggest that about 7.4% of the wells at such locations contain pesticides in excess of 1 µg/L.²⁵ When private water systems at such sites are used for drinking water, relatively high rates of herbicide exposure occur.
2. Private water systems derived from dug wells or springs are more likely to contain herbicides above 1 µg/L than are systems utilizing drilled wells. Springs and dug wells are more subject to contamination by surface waters than are drilled wells. Surface waters in farming areas can, on a seasonal basis, contain relatively high concentrations of herbicides.
3. Private water systems containing nitrate in excess of 3 mg/L are more likely to contain detectable herbicide residues than systems with nitrate less than 3 mg/L.
4. The majority of detections of herbicides are at concentrations below 1 µg/L and consequently well below the health guidance levels considered safe for lifetime consumption.
5. Because of its large volume use, relatively long persistence, and relatively high solubility, atrazine is the herbicide most commonly detected in private water systems. In Ohio, we estimate atrazine to be present in excess of 0.05 µg/L in about 4.3% of Ohio's private water systems. In about 0.2% of the systems, atrazine may be present in excess of its health advisory level of 3 µg/L.
6. It is probable that the low level atrazine occurrence (less than 1µg/L) described above (item 5) is in balance with (i.e., in steady state with) current agricultural practices in Ohio. In other words, what we currently see will not become worse with time because of herbicides already applied, and does not reflect the "tip of the iceberg" relative to groundwater contamination by agrichemicals. This conclusion is based in part on the rapid fluctuations of nitrate concentration in shallow groundwater, as observed in this study, and the seasonal fluctuations in herbicide levels observed in other states.^{32,33} Also, the reduced frequency of low level detections for other herbicides, also used in large quantities, that have similar

mobilities but less persistence than atrazine (e.g. alachlor), suggests that most compounds are being dissipated before reaching even shallow groundwater.

Health risks associated with herbicide exposures

Do the levels of herbicide exposure in private water supplies, as outlined above, constitute a significant health risk? Since two of the herbicides that are used in the largest quantities, atrazine and alachlor, also have relatively low HA's and MCL's (i.e., have relatively high toxicity), examination of the health risks associated with exposures to these herbicides is instructive. The following reviews of the atrazine and alachlor toxicity are based primarily on information included in their EPA health advisory documents.^{34,35}

Risks from atrazine in private water supplies

The proposed lifetime HA and MCL for atrazine is 3 µg/L. Thus, for atrazine, a person could consume 2 liters of water per day containing 3.0 µg/L of atrazine for their entire lifetime without appreciable risk of adverse effects.³⁴ The 3.0 µg/L value is derived by surveying long-term (chronic or sub-chronic) animal feeding studies and determining which species is most sensitive to the chemical. For that species, which for atrazine was dogs, the concentration for which no adverse effects are observed, is used for subsequent calculations. The effects which are "looked for" include an examination for a wide variety of organ-level, cellular, physiological, and biochemical attributes that commonly reflect various types of toxicological effects.

This "no effect level" for the most sensitive species is then converted to an equivalent (by weight) dose for a human. This dose is then divided by an uncertainty factor (100 for atrazine) to account for intra- and interspecies variability, the small number of animals tested, sensitive sub-populations, and the possibility of synergistic effects. Although atrazine is not considered a probable human carcinogen, it is considered to be a possible human carcinogen because of a positive cancer result in a single strain of a single species observed in studies reported by a manufacturer of atrazine. Following EPA policy, an additional uncertainty factor of 10 is applied. Thus, the permissible human "daily dose" of atrazine is 0.001 of the dose that caused no observable effect in the most sensitive animal species tested. To determine a safe drinking water concentration, it is assumed that sources other than drinking water could contribute 80% of the "daily dose" so the daily dose is divided by 5 to determine the allowable dose from water. It is assumed that daily water consumption is 2 liters per day, and the concentration at which 2 liters of water would contain the allowable daily dose from drinking water is finally calculated. For atrazine, that concentration is 3.0 µg/L.

Our survey of atrazine concentrations in private water systems suggests that, for 95% of the supplies, concentrations are below our detection limit of 0.05 µg/L. Assuming that the average atrazine concentration in these water systems is 0.03 µg/L, which is probably a high estimate, the drinking water exposure for 95% of the private water system users is 100 times lower than the lifetime health advisory level. This means that the atrazine exposures for this part of the human population is 100,000 times lower than the same relative concentration that caused no observable effect in the most sensitive animal species tested. Our exposure data also suggested that about 0.2% of the population are exposed at levels near 3.0 µg/L, so a small portion of the population receives atrazine in their drinking water that is only 1,000 times lower than levels causing no observable effect in test animals. The remaining portion of private water system users are exposed to doses somewhere between these extremes.

The above health risk analyses are based on the exposure data provided by our monitoring program and drinking water standards as they are currently calculated and interpreted by the EPA.³⁴ Based on this information, we judge the human health risks posed by atrazine in drinking water to be extremely small in absolute terms and insignificant in comparison with other health related risks.

Risks from alachlor in private water supplies

For alachlor, and other pesticides that are considered to be probable human carcinogens, the MCL (maximum contaminant level) is based on estimates of added lifetime risks for cancer. For pesticides, the standards are set at drinking water concentrations that, when consumed over an entire lifetime, increase the lifetime risk of cancer by one in one million. For alachlor, that concentration is thought to be 2 µg/L. The associated cancer risks for carcinogenic pesticides in general and alachlor in particular are illustrated in Table 10.

Table 10. Numbers of additional cancer occurrences in the United States in relation to three alternative acceptable risks used to set Maximum Contaminant Levels (MCL's) and various average exposures, with alachlor as an example.

Row	Exposure Level		Level of lifetime risk incorporated into the MCL		
	MCL µg/L	alachlor µg/L	1 in 10,000	1 in 100,000	1 in 1,000,000
-additional cancer occurrences in the U.S.-					
1	1	2	24,500	2,450	245
2	1	2	350/yr	35/yr	3.5/yr
3	0.1	0.2	35/yr	3.5/yr	0.35/yr
4	0.01	0.02	3.5/yr	.35/yr	0.035/yr
U.S. population = 245,000,000					
U.S. Cancer Deaths per year (1987) = 483,000					
U.S. Cancer, new cases per year (1987) = 965,000					

If the drinking water of the entire United States population (245,000,000) were to contain a carcinogenic pesticide at its MCL level, and the MCL was calculated to increase cancer risks by one in 10,000, one in 100,000 or one in 1,000,000 then the number of additional cancer cases in the United States are shown in Row 1. These additional cases range from 24,500 to 245, depending on the added risk level used to set the standard. For pesticides such as alachlor, the permissible added lifetime risk is one in 1,000,000 so the estimated increase in cancer cases would be 245. However, these reflect the total number of cancers that would develop over a 70 year (lifetime) period. The numbers in Row 2 illustrate the additional cancers per year estimated to occur in the United States if all of our drinking water supplies contained a pesticide at its MCL concentration. These values range from 350

to 3.5. If the average pesticide concentration is equal to 1/10 of its MCL standard, then the number of additional cases of cancer per year would range from 35 to 0.35 (Row 3), depending on the figure used to calculate acceptable risks. If the average concentrations are 1/100 of the MCL, additional cases of cancer would range from 3.5 to 0.35 (Row 4).

The average alachlor concentration in the 19 samples with alachlor detections was 1.36 µg/L. If we assume that, for the 591 samples where alachlor was below our detection limit of 0.05 µg/L, the alachlor concentration was actually at 0.025 µg/L, then the average alachlor concentration among the surveyed private water systems would be 0.07 µg/L. If that level of alachlor were to continue to be present at that concentration for the 2,000,000 Ohio residents using private water supplies, and the alachlor cancer risks are accurate, one could expect one additional cancer case every 1,000 years among the 2,000,000 users as a result of alachlor contamination in private water systems.

The above illustrations are based on alachlor exposure data, as monitored in these studies, and current EPA procedures for setting water quality standards for carcinogenic pesticides. In a League of Woman Voters Education Fund publication entitled *Safety on Tap: A Citizen's Drinking Water Handbook*, a section written by the Natural Resources Defense Council cites the figures in Row 1 of Table 10, and concludes these values represent unacceptable risks to the American public.⁸ The Natural Resources Defense Council does not present the data in the form of "per year" additional cases, nor do they recognize that average exposures are at least 10 to 100 fold lower than the MCL values set for drinking water exposures. Consequently, we believe the figures cited by the Natural Resources Defense Council grossly exaggerate the role of pesticides in causing cancer.

Risks from combinations of pesticides in private water supplies

It should be noted that the risks from atrazine and alachlor, as described above, very likely represent the greatest risks from individual pesticides used in Ohio. These pesticides have the highest concentrations and also have the greatest relative toxicity. While other herbicides are occasionally detected in private water systems, none have been detected at concentrations in excess of their HA or MCL values. It is likely that for Ohio, atrazine and alachlor represent the bulk of the risks posed by herbicides in private water supplies. Given the herbicide exposures observed in these studies, the drinking water standards that have been developed by the U. S. EPA for these compound, and the application of these standards in Ohio, it appears that the "iceberg" of human health risks posed by herbicide contamination in private water supplies is more like an "icecube."

Because the risks are so small, the effects are also uncertain. It is essential that groups of individuals be monitored closely, who, by virtue of occupation or location of residence, receive pesticide exposures in excess of average exposure. Through such research, as well as other advances in the science of risk assessment, the uncertainty currently accompanying the establishment of drinking water standards can be reduced.

Pesticide risk management programs

Even though the human health risks posed by contamination of private water supplies appear to be very small, these risks can and should be reduced. Many studies now indicate that "point sources" account for the highest concentrations of herbicides in private water systems. Programs to improve pesticide handling from point of manufacture to application in fields are being developed and implemented. Guidelines for reducing agricultural nonpoint pollution already include many "best management practices" for reducing pesticide contamination of both surface water and groundwater.^{30,31} Programs to speed adoption of

such practices need to be supported, particularly in areas that are especially vulnerable to aquifer contamination by pesticides.

As understanding improves regarding the occurrence of herbicides in private water systems and groundwater, private water systems with high herbicide concentrations may be located more efficiently and local remedial steps taken. Several procedures are available for removing pesticide from drinking water. Local "well head protection programs" for private water supplies may, in some locations, be appropriate. In Ohio, the greatest gains in reducing current exposures to pesticides could be achieved through seasonal treatment at the relatively small number of public water supplies that withdraw water directly from rivers draining agricultural watersheds.²⁷

Research in the area of "sustainable agriculture" may lead to the development of economically viable alternative production systems that involve greatly reduced applications of pesticides. While such research should proceed, in Ohio it should not base much of its justification on reduced health risks associated with pesticide contamination of drinking water supplies. As noted above, the current risks are very small, and many options are already available to make them even smaller.

REFERENCES

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- ¹Letter from Ohio Department of Health to All Certified Bacteriological Laboratories. July 30, 1987. Contains bacteriological standards for public and private water supplies.
- ²Lehr, J.H. 1989. Factual, Fictional, and Ethical Impacts on Ground-Water Contamination in the United States. *Ground Water* 27:2-11.
- ³Conservation Foundation. 1987. *State of the Environment: A View Toward the Nineties*. Washington D.C.
- ⁴State of Ohio. 1986. *Ohio Ground Water Protection and Management Strategy*. Columbus, Ohio: Ohio Environmental Protection Agency. 67 p.
- ⁵Ohio Environmental Council. 1986. *Buried Treasure at Risk: A Strategy to Protect Ohio's Groundwater*. Executive Summary. Columbus, Ohio. 26 p.
- ⁶Freshwater Foundation. 1987. *Agricultural Chemicals and Groundwater Protection: Suggested Directions for Consideration and Action*. Recommendations from the conference. Agricultural Chemicals and Groundwater Protection: Emerging Management and Policy, St. Paul, MN. 10 p.
- ⁷Nielsen, E.G. and L.K. Lee. 1987. The Magnitude and Costs of Groundwater Contamination From Agricultural Chemicals: A National Perspective. Washington D.C.: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Economic Research Service. 54 p.
- ⁸League of Women Voters Education Fund. 1987. *Safety on Tap: A Citizen's Drinking Water Handbook*. Washington D.C.: League of Women Voters of the U.S. Publication 840. 68 p.
- ⁹Environmental Protection Agency. 1988. *National Primary Drinking Water Regulations; (and following editions)*. 40 CFR Parts 141 and 142. Washington D.C.: EPA Office of Water.
- ¹⁰Mancl, K. 1987. *Nitrate in Drinking Water*. Columbus, Ohio: The Ohio State University, Cooperative Extension Service. Bulletin 744. 7 p.
- ¹¹Environmental Protection Agency. 1987. *National Pesticide Survey: Summary of Statistical Design*. Washington D.C.: U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Publication DU-87-A194.
- ¹²Madison, R.J. and J.O. Brunett. 1984. *Overview of the Occurrence of Nitrate in Ground Water of the United States*. U.S. Geological Survey, National Water Summary 1984 -- Water-Quality Issues pp. 93-105.
- ¹³Francis, J.D., et al. *National Statistical Assessment of Rural Water Conditions - Executive Summary*. Department of Rural Sociology, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY. Report prepared for the Office of Drinking Water, U. S. Environmental Protection Agency. 21 p.

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- ¹⁴Hallberg, G.R. 1986. "Nitrates in Iowa Groundwater". Chapter 3 In: *Rural Groundwater Contamination*. D'Itri, F.M. and Wolfson, L.G. Chelsea, MI: Lewis Publishers, Inc.
- ¹⁵Aller, L., T. Bennett, J. Lehr, R. Petty, and G. Hackett. 1987. *DRASTIC: A standardized system for evaluating ground water pollution potential using hydrogeologic settings*. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. EPA/600/2-87/035. Dublin, Ohio: National Well Water Association.
- ¹⁶Alexander, W.J., S.K. Liddle, R.E. Mason, and W.B. Yeager. 1985. *Ground-water vulnerability assessment in support of the first stage of the National Pesticide Survey*. Prepared for the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, contract no. 68-01-6646. Research Triangle Park, North Carolina: Research Triangle Institute.
- ¹⁷Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Division of Water Programs. Miscellaneous publication. Columbus, Ohio.
- ¹⁸Letter from Bradley Ross, District Administrator for Knox Soil and Water Conservation District to David B. Baker, Director Water Quality Laboratory. May 9, 1989.
- ¹⁹U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. 1989. Drinking Water Regulations and Health Advisories. (Draft 4/5/89). Washington D.C.: U.S. EPA, Office of Drinking Water.
- ²⁰Barrett, M.R. and W.M. Williams. 1989. The Occurrence of Atrazine in Ground Water as a Result of Agricultural Use. In Proceedings from national conference, Pesticides in Terrestrial and Aquatic Environments. Blacksburg, Virginia. In press.
- ²¹LeMasters, G. and D.J. Doyle. 1989. Grade A Dairy Farm Well Water Quality Survey. Madison, WI. 36 p.
- ²²Baker, D.B. and R.P. Richards. 1989. Herbicide Concentration Patterns in Rivers Draining Intensively Cultivated Farmlands of Northwestern Ohio. In Proceedings from national conference, Pesticides in Terrestrial and Aquatic Environments. Blacksburg, Virginia. In press.
- ²³Letter and report from Andrew J. Klein, Monsanto Agricultural Company, to Robert Wulfhorst, Ohio Department of Agriculture. April 19, 1988.
- ²⁴Ohio Environmental Protection Agency. 1988. *Environment Ohio*, Volume 2, Issue 4.
- ²⁵Ohio Department of Agriculture. *ODA Pesticides in Groundwater Survey* (Preliminary Summary). Reynoldsburg, Ohio.
- ²⁶Miltner, R.J., D.B. Baker, T.S. Speth, and C.A. Fronk. 1989. Treatment of Seasonal Pesticides in Surface Waters. *American Water Works Association Journal* 81:43-52.
- ²⁷Richards, R.P. and D.B. Baker. 1989. Potential for Reducing Human Exposures to Herbicides by Selective Treatment of Storm Runoff Water at Municipal Water Supplies. In Proceedings from national conference, Pesticides in Terrestrial and Aquatic Environments. Blacksburg, Virginia. In press.
- ²⁸Lane, R.I. 1989. *Effects of Domestic Sewage on Ground-water Quality in Two Subdivision, Coshocton County, Ohio*. Columbus, Ohio: Department of Health.

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- ²⁹U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. March 31, 1987. Health Advisory: Nitrate/Nitrite. U.S. EPA, Office of Drinking Water. 18 p.
- ³⁰Ohio Department of Natural Resources. 1988. *Ohio Nonpoint Source Management Program*. Columbus, Ohio. 545 p.
- ³¹Soil and Water Conservation Society. *A Guide for Safe, Profitable Fertilizer and Pesticide Use From SWCS*. Ankeny, Iowa.
- ³²McKenna, D.P., S.F.J. Chou, R.A. Griffin, J. Valkenburg, L.L. Spencer, and J.L. Gilkeson. 1988. *Assessment of the Occurrence of Agricultural Chemicals in Groundwater in a Part of Mason County, Illinois*. Proceedings of a Conference, March 1988. Dublin, Ohio: National Water Well Association. pp. 389-406.
- ³³Klaseus, T. 1987. *Minnesota Pesticide Monitoring Surveys: Interim Report*. Proceedings of a Conference, October 1986. Pesticides and Groundwater: A Health Concern for the Midwest. Navarre, Minnesota: Freshwater Foundation. pp. 137-160.
- ³⁴U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. September 1987. Health Advisory: Atrazine. U.S. EPA, Office of Drinking Water. 21 p.
- ³⁵U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. March 31, 1987. Health Advisory: Alachlor. U.S. EPA, Office of Drinking Water. 15 p.

*NITRATE AND PESTICIDES
IN PRIVATE WELLS
OF OHIO:
A STATE ATLAS*

PART 2 COUNTY SUMMARIES

DAVID B. BAKER, LAURA K. WALLRABENSTEIN, R. PETER RICHARDS, & NANCY L. CREAMER

*THE WATER QUALITY LABORATORY,
HEIDELBERG COLLEGE*

TIFFIN, OHIO 44883

JUNE 1989

ADAMS COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Adams County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Adams County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Adams County (average 2.44 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

ADAMS COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

ADAMS COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	36	26	19	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	22	5	4	1
1800's	0	1	0	0
1900-1949	1	0	0	0
1950-1970	9	2	4	1
after 1970	12	2	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1972	1945	1966	1952
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	26	12	6	1
< 50 ft.	7	10	4	0
50 - 100 ft.	17	2	2	1
over 100 ft.	2	0	0	0
SPRINGS	2	4	9	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	71	33	41	70
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	29	21	13	1
yes	18	8	3	1
no	11	13	10	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	32	23	18	2
yes	17	7	7	1
no	15	16	11	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	33	24	18	2
yes	3	5	3	1
no	30	19	15	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	33	24	18	2
yes	11	7	9	2
no	22	17	9	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	30	18	18	3
livestock	7	9	9	2
other	17	10	5	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Adams County

84 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.44 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BRATTON	5	0	4	0	9
BRUSHCREEK	5	2	0	0	7
FRANKLIN	11	3	1	1	16
GREEN	4	0	0	0	4
JEFFERSON	0	1	0	0	1
LIBERTY	1	4	1	0	6
MEIGS	6	1	2	0	9
MONROE	0	1	1	0	2
OLIVER	0	0	1	0	1
SCOTT	0	2	5	1	8
SPRIGG	1	0	2	0	3
TIFFIN	1	6	0	0	7
WAYNE	2	2	1	1	6
WINCHESTER	0	4	1	0	5

ALLEN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Allen County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Allen County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Allen County (average 0.39 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

ALLEN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

ALLEN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	121	4	1	2
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	66	1	1	2
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	10	1	1	1
1950-1970	26	0	0	0
after 1970	29	0	0	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1962	1940	1947	1952
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	68	2	1	2
< 50 ft.	29	2	0	2
50 - 100 ft.	25	0	1	0
over 100 ft.	14	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	73	39	66	23
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	98	2	1	2
yes	66	0	1	0
no	32	2	0	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	101	3	1	2
yes	63	2	1	2
no	38	1	0	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	101	3	1	2
yes	19	1	0	0
no	82	2	1	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	100	3	1	2
yes	78	2	0	1
no	22	1	1	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	117	3	1	2
livestock	38	0	0	0
other	12	1	0	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Allen County

128 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.39 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
AMANDA	15	1	0	0	16
AMERICAN	10	0	0	0	10
AUGLAIZE	16	0	0	1	17
BATH	4	0	1	0	5
JACKSON	10	0	0	0	10
MARION	15	1	0	0	16
MONROE	16	2	0	0	18
PERRY	6	0	0	0	6
RICHLAND	3	0	0	0	3
SCIPIO	4	0	0	0	4
SHAWNEE	9	0	0	0	9
SPENCER	6	0	0	0	6
SUGARCREEK	6	0	0	1	7

ASHLAND COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED FEBRUARY 1989

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Ashland County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Ashland County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Ashland County (average 1.72 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

ASHLAND COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

ASHLAND COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	276	89	55	18
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	171	34	21	4
1800's	1	1	0	0
1900-1949	20	6	4	0
1950-1970	71	12	8	2
after 1970	79	15	9	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1967	1962	1963	1967
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	194	46	30	9
< 50 ft.	24	11	8	5
50 - 100 ft.	101	15	9	3
over 100 ft.	69	20	13	1
SPRINGS	4	13	9	5
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	100	105	105	61
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	237	61	40	10
yes	164	32	23	7
no	73	29	17	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	241	75	41	14
yes	157	46	23	12
no	84	29	18	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	245	73	43	14
yes	64	19	15	7
no	181	54	28	7
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	246	75	43	14
yes	143	44	29	12
no	103	31	14	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	253	76	46	14
livestock	105	35	29	11
other	75	18	11	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Ashland County

438 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.72 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	1	0	0	3
CLEAR CREEK	13	0	1	0	14
GREEN	18	16	12	3	49
HANOVER	19	6	6	2	33
JACKSON	10	0	1	0	11
LAKE	6	10	9	3	28
MIFFLIN	11	3	0	0	14
MILTON	44	6	0	0	50
MOHICAN	13	7	2	1	23
MONTGOMERY	50	14	1	0	65
ORANGE	35	3	6	5	49
PERRY	24	5	3	2	34
RUGGLES	3	3	1	0	7
SULLIVAN	2	1	1	0	4
TROY	5	4	0	0	9
UNION	1	0	0	0	1
VERMILLION	20	10	12	2	44

ASHTABULA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Ashtabula County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Ashtabula County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Ashtabula County (average 0.53 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

ASHTABULA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

ASHTABULA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	79	10	2	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	51	10	0	1
1800's	1	1	0	0
1900-1949	12	2	0	1
1950-1970	20	3	0	0
after 1970	18	4	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1958	1954	0	1944
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	58	10	0	0
< 50 ft.	27	5	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	27	5	0	0
over 100 ft.	4	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	57	49	0	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	63	9	1	1
yes	45	7	0	1
no	18	2	1	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	66	10	2	1
yes	39	4	1	0
no	27	6	1	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	68	10	2	1
yes	14	2	0	0
no	54	8	2	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	69	10	2	1
yes	38	5	2	0
no	31	5	0	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	73	10	2	1
livestock	12	1	0	1
other	19	1	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Ashtabula County

92 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.53 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
AUSTINBURG	5	1	0	0	6
CHERRY VALLE	1	0	0	0	1
COLEBROOK	6	0	1	0	7
GENEVA	2	0	0	0	2
HARPERSFIELD	7	1	0	0	8
HARTSGROVE	7	0	0	0	7
JEFFERSON	3	0	0	0	3
LENOX	10	1	0	0	11
MONROE	4	2	0	0	6
MORGAN	1	0	0	0	1
NEW LYME	7	0	0	0	7
ORWELL	3	1	1	0	5
PIERPONT	2	1	0	0	3
PLYMOUTH	0	0	0	1	1
ROCK CREEK	1	0	0	0	1
ROME	4	0	0	0	4
SHEFFIELD	2	0	0	0	2
TRUMBULL	2	1	0	0	3
WAYNE	5	0	0	0	5
WILLIAMSFIEL	4	2	0	0	6
WINDSOR	3	0	0	0	3

AUGLAIZE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Auglaize County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Auglaize County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Auglaize County
(average 0.02 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested
(average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

AUGLAIZE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

AUGLAIZE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	112	0	0	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	52	0	0	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	13	0	0	0
1950-1970	16	0	0	0
after 1970	23	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	0	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	65	0	0	0
< 50 ft.	7	0	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	34	0	0	0
over 100 ft.	24	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	97	0	0	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	95	0	0	0
yes	65	0	0	0
no	30	0	0	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	95	0	0	0
yes	76	0	0	0
no	19	0	0	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	96	0	0	0
yes	39	0	0	0
no	57	0	0	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	96	0	0	0
yes	81	0	0	0
no	15	0	0	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	107	0	0	0
livestock	50	0	0	0
other	11	0	0	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Auglaize County

112 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.02 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
CLAY	4	0	0	0	4
DUCHOUQUET	11	0	0	0	11
GERMAN	5	0	0	0	5
GOSHEN	2	0	0	0	2
JACKSON	18	0	0	0	18
LOGAN	1	0	0	0	1
MOULTON	4	0	0	0	4
NOBLE	17	0	0	0	17
PUSHETA	4	0	0	0	4
SALEM	9	0	0	0	9
ST. MARY'S	18	0	0	0	18
UNION	4	0	0	0	4
WASHINGTON	11	0	0	0	11
WAYNE	2	0	0	0	2

BELMONT COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APRIL 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Belmont County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Belmont County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Belmont County (average 2.25 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

BELMONT COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

BELMONT COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	17	43	24	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	10	20	9	0
1800's	0	1	1	0
1900-1949	0	6	1	0
1950-1970	6	6	2	0
after 1970	4	7	5	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1966	1951	1959	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	11	25	11	0
< 50 ft.	2	8	3	0
50 - 100 ft.	6	12	5	0
over 100 ft.	3	5	3	0
SPRINGS	0	5	2	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	80	73	73	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	16	32	19	0
yes	6	20	9	0
no	10	12	10	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	16	34	19	0
yes	5	19	11	0
no	11	15	8	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	16	34	19	0
yes	0	3	10	0
no	16	31	9	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	16	31	19	0
yes	3	6	5	0
no	13	25	14	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	13	37	21	0
livestock	3	2	8	0
other	5	14	4	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Belmont County

84 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.25 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
COLERAIN	3	6	2	0	11
GOSHEN	0	7	2	0	9
MEAD	0	2	0	0	2
OXFORD	2	0	0	0	2
PEASE	1	5	1	0	7
PIEDMONT	1	0	0	0	1
PULTNEY	1	5	0	0	6
RICHLAND	1	4	5	0	10
SMITH	2	4	10	0	16
SOMERSET	2	5	0	0	7
UNION	0	1	2	0	3
WARREN	2	1	1	0	4
WASHINGTON	1	1	0	0	2
WAYNE	1	2	1	0	4

BUTLER COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Butler County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Butler County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Butler County (average 2.94 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

BUTLER COUNTY

Nitrate as N

BUTLER COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	152	202	108	31
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	95	90	56	17
1800's	4	4	6	1
1900-1949	22	22	9	6
1950-1970	35	39	29	6
after 1970	34	25	12	4
<u>average year drilled</u>	1956	1954	1947	1951
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	101	103	65	22
< 50 ft.	38	45	32	12
50 - 100 ft.	43	51	31	10
over 100 ft.	20	7	2	0
SPRINGS	3	8	3	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	70	54	53	43
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	124	143	85	28
yes	68	63	41	15
no	56	80	44	13
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	129	151	89	28
yes	63	79	53	14
no	66	72	36	14
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	131	155	88	26
yes	21	30	18	6
no	110	125	70	20
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	132	154	87	27
yes	46	53	36	12
no	86	101	51	15
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	129	155	87	25
livestock	31	43	28	12
other	46	56	23	9

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
 - More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Butler County

493 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.94 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	4	16	3	0	23
FAIRFIELD	19	30	16	2	67
HANOVER	7	12	6	2	27
LEMON	11	11	3	0	25
LIBERTY	14	12	4	2	32
MADISON	21	19	7	2	49
MILFORD	13	22	11	4	50
MORGAN	6	8	2	2	18
OXFORD	3	3	8	0	14
REILY	8	19	6	6	39
ROSS	14	18	24	5	61
ST. CLAIR	18	22	14	5	59
UNION	1	3	1	0	5
WAYNE	13	7	3	1	24

CARROLL COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED OCTOBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Carroll County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Carroll County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Carroll County (average 1.00 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CARROLL COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

CARROLL COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	72	23	14	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	46	10	3	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	4	2	1	0
1950-1970	17	3	0	0
after 1970	25	5	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1969	1966	1956	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	48	12	3	0
< 50 ft.	4	4	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	17	2	1	0
over 100 ft.	27	6	2	0
SPRINGS	1	2	7	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	133	104	160	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	59	19	8	0
yes	44	10	2	0
no	15	9	6	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	61	21	14	0
yes	39	13	5	0
no	22	8	9	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	62	20	14	0
yes	4	3	6	0
no	58	17	8	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	62	19	14	0
yes	20	3	10	0
no	42	16	4	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	71	20	14	0
livestock	8	4	5	0
other	19	8	4	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Carroll County

109 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.00 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
AUGUSTA	7	1	3	0	11
BROWN	12	1	1	0	14
CENTER	8	3	1	0	12
EAST	4	0	0	0	4
FOX	3	1	0	0	4
HARRISON	7	4	2	0	13
LEE	5	3	0	0	8
LOUDON	5	2	3	0	10
MONROE	4	0	0	0	4
ORANGE	2	0	0	0	2
PERRY	8	2	4	0	14
ROSE	2	2	0	0	4
UNION	2	2	0	0	4
WASHINGTON	3	2	0	0	5

CHAMPAIGN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Champaign County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Champaign County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Champaign County (average 2.04 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CHAMPAIGN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

CHAMPAIGN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	104	19	34	6
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	62	11	17	2
1800's	2	0	0	0
1900-1949	9	1	4	0
1950-1970	27	6	10	1
after 1970	24	4	3	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1961	1960	1959	1972
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	68	9	21	2
< 50 ft.	16	4	9	2
50 - 100 ft.	23	2	10	0
over 100 ft.	29	3	2	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	100	69	59	35
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	85	13	26	4
yes	46	10	12	1
no	39	3	14	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	92	15	27	5
yes	66	7	16	5
no	26	8	11	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	92	15	27	6
yes	21	4	8	1
no	71	11	19	5
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	89	15	27	6
yes	56	9	18	4
no	33	6	9	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	103	19	32	6
livestock	34	3	14	1
other	11	3	2	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Champaign County

163 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.04 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
ADAMS	6	0	0	0	6
CONCORD	15	2	1	0	18
GOSHEN	8	0	0	0	8
HARRISON	1	1	1	0	3
JACKSON	11	0	0	0	11
JOHNSON	8	0	0	0	8
MAD RIVER	7	2	4	0	13
RUSH	6	0	0	0	6
SALEM	5	3	18	3	29
UNION	12	6	0	0	18
URBANA	10	5	9	3	27
WAYNE	13	0	1	0	14

CLARK COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Clark County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Clark County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Clark County (average 1.29 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CLARK COUNTY

Nitrate as N

CLARK COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	114	20	20	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	77	12	12	3
1800's	0	1	0	0
1900-1949	14	1	6	2
1950-1970	32	9	5	1
after 1970	31	1	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1957	1949	1945
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	80	9	16	4
< 50 ft.	8	3	7	3
50 - 100 ft.	42	3	9	1
over 100 ft.	30	3	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	100	92	51	54
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	101	14	18	4
yes	63	6	5	1
no	38	8	13	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	103	15	19	4
yes	75	9	13	0
no	28	6	6	4
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	102	17	19	4
yes	11	0	2	4
no	91	17	17	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	102	17	19	4
yes	61	5	11	4
no	41	12	8	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	111	20	18	3
livestock	13	3	2	2
other	33	5	4	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Clark County

158 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.29 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	0	1	0	0	1
BETHEL	12	7	11	0	30
GERMAN	19	1	0	0	20
GREENE	4	1	3	0	8
HARMONY	14	0	0	0	14
MAD RIVER	7	2	5	3	17
MADISON	7	0	0	0	7
MOOREFIELD	12	1	0	0	13
PIKE	8	0	0	0	8
PLEASANT	6	0	0	0	6
SPRINGFIELD	25	7	1	1	34

CLERMONT COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Clermont County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Clermont County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Clermont County (average 1.63 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CLERMONT COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

CLERMONT COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	20	56	8	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	11	21	5	0
1800's	1	4	2	0
1900-1949	4	9	1	0
1950-1970	3	3	2	0
after 1970	3	5	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1945	1928	1897	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	12	35	6	1
< 50 ft.	7	26	6	1
50 - 100 ft.	4	5	0	0
over 100 ft.	1	4	0	0
SPRINGS	0	3	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	51	41	19	30
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	12	40	7	1
yes	6	24	4	1
no	6	16	3	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	13	44	6	1
yes	4	17	3	1
no	9	27	3	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	13	43	7	1
yes	1	9	3	1
no	12	34	4	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	14	44	7	1
yes	7	18	5	1
no	7	26	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	7	38	5	0
livestock	6	10	3	0
other	10	17	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Clermont County

85 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.63 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BATAVIA	0	2	0	0	2
GOSHEN	0	3	0	0	3
JACKSON	3	10	2	0	15
MIAMI	1	6	1	0	8
MONROE	0	3	0	0	3
OHIO	2	2	0	0	4
PIERCE	1	2	0	0	3
STONELICK	3	11	2	0	16
TATE	1	1	0	0	2
UNION	4	4	0	0	8
WASHINGTON	1	3	2	0	6
WAYNE	2	5	1	0	8
WILLIAMSBURG	2	4	0	1	7

CLINTON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Clinton County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Clinton County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Clinton County (average 1.60 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CLINTON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

CLINTON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	122	39	23	5
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	78	12	10	2
1800's	0	0	2	1
1900-1949	14	3	1	0
1950-1970	26	8	4	0
after 1970	38	1	3	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1964	1954	1936	1936
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	86	24	15	3
< 50 ft.	15	16	10	2
50 - 100 ft.	43	6	5	1
over 100 ft.	28	2	0	0
SPRINGS	1	3	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	92	49	39	40
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	101	28	18	4
yes	76	11	8	4
no	25	17	10	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	107	33	22	5
yes	52	16	7	3
no	55	17	15	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	109	34	22	5
yes	25	6	6	1
no	84	28	16	4
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	109	32	22	5
yes	68	23	14	5
no	41	9	8	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	117	34	21	4
livestock	30	3	2	4
other	28	11	8	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Clinton County

189 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.60 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	0	1	0	4
ADAMS	10	2	2	0	14
CHESTER	16	2	1	1	20
CLARK	7	3	1	0	11
GREEN	12	4	1	0	17
JEFFERSON	0	4	0	0	4
LIBERTY	11	2	2	1	16
MARION	0	5	0	0	5
RICHLAND	5	1	1	0	7
UNION	30	10	10	2	52
VERNON	6	1	3	1	11
WASHINGTON	11	3	1	0	15
WAYNE	6	2	0	0	8
WILSON	5	0	0	0	5

COLUMBIANA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Columbiana County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Columbiana County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Columbiana County (average 0.76 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

COLUMBIANA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

COLUMBIANA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	410	92	38	7
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	283	53	16	3
1800's	1	1	1	1
1900-1949	36	10	6	1
1950-1970	109	14	5	0
after 1970	137	28	4	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1967	1965	1944	1929
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	283	63	26	5
< 50 ft.	20	7	12	4
50 - 100 ft.	111	23	10	0
over 100 ft.	152	33	4	1
SPRINGS	4	6	7	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	132	126	64	80
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	354	78	33	6
yes	247	51	19	5
no	107	27	14	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	360	82	35	7
yes	238	40	24	3
no	122	42	11	4
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	367	87	36	7
yes	52	10	9	3
no	315	77	27	4
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	367	86	35	7
yes	124	32	23	4
no	243	54	12	3
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	391	82	34	6
livestock	64	20	7	4
other	82	21	7	2

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Columbiana County

547 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.76 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	3	0	0	6
BUTLER	38	5	5	2	50
CENTER	29	6	1	0	36
ELKRUN	28	7	5	0	40
FAIRFIELD	39	2	5	0	46
FRANKLIN	3	2	0	0	5
HANOVER	25	6	0	0	31
KNOX	35	1	2	2	40
LIVERPOOL	5	3	0	0	8
MADISON	44	14	1	0	59
MIDDLETON	15	3	1	0	19
PERRY	10	2	2	0	14
SALEM	20	5	4	1	30
ST. CLAIR	24	4	1	0	29
UNITY	47	12	5	1	65
WASHINGTON	1	1	0	0	2
WAYNE	4	6	0	0	10
WEST	14	4	4	0	22
YELLOW CREEK	26	6	2	1	35

COSHOCTON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MAY 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Coshocton County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Coshocton County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Coshocton County (average 2.42 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

COSHOCTON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

COSHOCTON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	87	56	38	8
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	53	33	14	4
1800's	1	0	1	0
1900-1949	3	7	4	2
1950-1970	26	14	6	0
after 1970	23	12	3	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1966	1963	1950	1953
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	62	39	16	4
< 50 ft.	12	7	8	3
50 - 100 ft.	27	14	7	1
over 100 ft.	23	18	1	0
SPRINGS	6	5	6	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	125	120	57	44
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	67	47	30	6
yes	40	25	13	4
no	27	22	17	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	80	51	33	6
yes	40	29	15	5
no	40	22	18	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	80	50	34	7
yes	14	8	8	2
no	66	42	26	5
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	79	53	34	7
yes	26	18	15	4
no	53	35	19	3
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	77	54	35	6
livestock	21	11	8	4
other	19	12	8	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Coshocton County

189 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.42 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	1	0	1	4
ADAMS	3	1	1	0	5
BEDFORD	2	2	1	0	5
BETHLEHEM	4	2	3	0	9
CLARK	2	1	0	0	3
CRAWFORD	3	3	5	0	11
FRANKLIN	1	1	0	0	2
JACKSON	8	3	2	0	13
JEFFERSON	2	3	0	0	5
KEENE	7	3	3	0	13
KILLBUCK	0	1	0	0	1
LAFAYETTE	5	7	4	1	17
LINTON	0	0	2	0	2
MILL CREEK	5	3	2	0	10
MONROE	7	2	1	0	10
NEW CASTLE	6	2	0	0	8
OXFORD	3	3	5	2	13
PERRY	5	1	4	1	11
PIKE	4	5	0	2	11
TIVERTON	2	3	0	0	5
TUSCARAWAS	0	2	2	0	4
VIRGINIA	3	0	1	0	4
WASHINGTON	9	4	0	0	13
WHITE EYES	4	3	2	1	10

CRAWFORD COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Crawford County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Crawford County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Crawford County (average 1.52 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CRAWFORD COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

CRAWFORD COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	84	12	14	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	42	2	2	0
1800's	0	1	0	0
1900-1949	4	0	1	0
1950-1970	26	1	1	0
after 1970	12	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	1922	1935	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	50	8	12	1
< 50 ft.	26	7	11	1
50 - 100 ft.	20	0	1	0
over 100 ft.	4	1	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	53	36	28	38
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	64	9	11	2
yes	42	3	7	2
no	22	6	4	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	66	9	13	2
yes	33	4	5	1
no	33	5	8	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	66	9	13	2
yes	16	2	5	1
no	50	7	8	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	67	9	13	2
yes	52	8	12	2
no	15	1	1	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	82	9	8	2
livestock	27	3	8	3
other	22	2	3	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Crawford County

114 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.52 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
AUBURN	0	1	2	0	3
BUCYRUS	8	0	2	0	10
CHATFIELD	1	0	2	0	3
CRANBERRY	4	2	1	0	7
DALLAS	5	1	0	0	6
HOLMES	14	0	0	0	14
JACKSON	1	1	0	0	2
JEFFERSON	5	0	2	0	7
LIBERTY	14	2	2	2	20
LYKENS	4	1	0	0	5
POLK	0	1	0	0	1
SANDUSKY	2	0	0	0	2
TEXAS	7	0	0	0	7
TOD	3	0	0	0	3
VERNON	2	0	0	0	2
WHETSTONE	14	3	3	2	22

CUYAHOGA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Cuyahoga County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Cuyahoga County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Cuyahoga County (average 0.31 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

CUYAHOGA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

CUYAHOGA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	116	22	3	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	31	7	1	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	7	3	1	0
1950-1970	21	4	0	0
after 1970	3	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1954	1952	1930	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	29	7	2	0
< 50 ft.	9	5	1	0
50 - 100 ft.	14	2	1	0
over 100 ft.	6	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	1	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	77	45	35	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	42	9	1	0
yes	15	4	1	0
no	27	5	0	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	50	11	1	0
yes	30	4	1	0
no	20	7	0	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	50	12	2	0
yes	3	0	0	0
no	47	12	2	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	50	12	2	0
yes	2	1	1	0
no	48	11	1	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	89	17	1	0
livestock	3	0	0	0
other	21	11	3	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Cuyahoga County

141 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.31 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	74	11	0	0	85
BEDFORD	0	1	0	0	1
BRECKSVILLE	3	0	0	0	3
BROADVIEW HT	4	0	1	0	5
BROOK PARK	2	0	0	0	2
CHAGRIN FALL	1	0	0	0	1
CLEVE. HGTS.	1	0	0	0	1
FAIRVIEW PK	1	0	0	0	1
INDEPENDENCE	1	0	0	0	1
MAPLE HGTS.	2	0	0	0	2
MIDDLEBURG	2	0	0	0	2
NO. OLMSTED	1	0	0	0	1
NO. ROYALTON	7	4	0	0	11
OLMSTED	12	3	1	0	16
STRONGSVILLE	4	3	1	0	8
WALTON HILLS	1	0	0	0	1

DEFIANCE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APRIL 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Defiance County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Defiance County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Defiance County (average 0.30 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

DEFIANCE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

No well location data for this county

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

DEFIANCE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	218	14	2	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	114	8	0	0
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	26	4	0	0
1950-1970	47	4	0	0
after 1970	40	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1959	1935	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	124	10	1	1
< 50 ft.	11	8	1	1
50 - 100 ft.	91	2	0	0
over 100 ft.	22	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	81	31	15	23
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	162	10	1	1
yes	89	5	0	0
no	73	5	1	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	174	12	1	2
yes	117	6	0	1
no	57	6	1	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	179	12	1	2
yes	45	2	0	0
no	134	10	1	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	180	12	1	2
yes	138	8	1	2
no	42	4	0	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	207	10	2	3
livestock	60	1	0	1
other	45	9	0	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Defiance County

237 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.30 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
ADAMS	22	0	0	0	22
DEFIANCE	8	3	0	1	12
DELAWARE	25	1	0	0	26
FARMER	22	1	0	0	23
HICKSVILLE	11	0	0	0	11
HIGHLAND	20	0	0	0	20
MARK	14	0	0	0	14
MILFORD	18	0	0	0	18
NOBLE	7	0	0	0	7
RICHLAND	28	9	2	2	41
TIFFIN	15	0	0	0	15
WASHINGTON	26	0	0	0	26

DELAWARE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DECEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Delaware County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Delaware County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Delaware County (average 1.96 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

DELAWARE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

DELAWARE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	100	32	20	7
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	55	17	9	4
1800's	1	0	1	0
1900-1949	4	4	3	1
1950-1970	25	8	3	2
after 1970	25	5	2	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1967	1959	1944	1954
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	68	21	14	6
< 50 ft.	31	8	10	5
50 - 100 ft.	31	12	4	1
over 100 ft.	6	1	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	59	62	41	31
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	87	27	17	7
yes	60	20	6	4
no	27	7	11	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	91	29	18	7
yes	61	15	13	1
no	30	14	5	6
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	93	29	18	7
yes	29	3	3	1
no	64	26	15	6
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	93	29	17	7
yes	49	16	7	6
no	44	13	10	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	87	24	17	6
livestock	34	4	6	1
other	32	16	8	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Delaware County

159 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.96 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
BERKSHIRE	2	2	0	0	4
BERLIN	3	3	1	0	7
BROWN	3	2	0	0	5
CONCORD	22	5	1	0	28
DELAWARE	5	1	1	1	8
GENOA	3	0	0	0	3
HARLEM	3	0	0	0	3
KINGSTON	5	3	4	0	12
LIBERTY	8	4	2	0	14
MARLBORO	1	0	0	0	1
ORANGE	0	2	0	0	2
OXFORD	1	1	0	0	2
PORTER	7	0	1	0	8
RADNOR	4	3	5	5	17
SCIOTO	8	1	1	0	10
THOMPSON	10	1	2	0	13
TRENTON	2	1	1	0	4
TROY	11	3	1	1	16

ERIE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JULY 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Erie County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Erie County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Erie County (average 2.36 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

ERIE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

ERIE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	127	44	37	15
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	83	20	16	5
1800's	2	2	0	1
1900-1949	11	4	6	2
1950-1970	34	7	3	1
after 1970	36	7	7	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	1952	1949	1940
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	89	24	21	10
< 50 ft.	37	18	16	9
50 - 100 ft.	42	4	4	1
over 100 ft.	10	2	1	0
SPRINGS	1	1	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	58	44	37	24
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	108	29	25	13
yes	63	15	9	5
no	45	14	16	8
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	106	33	28	14
yes	65	25	15	7
no	41	8	13	7
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	113	33	27	14
yes	16	9	2	2
no	97	24	25	12
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	112	34	28	14
yes	84	23	23	11
no	28	11	5	3
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	112	37	33	13
livestock	15	7	4	2
other	37	22	12	5

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Erie County

223 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.36 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	1	0	1	3
BERLIN	15	1	2	2	20
FLORENCE	9	6	4	3	22
GROTON	6	3	2	2	13
HURON	13	0	0	0	13
MARGARETTA	10	8	11	0	29
MILAN	37	9	5	2	53
OXFORD	32	8	13	5	58
PERKINS	1	3	0	0	4
VERMILION	3	5	0	0	8

FAIRFIELD COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JULY 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Fairfield County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Fairfield County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Fairfield County (average 1.51 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

FAIRFIELD COUNTY

Nitrate as N

FAIRFIELD COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	309	121	68	12
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	201	70	46	8
1800's	2	0	0	0
1900-1949	18	5	7	0
1950-1970	71	27	27	7
after 1970	110	38	12	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1968	1969	1961	1960
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	231	83	48	7
< 50 ft.	35	11	11	4
50 - 100 ft.	97	34	23	0
over 100 ft.	99	38	14	3
SPRINGS	0	4	2	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	107	116	87	65
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	267	105	58	9
yes	177	66	33	2
no	90	39	25	7
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	275	107	62	9
yes	184	61	46	5
no	91	46	16	4
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	283	109	63	9
yes	56	14	12	3
no	227	95	51	6
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	283	111	63	8
yes	171	38	35	7
no	112	73	28	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	300	116	64	11
livestock	87	25	17	4
other	68	27	20	4

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Fairfield County

510 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.51 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
AMANDA	11	4	1	0	16
BERNE	15	12	7	5	39
BLOOM	23	10	5	2	40
CLEAR CREEK	17	5	1	1	24
GREENFIELD	35	11	6	0	52
HOCKING	30	17	8	1	56
LIBERTY	37	2	2	1	42
MADISON	18	10	2	2	32
PLEASANT	44	21	18	0	83
RICHLAND	16	8	6	0	30
RUSH CREEK	18	16	10	0	44
VIOLET	12	2	1	0	15
WALNUT	32	3	1	0	36

FAYETTE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED AUG, NOV 1998

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Fayette County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Fayette County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Fayette County (average 0.69 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

FAYETTE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

FAYETTE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	70	3	6	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	35	0	0	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	6	0	0	0
1950-1970	16	0	0	0
after 1970	13	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	0	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	43	1	3	1
< 50 ft.	3	1	2	0
50 - 100 ft.	30	0	1	1
over 100 ft.	10	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	89	18	32	90
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	59	3	4	1
yes	40	0	1	1
no	19	3	3	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	3	5	0
yes	37	1	1	0
no	26	2	4	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	62	3	5	1
yes	17	2	2	0
no	45	1	3	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	3	5	1
yes	46	3	3	1
no	17	0	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	68	1	4	1
livestock	23	2	4	0
other	8	2	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Fayette County

80 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.69 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
CONCORD	6	0	0	0	6
GREEN	4	0	0	0	4
JASPER	6	0	0	0	6
JEFFERSON	20	2	3	0	25
MADISON	2	0	0	0	2
MARION	2	0	0	0	2
PAINT	2	0	2	0	4
PERRY	3	1	0	0	4
UNION	14	0	0	0	14
WAYNE	10	0	1	1	12

FRANKLIN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED OCTOBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Franklin County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Franklin County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Franklin County (average 0.32 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

FRANKLIN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

FRANKLIN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	229	28	9	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	145	11	3	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	8	2	1	0
1950-1970	69	8	1	0
after 1970	68	1	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1967	1957	1956	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	153	16	3	0
< 50 ft.	20	2	3	0
50 - 100 ft.	70	12	0	0
over 100 ft.	63	2	0	0
SPRINGS	0	2	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	99	85	37	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	185	22	7	0
yes	129	11	2	0
no	56	11	5	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	195	22	8	0
yes	140	11	2	0
no	55	11	6	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	193	22	8	0
yes	17	2	1	0
no	176	20	7	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	192	22	8	0
yes	79	8	4	0
no	113	14	4	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	217	25	7	0
livestock	20	1	1	0
other	69	16	4	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Franklin County

266 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.32 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	6	6	1	0	13
BLENDON	6	0	0	0	6
BROWN	20	1	0	0	21
DUBLIN	3	0	0	0	3
FRANKLIN	9	0	0	0	9
HAMILTON	3	1	1	0	5
JACKSON	58	3	1	0	62
JEFFERSON	24	3	2	0	29
MADISON	21	1	2	0	24
MARION	0	0	1	0	1
MIFFLIN	2	0	0	0	2
NORWICH	5	1	0	0	6
PERRY	5	2	0	0	7
PLAIN	6	0	1	0	7
PLEASANT	36	1	0	0	37
PRAIRIE	2	0	0	0	2
SHARON	11	1	0	0	12
TRURO	1	4	0	0	5
WASHINGTON	11	4	0	0	15

FULTON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Fulton County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Fulton County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Fulton County (average 2.32 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

FULTON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

FULTON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	118	15	17	17
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	73	6	6	6
1800's	1	0	0	2
1900-1949	17	1	1	1
1950-1970	24	1	2	0
after 1970	31	4	3	3
<u>average year drilled</u>	1961	1968	1968	1945
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	89	12	11	12
< 50 ft.	17	11	10	12
50 - 100 ft.	20	1	0	0
over 100 ft.	52	0	1	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	109	23	27	16
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	105	10	14	12
yes	67	4	6	6
no	38	6	8	6
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	105	13	15	15
yes	58	6	8	7
no	47	7	7	8
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	106	14	15	15
yes	38	2	2	5
no	68	12	13	10
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	108	13	14	15
yes	92	11	10	14
no	16	2	4	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	109	14	15	16
livestock	56	3	2	9
other	16	3	6	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Fulton County

167 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.32 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
AMBOY	4	3	5	1	13
CHESTERFIELD	16	1	1	1	19
CLINTON	12	0	0	5	17
DOVER	4	1	2	0	7
FRANKLIN	8	0	0	0	8
FULTON	8	3	6	6	23
GERMAN	23	0	0	0	23
GORHAM	11	0	0	0	11
PIKE	8	2	1	1	12
ROYALTON	2	3	1	1	7
SWANCREEK	4	2	1	2	9
YORK	17	0	0	0	17

GALLIA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DECEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Gallia County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Gallia County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Gallia County (average 1.90 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

GALLIA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

GALLIA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	3	1	2	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	3	1	1	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	0	0	0	0
1950-1970	1	1	1	0
after 1970	2	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1971	1962	1950	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	3	1	1	0
< 50 ft.	0	0	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	3	1	1	0
over 100 ft.	0	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	73	60	65	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	3	1	2	0
yes	1	0	1	0
no	2	1	1	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	3	1	2	0
yes	0	1	1	0
no	3	0	1	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	3	1	2	0
yes	0	0	1	0
no	3	1	1	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	3	1	2	0
yes	0	0	1	0
no	3	1	1	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	3	1	2	0
livestock	0	0	0	0
other	1	1	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Gallia County

6 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.90 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
ADDISON	0	1	0	0	1
CLAY	1	0	2	0	3
GREEN	1	0	0	0	1
PERRY	1	0	0	0	1

GEAUGA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Geauga County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Geauga County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Geauga County (average 1.07 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

GEAUGA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

GEAUGA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	75	39	18	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	51	24	13	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	8	3	3	0
1950-1970	25	11	7	0
after 1970	18	10	3	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1964	1964	1960	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	56	28	14	0
< 50 ft.	12	3	4	0
50 - 100 ft.	33	20	6	0
over 100 ft.	11	5	4	0
SPRINGS	1	2	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	82	88	129	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	64	31	18	0
yes	42	20	11	0
no	22	11	7	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	65	33	18	0
yes	42	18	8	0
no	23	15	10	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	67	35	18	0
yes	8	5	4	0
no	59	30	14	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	67	35	18	0
yes	19	10	5	0
no	48	25	13	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	74	36	17	0
livestock	8	3	5	0
other	27	8	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Geauga County

132 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.07 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
AUBURN	12	2	6	0	20
BAINBRIDGE	1	3	0	0	4
BURTON	1	7	4	0	12
CHARDON	8	4	0	0	12
CHESTER	5	3	3	0	11
CLARIDON	2	2	1	0	5
HAMBDEN	5	4	0	0	9
HUNTSBURG	5	1	1	0	7
MIDDLEFIELD	1	1	1	0	3
MONTVILLE	2	0	0	0	2
MUNSON	6	2	0	0	8
NEWBURY	8	2	1	0	11
PARKMAN	5	0	0	0	5
RUSSELL	3	4	0	0	7
THOMPSON	8	2	0	0	10
TROY	2	2	1	0	5

GREENE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH, JUNE 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Greene County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Greene County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Greene County (average 2.42 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

GREENE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

GREENE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	163	36	57	15
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	106	19	21	6
1800's	2	0	1	0
1900-1949	22	2	4	1
1950-1970	38	7	10	3
after 1970	44	10	6	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1961	1967	1956	1957
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	119	21	25	8
< 50 ft.	24	4	8	4
50 - 100 ft.	67	12	15	4
over 100 ft.	28	5	2	0
SPRINGS	2	0	6	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	95	78	64	52
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	154	30	46	12
yes	115	19	26	5
no	39	11	20	7
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	156	30	50	12
yes	90	17	25	6
no	66	13	25	6
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	157	30	51	12
yes	43	12	17	4
no	114	18	34	8
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	155	32	52	12
yes	108	24	33	6
no	47	8	19	6
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	151	28	42	14
livestock	65	16	28	10
other	43	3	10	2

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Greene County

271 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.42 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	0	1	1	0	2
BATH	5	0	5	2	12
BEAVER CREEK	14	2	7	1	24
CAESAR CREEK	18	3	1	0	22
CEDARVILLE	16	2	4	1	23
JEFFERSON	14	2	1	1	18
MIAMI	13	3	10	3	29
NEW JASPER	15	1	3	2	21
ROSS	14	4	2	0	20
SILVERCREEK	7	1	1	0	9
SPG. VALLEY	13	5	5	1	24
SUGARCREEK	14	4	5	1	24
XENIA	20	8	12	3	43

GUERNSEY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DECEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Guernsey County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Guernsey County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Guernsey County (average 1.00 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

GUERNSEY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

GUERNSEY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	63	34	11	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	39	15	5	1
1800's	3	1	0	1
1900-1949	3	1	0	0
1950-1970	17	4	1	0
after 1970	16	9	4	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1958	1967	1980	1860
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	37	12	4	1
< 50 ft.	4	3	1	1
50 - 100 ft.	22	6	2	0
over 100 ft.	11	3	1	0
SPRINGS	8	10	3	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	90	95	75	26
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	45	24	5	1
yes	26	15	3	0
no	19	9	2	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	51	25	8	1
yes	24	9	3	0
no	27	16	5	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	51	26	8	1
yes	9	5	4	0
no	42	21	4	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	49	26	8	1
yes	10	4	6	0
no	39	22	2	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	53	32	9	1
livestock	11	8	5	0
other	18	4	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Guernsey County

109 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.00 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	1	0	0	4
ADAMS	0	1	0	0	1
CAMBRIDGE	19	6	1	0	26
CENTER	5	2	0	0	7
JACKSON	4	2	0	0	6
LIBERTY	5	2	0	0	7
LONDONDERRY	3	3	2	0	8
MADISON	3	0	2	0	5
MILLWOOD	2	2	0	0	4
OXFORD	1	0	0	0	1
RICHLAND	3	3	2	0	8
SPENCER	0	2	1	0	3
VALLEY	4	2	0	0	6
WASHINGTON	1	1	0	0	2
WESTLAND	6	4	1	1	12
WHEELING	0	1	0	0	1
WILLS	4	2	2	0	8

HAMILTON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Hamilton County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Hamilton County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Hamilton County (average 1.56 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HAMILTON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

HAMILTON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	47	113	15	6
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	16	21	9	1
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	2	4	0	0
1950-1970	8	6	7	1
after 1970	6	11	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1966	1961	1966	1965
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	18	25	11	4
< 50 ft.	1	12	4	3
50 - 100 ft.	13	12	5	1
over 100 ft.	4	1	2	0
SPRINGS	0	1	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	89	57	63	38
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	22	27	13	4
yes	10	17	9	2
no	12	10	4	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	22	32	13	5
yes	12	8	6	4
no	10	24	7	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	22	33	12	5
yes	5	6	1	1
no	17	27	11	4
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	23	33	13	5
yes	12	8	10	4
no	11	25	3	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	36	85	15	5
livestock	6	7	3	0
other	7	20	3	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Hamilton County

181 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.56 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	17	34	0	0	51
ANDERSON	0	1	0	0	1
COLERAIN	9	37	2	0	48
COLUMBIA	1	4	0	1	6
CROSBY	8	5	9	3	25
DELHI	0	1	0	0	1
GREEN	0	2	0	0	2
HARRISON	6	0	1	1	8
SPRINGFIELD	4	22	0	1	27
SYCAMORE	1	1	0	0	2
SYMMES	1	1	0	0	2
WHITEWATER	0	5	3	0	8

HANCOCK COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DEC 1986, JAN 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Hancock County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Hancock County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Hancock County (average 0.61 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HANCOCK COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

HANCOCK COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	199	15	8	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	105	8	2	1
1800's	3	1	0	0
1900-1949	23	1	0	0
1950-1970	40	3	1	1
after 1970	39	3	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1957	1953	1975	1950
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	104	7	3	2
< 50 ft.	48	5	3	0
50 - 100 ft.	45	1	0	1
over 100 ft.	11	1	0	1
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	63	51	29	90
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	169	12	8	3
yes	119	8	3	0
no	50	4	5	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	172	12	8	3
yes	129	9	5	1
no	43	3	3	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	171	12	8	3
yes	30	3	2	1
no	141	9	6	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	171	11	8	3
yes	133	11	7	2
no	38	0	1	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	183	12	8	3
livestock	39	4	0	2
other	44	7	3	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Hancock County

226 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.60 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
ALLEN	9	0	0	0	9
AMANDA	8	1	0	0	9
BIGLICK	20	2	1	2	25
BLANCHARD	5	0	0	0	5
CASS	11	0	1	1	13
DELAWARE	3	0	0	0	3
EAGLE	6	1	0	0	7
JACKSON	3	2	1	0	6
LIBERTY	37	5	1	0	43
MADISON	17	2	0	0	19
MARION	28	1	1	0	30
ORANGE	3	0	1	0	4
PLEASANT	3	0	0	0	3
PORTAGE	8	0	0	0	8
UNION	13	0	0	0	13
VAN BUREN	8	0	1	1	10
WASHINGTON	17	1	1	0	19

HARRISON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED OCTOBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Harrison County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Harrison County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Harrison County (average 0.93 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HARRISON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

HARRISON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	70	44	12	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	43	13	5	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	4	3	2	0
1950-1970	13	1	1	0
after 1970	26	9	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1968	1969	1952	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	43	21	3	0
< 50 ft.	1	3	2	0
50 - 100 ft.	22	9	0	0
over 100 ft.	20	9	1	0
SPRINGS	8	7	3	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	112	99	75	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	57	31	8	0
yes	39	22	4	0
no	18	9	4	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	64	36	11	0
yes	35	10	3	0
no	29	26	8	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	36	11	0
yes	12	9	3	0
no	51	27	8	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	62	35	11	0
yes	11	13	5	0
no	51	22	6	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	64	40	11	0
livestock	22	14	8	0
other	17	7	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Harrison County

126 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.93 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
ARCHER	4	5	0	0	9
ATHENS	0	1	0	0	1
CADIZ	7	7	0	0	14
FRANKLIN	11	2	1	0	14
FREEPORT	6	4	0	0	10
GERMAN	12	6	1	0	19
GREEN	3	4	0	0	7
MONROE	1	0	0	0	1
MOOREFIELD	1	2	1	0	4
NORTH	3	2	0	0	5
NOTTINGHAM	4	4	0	0	8
RUMLEY	4	2	4	0	10
SHORT CREEK	3	1	2	0	6
STOCK	9	4	2	0	15
WASHINGTON	2	0	1	0	3

HENRY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Henry County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Henry County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Henry County (average 0.74 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HENRY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

HENRY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	68	10	2	2
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	49	7	1	2
1800's	0	1	1	0
1900-1949	14	2	0	0
1950-1970	14	3	0	2
after 1970	21	1	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1941	1855	1965
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	54	6	1	2
< 50 ft.	14	5	1	2
50 - 100 ft.	35	1	0	0
over 100 ft.	5	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	70	32	14	15
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	63	8	2	2
yes	34	3	1	1
no	29	5	1	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	64	9	2	2
yes	44	6	2	2
no	20	3	0	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	64	9	2	2
yes	16	0	0	0
no	48	9	2	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	64	9	2	2
yes	54	7	2	1
no	10	2	0	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	67	10	2	2
livestock	10	0	0	0
other	12	2	1	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Henry County

82 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.74 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BARTLOW	3	0	0	0	3
DAMASCUS	4	0	0	0	4
FLATROCK	2	1	1	0	4
FREEDOM	6	0	0	0	6
HARRISON	5	1	0	1	7
LIBERTY	3	1	0	1	5
MARION	6	0	0	0	6
MONROE	10	2	0	0	12
NAPOLEON	13	3	0	0	16
PLEASANT	3	0	0	0	3
RICHFIELD	4	1	0	0	5
RIDGEVILLE	7	0	0	0	7
WASHINGTON	2	1	1	0	4

HIGHLAND COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Highland County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Highland County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Highland County (average 3.07 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HIGHLAND COUNTY

Nitrate as N

HIGHLAND COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	78	36	30	18
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	43	14	5	5
1800's	2	1	0	1
1900-1949	2	1	1	0
1950-1970	20	5	2	0
after 1970	19	7	2	4
<u>average year drilled</u>	1962	1962	1961	1963
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	50	19	12	8
< 50 ft.	7	7	5	4
50 - 100 ft.	24	8	6	2
over 100 ft.	19	4	1	2
SPRINGS	1	4	5	2
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	93	69	50	62
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	69	31	23	13
yes	49	17	12	8
no	20	14	11	5
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	74	32	26	16
yes	44	14	15	6
no	30	18	11	10
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	73	32	27	16
yes	19	7	11	8
no	54	25	16	8
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	75	33	25	15
yes	35	16	17	14
no	40	17	8	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	70	29	27	17
livestock	25	11	10	7
other	27	13	11	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Highland County

162 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 3.07 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	2	0	0	3
BRUSH CREEK	9	1	6	3	19
CLAY	1	2	0	1	4
CONCORD	7	1	1	0	9
DODSON	1	3	3	0	7
FAIRFIELD	10	2	7	7	26
HAMER	3	1	1	2	7
JACKSON	0	2	0	1	3
LIBERTY	5	4	4	0	13
MADISON	4	0	0	0	4
MARSHALL	3	3	1	0	7
NEW MARKET	4	0	1	0	5
PAINT	9	6	5	1	21
PENN	14	1	0	2	17
SALEM	0	1	0	1	2
UNION	2	1	0	0	3
WASHINGTON	3	5	1	0	9
WHITE OAK	2	1	0	0	3

HOLMES COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Holmes County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Holmes County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Holmes County (average 1.62 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HOLMES COUNTY

Nitrate as N

HOLMES COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	278	146	71	17
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	149	44	12	3
1800's	0	0	2	0
1900-1949	8	6	3	0
1950-1970	45	9	2	1
after 1970	96	29	5	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1972	1971	1953	1974
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	161	56	19	6
< 50 ft.	7	6	7	3
50 - 100 ft.	50	23	7	1
over 100 ft.	104	27	5	2
SPRINGS	19	66	36	9
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	155	129	84	94
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	207	76	34	7
yes	156	53	15	6
no	51	23	19	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	210	99	42	9
yes	108	44	22	5
no	102	55	20	4
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	222	101	40	9
yes	55	28	8	2
no	167	73	32	7
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	220	98	41	9
yes	107	44	26	3
no	113	54	15	6
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	261	125	57	9
livestock	93	60	38	10
other	52	25	12	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Holmes County

512 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.62 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	4	0	2	9
BERLIN	25	6	5	0	36
CLARK	16	7	10	5	38
HARDY	39	25	4	1	69
KILLBUCK	13	23	5	0	41
KNOX	6	7	2	3	18
MECHANIC	13	8	3	0	24
MONROE	19	11	5	2	37
PAINT	9	5	4	0	18
PRAIRIE	34	18	3	0	55
RICHLAND	10	7	4	0	21
RIPLEY	29	6	3	0	38
SALT CREEK	19	7	8	1	35
WALNUT CREEK	2	1	1	2	6
WASHINGTON	41	11	14	1	67

HURON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APRIL 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Huron County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Huron County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Huron County (average 2.43 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

HURON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

HURON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	79	23	28	5
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	40	7	4	1
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	5	1	1	1
1950-1970	21	3	3	0
after 1970	14	3	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1966	1956	1900
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	51	14	15	3
< 50 ft.	18	12	14	3
50 - 100 ft.	29	1	1	0
over 100 ft.	4	1	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	60	34	29	20
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	63	15	13	3
yes	48	8	5	0
no	15	7	8	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	67	18	17	3
yes	34	6	7	2
no	33	12	10	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	67	18	17	3
yes	9	0	3	2
no	58	18	14	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	66	18	17	3
yes	43	15	11	2
no	23	3	6	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	70	17	24	5
livestock	19	7	8	0
other	23	7	8	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Huron County

135 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.43 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	1	0	2
BRONSON	8	4	2	0	14
BRONWON	1	0	0	0	1
CLARKSFIELD	4	0	2	0	6
FAIRFIELD	4	1	1	0	6
FITCHVILLE	1	0	0	0	1
GREENFIELD	3	0	0	0	3
GREENWICH	2	1	0	1	4
HARTLAND	6	4	3	0	13
LYME	1	2	2	1	6
NEW HAVEN	14	0	3	0	17
NEW LONDON	3	0	0	0	3
NORWALK	13	3	6	1	23
PERU	4	0	0	0	4
RICHMOND	1	0	0	0	1
RIDGEFIELD	2	1	2	1	6
RIPLEY	1	1	1	0	3
SHERMAN	1	1	1	0	3
TOWNSEND	4	0	1	1	6
WAKEMAN	5	5	3	0	13

JEFFERSON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED OCTOBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Jefferson County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Jefferson County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Jefferson County (average 1.04 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

JEFFERSON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

JEFFERSON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	139	96	21	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	102	55	12	2
1800's	0	1	0	0
1900-1949	15	11	3	0
1950-1970	46	27	7	2
after 1970	41	16	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1966	1958	1959	1961
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	104	58	9	2
< 50 ft.	6	7	1	2
50 - 100 ft.	36	23	4	0
over 100 ft.	62	28	4	0
SPRINGS	2	8	5	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	120	109	115	21
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	127	78	17	3
yes	56	37	7	1
no	71	41	10	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	127	85	19	4
yes	68	35	7	1
no	59	50	12	3
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	128	85	18	4
yes	17	11	2	2
no	111	74	16	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	128	84	18	4
yes	36	27	8	2
no	92	57	10	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	132	89	18	3
livestock	21	21	8	1
other	38	23	3	2

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Jefferson County

260 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.04 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
BRUSH CREEK	1	0	1	0	2
CROSS CREEK	21	16	1	0	38
ISLAND CREEK	19	12	0	1	32
KNOX	7	0	1	0	8
MT. PLEASANT	10	2	3	0	15
ROSS	9	8	7	3	27
SALEM	31	17	5	0	53
SALINE	3	1	0	0	4
SMITHFIELD	8	7	0	0	15
SPRINGFIELD	10	6	0	0	16
STEUBENVILLE	4	3	0	0	7
WARREN	3	8	0	0	11
WAYNE	11	10	1	0	22
WELLS	1	6	2	0	9

KNOX COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE, JULY 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Knox County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Knox County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Knox County (average 1.46 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

KNOX COUNTY

Nitrate as N

KNOX COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	416	195	115	12
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	222	107	47	6
1800's	0	0	0	1
1900-1949	28	13	11	1
1950-1970	87	43	17	2
after 1970	107	51	19	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1966	1965	1961	1946
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	266	107	54	8
< 50 ft.	30	11	12	4
50 - 100 ft.	97	21	13	3
over 100 ft.	139	75	29	1
SPRINGS	1	12	10	3
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	128	135	111	59
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	340	165	88	9
yes	218	99	48	4
no	122	66	40	5
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	347	173	101	12
yes	227	108	65	9
no	120	65	36	3
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	358	174	100	12
yes	82	33	25	6
no	276	141	75	6
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	356	174	100	12
yes	200	69	53	11
no	156	105	47	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	395	181	107	10
livestock	124	55	42	6
other	102	51	26	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Knox County

738 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.46 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	7	1	2	0	10
BERLIN	13	13	6	1	33
BROWN	9	10	4	0	23
BUTLER	9	3	0	0	12
CLAY	4	12	9	0	25
CLINTON	57	15	8	1	81
COLLEGE	8	6	3	0	17
HARRISON	14	5	5	0	24
HILLIAR	19	2	0	0	21
HOWARD	10	10	5	0	25
JACKSON	18	8	2	1	29
JEFFERSON	8	7	1	0	16
LIBERTY	28	1	1	0	30
MIDDLEBURY	38	7	5	2	52
MILFORD	35	1	0	0	36
MILLER	20	2	0	0	22
MONROE	29	24	5	1	59
MORGAN	13	9	6	0	28
MORRIS	18	19	20	2	59
PIKE	0	6	13	1	20
PLEASANT	16	17	13	2	48
UNION	13	12	2	0	27
WAYNE	30	5	5	1	41

LAKE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Lake County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Lake County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Lake County (average 2.00 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

LAKE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

LAKE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	27	21	12	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	14	11	6	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	2	1	2	0
1950-1970	8	5	3	0
after 1970	4	5	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1962	1966	1953	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	18	18	9	2
< 50 ft.	10	13	9	2
50 - 100 ft.	6	4	0	0
over 100 ft.	2	1	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	53	40	16	20
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	26	17	9	3
yes	18	7	6	1
no	8	10	3	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	26	18	11	3
yes	18	7	6	2
no	8	11	5	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	26	18	10	3
yes	5	2	4	1
no	21	16	6	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	25	17	11	3
yes	4	5	6	2
no	21	12	5	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	25	19	8	2
livestock	4	1	3	1
other	11	7	7	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Lake County

63 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.00 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	3	0	0	5
CONCORD	3	2	0	0	5
KIRTLAND	3	0	0	0	3
LEROY	7	4	0	0	11
MADISON	8	2	2	0	12
MENTOR	0	2	3	1	6
PAINESVILLE	1	5	4	1	11
PERRY	1	3	3	1	8
WILLOUGHBY	2	0	0	0	2

LICKING COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED FEBRUARY 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Licking County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Licking County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Licking County (average 1.09 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

LICKING COUNTY

Nitrate as N

LICKING COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	288	129	39	8
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	200	90	25	2
1800's	0	0	2	0
1900-1949	14	10	7	1
1950-1970	85	45	8	1
after 1970	101	35	8	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1968	1966	1950	1939
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	223	93	27	2
< 50 ft.	24	7	6	2
50 - 100 ft.	87	24	8	0
over 100 ft.	112	62	13	0
SPRINGS	0	3	1	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	120	158	86	23
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	260	116	34	3
yes	188	70	21	0
no	72	46	13	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	268	119	34	4
yes	175	77	22	3
no	93	42	12	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	270	120	35	5
yes	57	21	7	0
no	213	99	28	5
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	271	120	35	6
yes	115	35	16	2
no	156	85	19	4
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	275	125	38	7
livestock	69	27	13	2
other	69	34	7	4

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Licking County

464 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.09 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	15	3	0	0	18
BENNINGTON	10	2	1	1	14
BOWLING GR	6	8	1	0	15
BURLINGTON	7	1	2	0	10
EDEN	3	2	1	0	6
ETNA	12	0	1	0	13
FALLSBURY	0	3	0	0	3
FRANKLIN	8	9	1	1	19
GRANVILLE	17	15	3	0	35
HANOVER	9	5	1	0	15
HARRISON	15	2	0	0	17
HARTFORD	18	3	1	1	23
HOPEWELL	3	3	0	0	6
JERSEY	14	0	0	0	14
LIBERTY	21	2	1	0	24
LICKING	11	18	4	1	34
LIMA	8	3	0	1	12
MADISON	10	13	3	1	27
MARY ANN	3	2	0	0	5
MCKEAN	7	3	0	1	11
MONROE	18	2	0	0	20
NEWARK	11	5	2	0	18
NEWTON	9	1	3	0	13
PERRY	2	9	0	0	11
ST. ALBANS	18	4	0	0	22
UNION	26	10	11	0	47
WASHINGTON	7	1	3	1	12

LOGAN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Logan County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Logan County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Logan County (average 0.61 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

LOGAN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

LOGAN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	74	6	5	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	36	4	1	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	2	0	0	0
1950-1970	13	1	0	0
after 1970	21	3	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1971	1974	1971	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	47	6	1	0
< 50 ft.	13	2	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	16	2	0	0
over 100 ft.	18	2	1	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	107	77	125	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	60	6	3	1
yes	43	3	2	1
no	17	3	1	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	6	4	1
yes	41	6	2	1
no	22	0	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	64	6	4	1
yes	11	1	0	1
no	53	5	4	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	6	4	1
yes	23	4	0	1
no	40	2	4	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	71	6	5	1
livestock	16	1	2	1
other	7	1	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Logan County

86 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.61 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
BLOOMFIELD	2	0	0	0	2
HARRISON	8	1	1	0	10
JEFFERSON	6	0	0	0	6
LAKE	7	0	0	0	7
LIBERTY	1	0	1	0	2
MCARTHUR	8	1	1	0	10
MONROE	3	2	0	1	6
PERRY	2	0	0	0	2
PLEASANT	1	0	0	0	1
RICHLAND	4	0	1	0	5
RUSHCREEK	6	1	0	0	7
STOKES	11	0	0	0	11
UNION	3	1	1	0	5
WASHINGTON	7	0	0	0	7
ZANE	3	0	0	0	3

LORAIN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APR, SEPT 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Lorain County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Lorain County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Lorain County (average 0.71 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

LORAIN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

LORAIN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	16	7	3	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	12	5	2	0
1800's	0	1	1	0
1900-1949	2	2	1	0
1950-1970	7	1	0	0
after 1970	3	1	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1944	1908	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	12	6	3	0
< 50 ft.	4	5	3	0
50 - 100 ft.	5	1	0	0
over 100 ft.	3	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	65	27	22	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	12	6	2	0
yes	8	3	0	0
no	4	3	2	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	13	6	3	0
yes	10	3	3	0
no	3	3	0	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	13	6	3	0
yes	3	0	1	0
no	10	6	2	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	13	6	3	0
yes	6	6	2	0
no	7	0	1	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	12	6	2	0
livestock	4	1	1	0
other	9	3	3	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Lorain County

26 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.71 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
BRIGHTON	1	1	1	0	3
BROWHELM	0	1	0	0	1
CAMDEN	1	0	0	0	1
COLUMBIA	2	1	0	0	3
HENRIETTA	7	1	1	0	9
HUNTINGTON	0	2	0	0	2
LAGRANGE	0	1	1	0	2
PENFIELD	1	0	0	0	1
PITTSFIELD	2	0	0	0	2

LUCAS COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Lucas County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Lucas County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Lucas County (average 0.65 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

LUCAS COUNTY

Nitrate as N

LUCAS COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	152	19	9	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	89	15	6	1
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	9	1	0	0
1950-1970	29	7	2	1
after 1970	51	7	4	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1969	1966	1974	1958
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	101	15	5	2
< 50 ft.	20	10	5	2
50 - 100 ft.	72	5	0	0
over 100 ft.	9	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	69	37	17	20
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	130	17	8	2
yes	84	12	1	1
no	46	5	7	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	133	19	7	2
yes	94	12	5	2
no	39	7	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	137	19	8	2
yes	10	0	0	0
no	127	19	8	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	138	19	9	2
yes	67	8	1	2
no	71	11	8	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	147	15	8	3
livestock	9	0	0	1
other	51	11	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Lucas County

183 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.65 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	1	0	2
HARDING	2	0	0	0	2
JERUSALEM	13	0	0	0	13
MONCLOVA	32	5	0	1	38
OREGON	4	0	0	0	4
PROVIDENCE	19	2	0	0	21
RICHFIELD	11	0	0	0	11
SPENCER	8	0	0	0	8
SPRINGFIELD	10	3	1	0	14
SWANTON	13	3	3	2	21
SYLVANIA	17	3	4	0	24
WASHINGTON	1	1	0	0	2
WATERVILLE	21	2	0	0	23

MADISON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Madison County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Madison County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Madison County (average 0.38 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MADISON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MADISON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	100	4	4	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	58	1	1	0
1800's	0	1	1	0
1900-1949	19	0	0	0
1950-1970	25	0	0	0
after 1970	14	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1957	1860	1890	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	66	1	3	0
< 50 ft.	7	1	2	0
50 - 100 ft.	24	0	1	0
over 100 ft.	35	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	111	18	47	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	78	2	3	0
yes	44	1	2	0
no	34	1	1	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	87	3	4	0
yes	53	1	2	0
no	34	2	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	88	4	4	0
yes	25	1	0	0
no	63	3	4	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	88	4	4	0
yes	52	3	3	0
no	36	1	1	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	97	4	4	1
livestock	47	1	1	0
other	8	1	0	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Madison County

109 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.38 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	1	2
CANAAN	6	0	0	0	6
DARBY	2	0	0	0	2
DEERCREEK	5	1	0	0	6
FAIRFIELD	10	0	0	0	10
JEFFERSON	7	0	0	0	7
MONROE	2	0	0	0	2
OAK RUN	8	1	0	0	9
PAINT	1	0	0	0	1
PIKE	5	0	0	0	5
PLEASANT	13	0	0	0	13
RANGE	10	1	1	0	12
SOMERFORD	4	0	1	0	5
STOKES	15	1	2	0	18
UNION	11	0	0	0	11

MAHONING COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Mahoning County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Mahoning County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Mahoning County (average 0.40 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MAHONING COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MAHONING COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	360	43	10	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	264	26	2	1
1800's	0	2	0	0
1900-1949	35	7	1	1
1950-1970	120	10	0	0
after 1970	109	7	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1947	1942	1900
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	263	26	5	2
< 50 ft.	9	6	1	1
50 - 100 ft.	107	11	4	1
over 100 ft.	147	9	0	0
SPRINGS	3	4	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	130	102	63	47
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	320	34	5	3
yes	213	13	2	3
no	107	21	3	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	329	38	7	3
yes	226	26	5	1
no	103	12	2	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	333	38	7	3
yes	57	6	4	1
no	276	32	3	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	328	38	6	3
yes	141	18	4	3
no	187	20	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	340	39	9	3
livestock	77	6	2	1
other	82	13	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Mahoning County

417 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.40 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	1	0	0	2
AUSTINTOWN	2	3	1	0	6
BEAVER	44	6	4	1	55
BERLIN	21	2	1	0	24
BOARDMAN	2	1	0	0	3
CANFIELD	76	7	0	0	83
COITSVILLE	1	0	0	0	1
ELLSWORTH	31	2	1	0	34
GOSHEN	35	1	0	1	37
GREEN	68	12	0	0	80
JACKSON	8	0	1	0	9
MILTON	12	1	1	0	14
POLAND	14	3	0	0	17
SMITH	8	1	0	0	9
SPRINGFIELD	36	3	1	2	42
YOUNGSTOWN	1	0	0	0	1

MARION COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JULY 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Marion County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Marion County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Marion County (average 0.22 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MARION COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

MARION COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	65	1	1	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	31	1	0	0
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	9	0	0	0
1950-1970	11	1	0	0
after 1970	10	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1951	1967	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	38	1	0	1
< 50 ft.	6	0	0	1
50 - 100 ft.	21	1	0	0
over 100 ft.	11	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	87	58	0	25
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	53	1	0	1
yes	35	0	0	1
no	18	1	0	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	55	1	0	1
yes	40	1	0	1
no	15	0	0	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	55	1	0	1
yes	12	0	0	0
no	43	1	0	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	56	1	0	1
yes	42	0	0	1
no	14	1	0	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	61	1	0	1
livestock	18	0	0	0
other	9	0	0	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Marion County

68 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.22 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BIG ISLAND	8	0	0	0	8
BOWLING GREE	11	0	0	0	11
CLARIDON	3	0	1	1	5
GRAND	4	0	0	0	4
GRAND PRAIRI	9	1	0	0	10
GREEN CAMP	1	0	0	0	1
MARION	4	0	0	0	4
MONTGOMERY	9	0	0	0	9
PLEASANT	9	0	0	0	9
PROSPECT	1	0	0	0	1
RICHLAND	3	0	0	0	3
SALT ROCK	2	0	0	0	2
WALDO	1	0	0	0	1

MEDINA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APR 1987, APR 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Medina County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Medina County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Medina County (average 0.93 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MEDINA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MEDINA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	136	29	13	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	96	16	5	2
1800's	1	2	0	1
1900-1949	10	6	3	1
1950-1970	35	5	2	0
after 1970	50	3	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1967	1940	1942	1885
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	94	14	7	2
< 50 ft.	8	9	6	2
50 - 100 ft.	54	3	1	0
over 100 ft.	32	2	0	0
SPRINGS	1	0	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	101	62	25	22
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	108	20	10	2
yes	86	13	3	1
no	22	7	7	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	113	19	11	2
yes	80	12	4	0
no	33	7	7	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	115	21	11	2
yes	28	4	4	1
no	87	17	7	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	115	22	11	2
yes	55	12	6	2
no	60	10	5	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	112	23	12	2
livestock	39	4	5	3
other	49	11	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Medina County

182 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.93 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BRUNSWICK HI	3	0	1	0	4
CHATHAM	3	0	1	0	4
GRANGER	12	1	0	0	13
GUILFORD	16	0	1	0	17
HARRISVILLE	6	0	1	0	7
HINCKLEY	8	1	1	0	10
HOMER	2	2	0	0	4
LAFAYETTE	7	2	2	0	11
LITCHFIELD	5	0	0	1	6
LIVERPOOL	0	2	2	0	4
MEDINA	40	12	2	1	55
MONTVILLE	8	1	0	0	9
SHARON	3	1	1	0	5
WADSWORTH	2	1	0	0	3
WESTFIELD	6	1	0	1	8
YORK	15	5	1	1	22

MEIGS COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DECEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Meigs County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Meigs County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Meigs County (average 2.83 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MEIGS COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MEIGS COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	8	2	2	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	4	0	1	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	0	0	1	0
1950-1970	2	0	0	0
after 1970	2	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1974	0	1948	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	3	0	1	1
< 50 ft.	0	0	0	1
50 - 100 ft.	1	0	1	0
over 100 ft.	2	0	0	0
SPRINGS	2	1	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	145	0	100	27
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	4	1	1	0
yes	1	0	1	0
no	3	1	0	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	6	1	2	1
yes	3	0	0	1
no	3	1	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	6	1	2	1
yes	3	0	1	0
no	3	1	1	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	5	1	2	1
yes	4	0	0	1
no	1	1	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	7	2	1	1
livestock	2	1	1	0
other	1	0	0	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Meigs County

13 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.83 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
CHESTER	1	0	1	0	2
COLUMBIA	0	1	0	0	1
LEBANON	1	1	0	0	2
OLIVE	1	0	0	0	1
RUTLAND	3	0	0	0	3
SALEM	1	0	0	1	2
SUTTON	1	0	1	0	2

MERCER COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Mercer County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Mercer County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Mercer County (average 0.11 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MERCER COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	96	4	1	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	44	3	0	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	15	0	0	0
1950-1970	13	3	0	0
after 1970	16	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1956	1965	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	49	3	0	0
< 50 ft.	1	0	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	17	0	0	0
over 100 ft.	31	3	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	131	144	0	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	81	4	0	0
yes	57	2	0	0
no	24	2	0	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	84	4	1	0
yes	67	2	0	0
no	17	2	1	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	88	4	1	0
yes	37	0	0	0
no	51	4	1	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	87	4	1	0
yes	75	1	0	0
no	12	3	1	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	95	4	1	0
livestock	39	0	0	0
other	23	0	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Mercer County

101 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.11 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
BLACK CREEK	2	1	0	0	3
BUTLER	9	0	0	0	9
CENTER	12	0	0	0	12
DUBLIN	12	2	0	0	14
FRANKLIN	19	1	0	0	20
GRANVILLE	3	0	0	0	3
HOPEWELL	2	0	0	0	2
JEFFERSON	7	0	0	0	7
LIBERTY	6	0	0	0	6
MARION	11	0	0	0	11
UNION	8	0	1	0	9
WASHINGTON	4	0	0	0	4

MIAMI COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOV 1987, FEB 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Miami County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Miami County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Miami County (average 2.52 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MIAMI COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MIAMI COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	176	28	37	21
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	115	16	18	12
1800's	1	0	1	2
1900-1949	31	0	1	2
1950-1970	43	10	8	5
after 1970	40	6	8	3
<u>average year drilled</u>	1961	1966	1963	1945
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	129	18	22	14
< 50 ft.	31	4	10	7
50 - 100 ft.	71	11	7	4
over 100 ft.	27	3	5	3
SPRINGS	0	0	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	79	73	67	57
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	168	25	35	19
yes	116	17	24	13
no	52	8	11	6
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	169	25	34	17
yes	111	15	18	5
no	58	10	16	12
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	173	26	36	19
yes	40	5	2	2
no	133	21	34	17
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	173	26	36	19
yes	129	13	23	14
no	44	13	13	5
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	168	25	37	20
livestock	50	12	6	5
other	42	5	9	6

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Miami County

262 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.52 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	1	0	0	3
BETHEL	9	3	8	4	24
BROWN	8	0	0	0	8
CONCORD	20	2	4	1	27
ELIZABETH	3	0	4	2	9
LOSTCREEK	12	1	0	1	14
MONROE	15	6	5	4	30
NEWBERRY	23	5	2	1	31
NEWTON	19	4	3	2	28
SPRINGCREEK	20	0	0	0	20
STAUNTON	14	0	2	2	18
UNION	17	6	6	3	32
WASHINGTON	14	0	3	1	18

MONROE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Monroe County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Monroe County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Monroe County (average 2.80 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MONROE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MONROE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	11	18	6	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	4	4	3	3
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	0	1	2	1
1950-1970	2	2	1	2
after 1970	2	1	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1978	1958	1930	1942
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	5	11	3	3
< 50 ft.	2	4	3	1
50 - 100 ft.	0	6	0	2
over 100 ft.	3	1	0	0
SPRINGS	3	2	1	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	77	67	36	63
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	6	14	4	4
yes	4	4	1	2
no	2	10	3	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	10	15	5	4
yes	1	8	1	2
no	9	7	4	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	10	15	5	4
yes	3	6	3	3
no	7	9	2	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	10	15	5	4
yes	4	10	3	4
no	6	5	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	7	11	3	2
livestock	4	7	3	2
other	1	3	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Monroe County

39 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.80 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BENTON	2	0	0	0	2
CENTER	2	1	3	0	6
FRANKLIN	1	1	0	0	2
GREEN	0	1	0	1	2
LEE	2	5	0	0	7
MALAGA	1	3	1	1	6
OHIO	0	4	0	0	4
SALEM	0	1	1	0	2
SENECA	0	1	0	0	1
SUMMIT	1	0	0	0	1
SUNSBURY	1	1	1	2	5
WAYNE	1	0	0	0	1

MONTGOMERY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MAY 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Montgomery County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Montgomery County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Montgomery County (average 1.80 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MONTGOMERY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MONTGOMERY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	167	37	34	10
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	101	8	18	2
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	21	0	4	0
1950-1970	54	4	5	2
after 1970	26	4	9	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1971	1962	1966
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	116	18	23	6
< 50 ft.	23	10	5	4
50 - 100 ft.	77	8	13	2
over 100 ft.	16	0	5	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	70	47	69	45
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	148	27	28	6
yes	113	11	14	1
no	35	16	14	5
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	145	29	30	8
yes	92	16	21	4
no	53	13	9	4
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	151	30	30	8
yes	14	11	5	2
no	137	19	25	6
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	149	29	30	8
yes	90	19	21	6
no	59	10	9	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	154	34	33	9
livestock	21	8	6	3
other	57	5	10	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Montgomery County

248 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.80 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BUTLER	4	2	2	1	9
CLAY	48	9	9	1	67
GERMAN	8	4	4	1	17
JACKSON	11	2	1	0	14
JEFFERSON	8	1	1	0	10
MAD RIVER	0	0	1	0	1
MADISON	12	3	0	0	15
MIAMI	3	1	3	0	7
PERRY	51	13	6	3	73
RANDOLPH	16	2	6	3	27
WASHINGTON	1	0	1	0	2
WAYNE	5	0	0	1	6

MORGAN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Morgan County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Morgan County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Morgan County (average 2.56 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MORGAN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MORGAN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	46	85	48	5
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	20	36	18	2
1800's	0	2	0	1
1900-1949	0	7	1	0
1950-1970	6	10	5	1
after 1970	14	17	12	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1974	1956	1970	1884
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	27	48	30	5
< 50 ft.	7	26	21	2
50 - 100 ft.	15	21	7	2
over 100 ft.	5	1	2	1
SPRINGS	1	4	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	74	51	48	52
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	34	63	34	4
yes	19	36	17	2
no	15	27	17	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	38	65	40	5
yes	16	31	22	0
no	22	34	18	5
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	37	68	39	5
yes	4	10	3	2
no	33	58	36	3
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	38	67	39	5
yes	8	15	15	3
no	30	52	24	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	39	80	45	5
livestock	3	8	7	2
other	17	28	14	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Morgan County

184 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.56 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	4	1	1	0	6
BLOOM	2	6	1	0	9
BRISTOL	0	0	1	0	1
CENTER	0	2	1	0	3
DEERFIELD	1	7	3	0	11
HOMER	0	0	1	0	1
MALTA	4	7	4	0	15
MARION	8	9	7	1	25
MEIGSVILLE	5	10	2	0	17
MORGAN	2	10	0	1	13
PENN	2	6	5	1	14
UNION	0	4	3	0	7
WINDSOR	17	21	18	2	58
YORK	1	2	1	0	4

MORROW COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Morrow County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Morrow County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Morrow County (average 0.80 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MORROW COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MORROW COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	60	7	1	2
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	30	4	1	2
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	7	0	0	0
1950-1970	13	2	0	0
after 1970	10	2	1	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1967	1980	1982
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	39	4	1	2
< 50 ft.	13	3	1	2
50 - 100 ft.	13	0	0	0
over 100 ft.	13	1	0	0
SPRINGS	0	1	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	92	72	17	31
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	54	7	0	2
yes	30	5	0	1
no	24	2	0	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	52	7	1	2
yes	32	4	0	1
no	20	3	1	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	53	7	1	1
yes	15	0	0	0
no	38	7	1	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	54	7	1	2
yes	33	7	1	0
no	21	0	0	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	57	7	1	2
livestock	22	3	1	1
other	21	1	0	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Morrow County

70 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.80 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
BENNINGTON	6	0	0	1	7
CANAAN	3	0	0	0	3
CANNON	1	0	0	0	1
CARDINGTON	0	2	0	0	2
CHESTER	8	0	0	0	8
CONGRESS	14	1	0	0	15
FRANKLIN	5	0	0	0	5
GILEAD	3	0	0	0	3
HARMONY	2	0	0	0	2
LINCOLN	4	0	0	0	4
PERRY	1	1	0	0	2
PERU	1	0	1	0	2
S. BLOOMFIEL	1	0	0	0	1
S. BLOOMFIELD	5	0	0	0	5
TROY	2	2	0	0	4
WASHINGTON	1	1	0	0	2
WESTFIELD	2	0	0	1	3

MUSKINGUM COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Muskingum County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Muskingum County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Muskingum County (average 2.12 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

MUSKINGUM COUNTY

Nitrate as N

MUSKINGUM COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	235	145	72	22
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	160	91	40	11
1800's	0	1	2	0
1900-1949	6	16	9	6
1950-1970	68	37	11	5
after 1970	86	37	18	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1971	1962	1957	1950
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	163	91	43	16
< 50 ft.	15	25	19	6
50 - 100 ft.	89	37	19	6
over 100 ft.	59	29	5	4
SPRINGS	1	12	10	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	121	92	60	67
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	211	122	55	19
yes	134	62	29	6
no	77	60	26	13
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	209	134	62	18
yes	113	64	28	10
no	96	70	34	8
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	211	133	63	19
yes	21	22	13	4
no	190	111	50	15
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	212	134	63	19
yes	55	41	32	8
no	157	93	31	11
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	217	128	63	20
livestock	41	26	17	4
other	65	42	29	5

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Muskingum County

474 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.12 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	4	1	0	0	5
ADAMS	2	2	1	1	6
BLUE ROCK	5	3	1	1	10
BRUSH CREEK	9	1	1	1	12
CASS	17	2	0	0	19
CLAY	1	1	0	0	2
FALLS	21	11	4	2	38
HARRISON	8	2	2	1	13
HIGHLAND	1	8	4	0	13
HOPEWELL	26	10	1	2	39
JACKSON	3	5	0	0	8
LICKING	14	4	1	0	19
MADISON	5	4	1	1	11
MEIGS	2	2	5	0	9
MONROE	6	1	1	0	8
MUSKINGUM	24	10	4	0	38
NEWTON	14	12	3	0	29
PERRY	7	3	2	3	15
RICH HILL	2	5	3	0	10
SALEM	4	3	4	0	11
SALT CREEK	13	9	4	1	27
SPRINGFIELD	7	2	2	0	11
UNION	5	10	2	0	17
WASHINGTON	18	13	6	0	37
WAYNE	17	21	20	9	67

OTTAWA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Ottawa County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Ottawa County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Ottawa County (average 0.22 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

OTTAWA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

OTTAWA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	171	6	7	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	97	4	3	0
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	16	1	0	0
1950-1970	41	2	1	0
after 1970	39	1	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1962	1958	1974	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	111	4	5	0
< 50 ft.	14	1	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	84	3	5	0
over 100 ft.	13	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	76	70	74	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	151	6	5	0
yes	122	3	4	0
no	29	3	1	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	154	5	5	0
yes	127	2	3	0
no	27	3	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	155	6	5	0
yes	19	0	1	0
no	136	6	4	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	154	6	5	0
yes	125	3	1	0
no	29	3	4	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	163	6	7	0
livestock	18	0	1	0
other	35	1	3	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Ottawa County

184 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.22 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
ALLEN	16	1	0	0	17
BAY	2	0	0	0	2
BENTON	37	1	0	0	38
CARROLL	16	0	0	0	16
CATAWBA	3	2	2	0	7
CLAY	19	0	4	0	23
DANBURY	3	0	0	0	3
ERIE	1	0	0	0	1
HARRIS	36	2	0	0	38
PORTAGE	0	0	1	0	1
SALEM	38	0	0	0	38

PAULDING COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Paulding County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Paulding County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Paulding County (average 0.06 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

PAULDING COUNTY

Nitrate as N

PAULDING COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	321	8	2	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	170	2	0	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	32	0	0	0
1950-1970	75	0	0	0
after 1970	63	2	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1962	1981	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	200	3	2	0
< 50 ft.	79	1	1	0
50 - 100 ft.	105	2	1	0
over 100 ft.	16	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	61	45	50	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	281	5	2	0
yes	226	4	2	0
no	55	1	0	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	284	5	2	0
yes	207	3	1	0
no	77	2	1	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	286	5	2	0
yes	40	1	1	0
no	246	4	1	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	286	5	2	0
yes	223	3	2	0
no	63	2	0	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	312	6	0	0
livestock	45	0	0	0
other	80	3	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Paulding County

331 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.06 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	0	0	0	3
AUGLAIZE	9	0	0	0	9
BENTON	28	0	0	0	28
BLUECREEK	43	1	0	0	44
BROWN	29	1	0	0	30
CARRYALL	45	0	0	0	45
CRANE	24	1	2	0	27
EMERALD	16	0	0	0	16
HARRISON	33	1	0	0	34
JACKSON	20	1	0	0	21
LATTY	25	0	0	0	25
PAULDING	34	2	0	0	36
WASHINGTON	12	1	0	0	13

PERRY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JULY 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Perry County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Perry County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Perry County (average 1.47 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

PERRY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

PERRY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	70	61	23	2
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	47	25	12	1
1800's	0	1	1	0
1900-1949	1	0	1	0
1950-1970	17	8	3	0
after 1970	29	16	7	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1973	1969	1963	1975
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	53	35	11	1
< 50 ft.	6	7	6	1
50 - 100 ft.	30	18	2	0
over 100 ft.	17	10	3	0
SPRINGS	1	8	3	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	108	101	68	15
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	62	50	20	2
yes	48	28	11	1
no	14	22	9	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	62	54	21	2
yes	26	25	9	0
no	36	29	12	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	55	21	2
yes	5	7	6	1
no	58	48	15	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	63	52	20	2
yes	22	22	8	2
no	41	30	12	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	64	56	21	2
livestock	16	19	9	1
other	26	10	5	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Perry County

156 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.47 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	0	0	0	3
BEARFIELD	3	5	0	0	8
CLAYTON	2	3	0	0	5
HARRISON	1	2	0	0	3
HOPEWELL	9	7	1	0	17
JACKSON	9	12	5	2	28
MADISON	6	6	2	0	14
MONDAY CREEK	0	2	0	0	2
PIKE	6	4	2	0	12
PLEASANT	0	1	0	0	1
READING	16	17	8	0	41
SALT LICK	1	1	0	0	2
THORN	14	1	5	0	20

PICKAWAY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUL, DEC 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Pickaway County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Pickaway County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Pickaway County (average 1.31 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

PICKAWAY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

PICKAWAY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	130	19	13	9
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	81	9	5	1
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	13	1	1	1
1950-1970	28	3	2	0
after 1970	39	5	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1965	1954	1903
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	97	15	8	3
< 50 ft.	30	8	6	1
50 - 100 ft.	50	5	2	1
over 100 ft.	17	2	0	1
SPRINGS	0	0	0	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	73	53	37	93
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	111	16	11	5
yes	65	6	7	0
no	46	10	4	5
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	113	14	11	5
yes	64	7	3	3
no	49	7	8	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	114	16	11	6
yes	17	4	1	1
no	97	12	10	5
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	113	16	11	6
yes	71	12	7	3
no	42	4	4	3
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	118	18	13	9
livestock	19	3	3	2
other	54	2	6	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Pickaway County

171 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.31 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	1	2	5
CIRCLEVILLE	15	2	2	0	19
DARBY	2	0	0	1	3
DEER CREEK	11	2	1	1	15
HARRISON	5	1	0	0	6
JACKSON	5	1	1	1	8
MADISON	6	2	0	0	8
MONROE	2	2	1	4	9
MUHLENBERG	5	0	0	0	5
PERRY	8	1	0	0	9
PICKAWAY	20	3	2	0	25
SALT CREEK	10	3	1	0	14
SCIOTO	22	1	1	0	24
WALNUT	11	1	2	0	14
WASHINGTON	2	0	0	0	2
WAYNE	4	0	1	0	5

PORTAGE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APRIL 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Portage County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Portage County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Portage County (average 2.72 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

PORTAGE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

PORTAGE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	53	11	19	8
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	41	5	12	6
1800's	2	0	0	1
1900-1949	14	0	4	1
1950-1970	11	2	5	3
after 1970	14	3	3	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1952	1971	1957	1940
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	41	7	13	8
< 50 ft.	7	2	5	5
50 - 100 ft.	15	3	6	2
over 100 ft.	19	2	2	1
SPRINGS	0	0	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	104	71	62	61
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	44	8	15	8
yes	25	4	7	3
no	19	4	8	5
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	45	8	17	8
yes	35	3	11	3
no	10	5	6	5
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	46	7	17	8
yes	17	0	5	0
no	29	7	12	8
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	46	8	17	8
yes	29	5	9	6
no	17	3	8	2
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	47	11	17	8
livestock	24	7	6	4
other	8	1	3	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Portage County

91 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.72 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
ATWATER	1	1	2	0	4
AURORA	1	1	0	0	2
BRIMFIELD	5	0	0	0	5
DEERFIELD	5	0	0	0	5
EDINBURG	0	0	1	0	1
FRANKLIN	2	0	0	0	2
FREEDOM	8	2	4	3	17
HIRAM	4	2	3	2	11
NELSON	2	0	1	0	3
RANDOLPH	9	1	0	2	12
RAVENNA	3	0	0	0	3
ROOTSTOWN	0	0	3	1	4
SHALERSVILLE	8	2	4	0	14
STREETSBORO	1	0	0	0	1
SUFFIELD	4	0	0	0	4
WINDHAM	0	2	1	0	3

PREBLE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MAY 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Preble County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Preble County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Preble County (average 1.90 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

PREBLE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

PREBLE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	75	22	18	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	47	5	5	1
1800's	0	1	0	0
1900-1949	13	1	1	0
1950-1970	14	2	1	1
after 1970	20	1	3	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1926	1970	1958
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	63	13	9	3
< 50 ft.	22	8	8	2
50 - 100 ft.	33	5	1	1
over 100 ft.	8	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	68	47	28	42
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	68	16	13	4
yes	35	8	6	1
no	33	8	7	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	72	17	15	4
yes	40	7	6	2
no	32	10	9	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	73	19	14	4
yes	22	2	4	2
no	51	17	10	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	73	19	15	4
yes	51	10	10	3
no	22	9	5	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	68	19	14	2
livestock	23	7	5	2
other	20	4	8	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Preble County

119 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.90 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	2	0	0	3
DIXON	4	2	0	1	7
GASPER	4	1	0	0	5
GRATIS	0	0	0	1	1
HARRISON	7	3	0	0	10
ISRAEL	6	3	7	0	16
JACKSON	7	1	0	0	8
JEFFERSON	4	0	1	0	5
LANIER	8	1	5	1	15
MONROE	10	0	1	0	11
SOMERS	7	4	1	1	13
TWIN	6	4	2	0	12
WASHINGTON	11	1	1	0	13

PUTNAM COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Putnam County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Putnam County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Putnam County (average 0.20 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

PUTNAM COUNTY

Nitrate as N

PUTNAM COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	271	8	2	2
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	154	3	0	2
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	28	0	0	1
1950-1970	55	1	0	1
after 1970	71	2	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	1973	0	1927
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	186	4	0	2
< 50 ft.	55	3	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	101	1	0	1
over 100 ft.	30	0	0	1
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	87	32	0	108
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	236	5	0	2
yes	200	5	0	1
no	36	0	0	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	243	5	0	2
yes	170	4	0	1
no	73	1	0	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	240	5	0	2
yes	52	0	0	2
no	188	5	0	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	241	5	0	2
yes	179	3	0	2
no	62	2	0	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	258	7	0	2
livestock	61	1	0	2
other	50	2	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Putnam County

283 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.20 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	7	0	0	0	7
BLANCHARD	8	0	0	0	8
GREENSBURG	7	0	0	0	7
JACKSON	11	0	0	0	11
JENNINGS	8	0	0	0	8
LIBERTY	23	1	2	0	26
MONROE	31	0	0	0	31
MONTEREY	7	0	0	0	7
OTTAWA	32	0	0	1	33
PALMER	26	0	0	0	26
PERRY	13	1	0	0	14
PLEASANT	21	1	0	0	22
RILEY	5	0	0	0	5
SUGAR CREEK	38	3	0	1	42
UNION	21	1	0	0	22
VAN BUREN	13	1	0	0	14

RICHLAND COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Richland County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Richland County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Richland County (average 0.99 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

RICHLAND COUNTY

Nitrate as N

RICHLAND COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	72	42	10	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	47	20	5	0
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	8	1	2	0
1950-1970	21	13	2	0
after 1970	17	6	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1962	1962	1952	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	44	28	6	0
< 50 ft.	10	3	1	0
50 - 100 ft.	21	10	3	0
over 100 ft.	13	15	2	0
SPRINGS	0	1	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	106	124	100	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	59	36	7	0
yes	36	19	5	0
no	23	17	2	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	60	37	7	0
yes	40	19	5	0
no	20	18	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	61	37	7	0
yes	11	10	1	0
no	50	27	6	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	60	37	7	0
yes	32	18	5	0
no	28	19	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	70	39	10	1
livestock	20	10	4	1
other	22	11	4	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Richland County

125 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.99 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	2	0	1	6
BLOOMING GRO	1	1	1	0	3
BUTLER	11	0	0	0	11
CASS	4	2	0	0	6
FRANKLIN	5	2	0	0	7
JACKSON	7	0	0	0	7
JEFFERSON	1	6	2	0	9
MADISON	3	3	1	0	7
MIFFLIN	5	4	0	0	9
MONROE	3	2	0	0	5
PERRY	3	0	1	0	4
PLYMOUTH	2	1	0	0	3
SANDUSKY	3	0	1	0	4
SHARON	5	1	0	0	6
SPRINGFIELD	7	7	0	0	14
TROY	3	2	0	0	5
WASHINGTON	2	7	3	0	12
WELLER	2	1	1	0	4
WORTHINGTON	2	1	0	0	3

ROSS COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MAY, JUN 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Ross County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Ross County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Ross County (average 2.67 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

ROSS COUNTY

Nitrate as N

ROSS COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	94	31	37	13
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	69	18	15	7
1800's	1	2	2	2
1900-1949	14	1	5	4
1950-1970	31	4	6	0
after 1970	23	11	2	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1962	1928	1893
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	69	23	21	10
< 50 ft.	13	16	16	8
50 - 100 ft.	37	5	1	0
over 100 ft.	19	2	4	2
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	96	49	43	43
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	78	27	28	13
yes	38	13	6	5
no	40	14	22	8
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	81	29	30	13
yes	44	16	16	10
no	37	13	14	3
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	80	29	30	13
yes	27	7	5	4
no	53	22	25	9
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	81	29	30	13
yes	47	20	19	10
no	34	9	11	3
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	90	30	36	13
livestock	37	10	15	5
other	17	3	7	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Ross County

175 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.67 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BUCKSKIN	15	5	3	1	24
COLERAIN	1	0	2	1	4
CONCORD	20	4	7	1	32
DEERFIELD	9	3	5	2	19
GREEN	11	6	4	1	22
HARRISON	2	1	0	0	3
HUNTINGTON	2	1	2	0	5
JEFFERSON	1	1	0	0	2
LIBERTY	8	0	5	2	15
PAINT	3	1	2	0	6
PAXTON	3	0	0	0	3
SCIOTO	6	1	0	0	7
SPRINGFIELD	2	3	3	0	8
TWIN	3	2	2	2	9
UNION	8	3	2	3	16

SANDUSKY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DEC 1986 - FEB 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Sandusky County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Sandusky County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Sandusky County (average 0.71 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

SANDUSKY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

SANDUSKY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	155	15	10	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	101	9	5	3
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	14	2	0	1
1950-1970	46	2	0	2
after 1970	41	5	5	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	1968	1983	1942
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	87	10	5	2
< 50 ft.	4	2	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	61	4	3	0
over 100 ft.	22	4	2	2
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	91	94	113	139
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	136	12	9	3
yes	97	9	9	2
no	39	3	0	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	140	14	9	3
yes	93	8	5	0
no	47	6	4	3
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	140	14	9	3
yes	9	0	0	0
no	131	14	9	3
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	143	13	9	3
yes	97	5	7	2
no	46	8	2	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	151	14	9	3
livestock	10	0	1	1
other	36	2	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Sandusky County

183 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.71 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
BALLVILLE	41	4	0	0	45
GREEN CREEK	27	1	0	0	28
JACKSON	12	1	1	0	14
MADISON	7	0	1	0	8
RICE	5	0	0	0	5
RILEY	10	0	0	1	11
SANDUSKY	19	3	1	0	23
SCOTT	5	0	2	1	8
TOWNSEND	5	1	0	0	6
WASHINGTON	11	0	0	0	11
WOODVILLE	3	3	0	0	6
YORK	8	2	5	1	16

SENECA COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOV, DEC 1986

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Seneca County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Seneca County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Seneca County (average 0.72 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

SENECA COUNTY

Nitrate as N

SENECA COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	218	23	16	4
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	125	15	8	2
1800's	3	0	0	2
1900-1949	14	3	2	0
1950-1970	47	4	5	0
after 1970	61	8	1	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	1964	1959	1883
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	124	16	11	3
< 50 ft.	18	3	1	3
50 - 100 ft.	74	9	7	0
over 100 ft.	32	4	3	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	84	84	95	22
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	176	20	15	3
yes	97	10	6	0
no	79	10	9	3
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	187	21	15	3
yes	138	18	12	2
no	49	3	3	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	187	21	15	3
yes	29	4	4	0
no	158	17	11	3
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	190	21	15	3
yes	137	16	9	3
no	53	5	6	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	190	18	13	2
livestock	35	2	2	0
other	48	2	7	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Seneca County

261 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.72 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	6	2	0	0	8
ADAMS	10	2	0	0	12
BIG SPRING	34	3	3	0	40
BLOOM	1	2	0	0	3
CLINTON	26	1	1	0	28
EDEN	16	1	2	0	19
HOPEWELL	38	1	0	0	39
JACKSON	2	0	0	0	2
LIBERTY	2	4	2	0	8
LOUDON	25	0	0	0	25
PLEASANT	17	0	0	0	17
REED	2	1	0	0	3
SCIPIO	10	3	1	0	14
SENECA	21	0	1	2	24
THOMPSON	5	2	4	0	11
VENICE	3	1	2	2	8

SHELBY COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MARCH 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Shelby County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Shelby County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Shelby County (average 0.21 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

SHELBY COUNTY

Nitrate as N

SHELBY COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	259	13	6	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	148	4	2	0
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	38	2	1	0
1950-1970	56	1	1	0
after 1970	54	1	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1960	1951	1949	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	177	7	3	0
< 50 ft.	23	1	2	0
50 - 100 ft.	68	3	1	0
over 100 ft.	86	3	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	1	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	105	115	57	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	236	12	5	1
yes	162	9	1	1
no	74	3	4	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	240	12	5	1
yes	162	11	3	1
no	78	1	2	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	242	11	5	1
yes	81	2	1	1
no	161	9	4	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	243	12	5	1
yes	167	10	4	0
no	76	2	1	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	253	12	6	1
livestock	112	4	3	0
other	49	1	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Shelby County

279 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.21 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	1	0	0	2
CLINTON	9	0	1	0	10
CYNTHIAN	17	1	0	0	18
DINSMORE	23	2	0	0	25
FRANKLIN	18	0	0	0	18
GREEN	19	1	0	1	21
JACKSON	23	0	1	0	24
LORAMIE	18	1	1	0	20
MCLEAN	21	0	0	0	21
ORANGE	9	1	0	0	10
PERRY	19	0	0	0	19
SALEM	15	2	0	0	17
TURTLE CREEK	14	0	0	0	14
VAN BUREN	32	2	0	0	34
WASHINGTON	21	2	3	0	26

STARK COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JANUARY 1989

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Stark County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Stark County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Stark County (average 0.53 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

STARK COUNTY

Nitrate as N

STARK COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	485	45	29	5
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	387	27	19	2
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	51	5	6	1
1950-1970	192	10	8	0
after 1970	144	12	5	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1964	1965	1958	1950
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	363	30	19	3
< 50 ft.	33	6	10	3
50 - 100 ft.	172	15	6	0
over 100 ft.	158	9	3	0
SPRINGS	2	1	2	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	117	87	60	29
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	442	34	25	5
yes	292	18	8	3
no	150	16	17	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	465	40	26	5
yes	305	23	15	3
no	160	17	11	2
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	464	40	27	5
yes	36	3	0	2
no	428	37	27	3
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	464	39	27	5
yes	170	11	8	4
no	294	28	19	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	468	43	27	3
livestock	40	3	2	1
other	148	19	10	4

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Stark County

564 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.53 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	1	0	0	2
BETHLEHEM	7	3	0	0	10
CANTON	28	3	2	0	33
JACKSON	36	4	3	1	44
LAKE	95	4	5	0	104
LAWRENCE	26	4	1	0	31
LEXINGTON	8	1	1	0	10
MARLBORO	31	3	0	0	34
NIMISHILLEN	49	4	3	0	56
OSNABURG	22	1	4	0	27
PARIS	21	3	4	2	30
PERRY	26	3	0	0	29
PIKE	4	0	0	0	4
PLAIN	91	9	4	0	104
SANDY	7	0	0	0	7
SUGAR CREEK	4	1	0	0	5
TUSCARAWAS	11	1	1	0	13
WASHINGTON	18	0	1	2	21

TRUMBULL COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUN 1987, JUN 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Trumbull County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Trumbull County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Trumbull County (average 0.46 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

TRUMBULL COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

TRUMBULL COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	249	25	10	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	154	13	3	0
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	40	2	0	0
1950-1970	61	8	1	0
after 1970	52	3	2	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1959	1962	1976	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	168	13	6	0
< 50 ft.	16	3	2	0
50 - 100 ft.	100	6	2	0
over 100 ft.	52	4	2	0
SPRINGS	0	1	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	100	83	112	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	210	17	10	1
yes	154	12	6	0
no	56	5	4	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	215	20	10	2
yes	147	13	8	1
no	68	7	2	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	218	19	10	2
yes	48	3	5	2
no	170	16	5	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	219	20	10	2
yes	106	11	4	1
no	113	9	6	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	229	19	9	2
livestock	67	6	2	2
other	64	4	2	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Trumbull County

287 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.45 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
BAZETTA	15	1	0	0	16
BLOOMFIELD	3	0	0	0	3
BRACEVILLE	31	3	1	1	36
BRISTOL	6	0	1	0	7
BROOKFIELD	1	0	0	0	1
CHAMPION	9	0	0	0	9
FARMINGTON	9	0	0	0	9
FOWLER	9	0	2	0	11
GREENE	11	1	0	0	12
GUSTAVUS	25	1	1	0	27
HARTFORD	14	2	2	0	18
HOWLAND	4	0	0	0	4
JOHNSTON	22	1	1	0	24
KINSMAN	12	4	0	0	16
LIBERTY	11	2	0	0	13
LORDSTOWN	6	1	0	0	7
MECCA	8	0	0	0	8
MESOPOTAMIA	1	1	1	0	3
NEWTON	17	3	0	1	21
SOUTHINGTON	15	1	0	0	16
VERNON	6	0	0	0	6
VIENNA	8	3	1	1	13
WARREN	5	1	0	0	6
WEATHERSFIEL	1	0	0	0	1

TUSCARAWAS COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DECEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Tuscarawas County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Tuscarawas County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Tuscarawas County (average 1.95 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

TUSCARAWAS COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

TUSCARAWAS COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	246	72	60	22
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	171	32	29	9
1800's	1	0	0	0
1900-1949	19	1	6	1
1950-1970	76	19	8	5
after 1970	75	12	15	3
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1968	1964	1964
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	182	27	29	12
< 50 ft.	13	7	22	9
50 - 100 ft.	75	11	6	3
over 100 ft.	94	9	1	0
SPRINGS	18	32	15	4
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	146	94	40	39
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	207	49	45	16
yes	148	23	27	5
no	59	26	18	11
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	224	64	55	20
yes	144	29	32	16
no	80	35	23	4
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	230	63	53	19
yes	39	11	9	3
no	191	52	44	16
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	225	66	53	19
yes	96	33	30	15
no	129	33	23	4
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	232	58	55	20
livestock	62	28	10	7
other	41	21	15	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Tuscarawas County

400 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.95 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	0	1	1	0	2
AUBURN	13	3	6	0	22
BUCKS	6	4	5	2	17
CLAY	5	2	2	3	12
DOVER	59	8	5	0	72
FAIRFIELD	14	1	0	0	15
FRANKLIN	6	1	4	1	12
GOSHEN	30	10	10	0	50
JEFFERSON	8	5	1	0	14
LAWRENCE	17	3	1	0	21
MILL	4	1	1	0	6
OXFORD	12	4	3	4	23
PERRY	1	1	0	0	2
RUSH	3	2	0	0	5
SALEM	8	3	8	3	22
SANDY	2	0	2	1	5
SUGAR CREEK	10	3	0	0	13
UNION	1	3	0	0	4
WARREN	7	3	1	0	11
WARWICK	10	3	8	7	28
WASHINGTON	3	1	0	0	4
WAYNE	5	0	1	0	6
YORK	22	10	1	1	34

UNION COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JUNE 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Union County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Union County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Union County (average 1.27 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

UNION COUNTY

Nitrate as N

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

UNION COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	38	2	1	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	30	2	1	2
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	8	0	1	0
1950-1970	9	1	0	0
after 1970	13	1	0	2
<u>average year drilled</u>	1959	1979	1920	1977
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	33	2	1	3
< 50 ft.	8	0	1	0
50 - 100 ft.	17	2	0	3
over 100 ft.	8	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	81	79	26	73
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	36	2	1	3
yes	24	2	0	3
no	12	0	1	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	37	2	1	3
yes	33	1	1	0
no	4	1	0	3
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	36	2	1	3
yes	14	1	0	1
no	22	1	1	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	37	2	1	3
yes	30	2	1	2
no	7	0	0	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	37	2	1	3
livestock	20	2	0	1
other	5	0	0	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Union County

44 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.27 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
ALLEN	1	0	0	0	1
CLAIBOURNE	1	0	0	0	1
DARBY	6	0	0	0	6
DOVER	2	0	0	0	2
JEROME	3	0	0	0	3
LEESBURG	2	0	0	0	2
LIBERTY	2	0	0	0	2
MILLCREEK	1	0	0	1	2
PARIS	2	0	0	0	2
TAYLOR	2	0	0	0	2
UNION	3	2	1	2	8
WASHINGTON	4	0	0	0	4
YORK	8	0	0	0	8

VAN WERT COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APRIL 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Van Wert County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Van Wert County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Van Wert County (average 0.17 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

VAN WERT COUNTY

Nitrate as N

No well location data for this county

• 0 - 0.3 mg/L

● 0.3 - 3.0 mg/L

● 3.0 - 10.0 mg/L

● more than 10.0 mg/L

VAN WERT COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	484	20	4	1
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	270	8	2	0
1800's	3	0	0	0
1900-1949	80	2	1	0
1950-1970	73	4	1	0
after 1970	114	2	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1958	1952	1945	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	293	6	2	1
< 50 ft.	67	3	2	1
50 - 100 ft.	141	3	0	0
over 100 ft.	85	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	86	51	32	40
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	420	17	4	1
yes	300	11	3	0
no	120	6	1	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	432	18	4	1
yes	332	8	4	0
no	100	10	0	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	433	17	4	1
yes	83	2	1	0
no	350	15	3	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	434	18	4	1
yes	344	13	4	1
no	90	5	0	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	465	13	3	0
livestock	78	6	0	0
other	129	10	4	1

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Van Wert County

509 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.17 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	0	0	0	3
HARRISON	54	1	0	0	55
HOAGLIN	18	3	0	0	21
JACKSON	26	5	1	0	32
JENNINGS	22	0	1	0	23
LIBERTY	29	0	0	0	29
PLEASANT	73	2	0	0	75
RIDGE	41	1	0	0	42
TULLY	35	1	0	0	36
UNION	46	4	1	0	51
WASHINGTON	17	1	0	0	18
WILLSHIRE	72	2	1	0	75

WARREN COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED NOVEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Warren County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Warren County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Warren County (average 2.84 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

WARREN COUNTY

Nitrate as N

WARREN COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	64	59	26	19
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	31	26	6	2
1800's	0	5	0	1
1900-1949	3	6	2	0
1950-1970	14	11	1	1
after 1970	14	4	3	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1939	1948	1914
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	41	33	15	11
< 50 ft.	11	22	14	9
50 - 100 ft.	27	8	1	2
over 100 ft.	3	3	0	0
SPRINGS	1	1	2	1
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	65	46	28	26
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	51	44	21	12
yes	22	19	6	3
no	29	25	15	9
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	54	49	23	15
yes	23	18	9	9
no	31	31	14	6
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	54	49	23	16
yes	9	8	3	7
no	45	41	20	9
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	55	49	23	15
yes	22	22	15	11
no	33	27	8	4
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	51	47	18	11
livestock	14	17	7	7
other	26	17	10	4

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Warren County

168 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.84 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	1	0	0	2
CLEAR CREEK	9	5	1	4	19
DEERFIELD	9	2	4	0	15
FRANKLIN	5	2	2	1	10
HAMILTON	1	3	1	1	6
HARLAN	5	3	2	1	11
MASSIE	0	4	0	1	5
SALEM	4	11	4	1	20
TURTLE CREEK	21	15	6	6	48
UNION	4	4	2	0	10
WASHINGTON	2	2	2	3	9
WAYNE	3	7	2	1	13

WASHINGTON COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED SEPTEMBER 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Washington County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Washington County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Washington County (average 1.78 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

WASHINGTON COUNTY

Nitrate as N

WASHINGTON COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	75	70	33	2
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	47	30	20	0
1800's	0	2	1	0
1900-1949	4	6	3	0
1950-1970	23	5	9	0
after 1970	20	17	7	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1967	1954	1958	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	54	38	21	1
< 50 ft.	14	15	4	1
50 - 100 ft.	24	12	14	0
over 100 ft.	16	11	3	0
SPRINGS	2	4	2	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	87	71	71	25
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	67	49	26	1
yes	31	19	13	0
no	36	30	13	1
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	70	57	29	1
yes	30	13	15	1
no	40	44	14	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	69	56	30	1
yes	5	12	1	0
no	64	44	29	1
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	70	56	31	1
yes	26	17	17	1
no	44	39	14	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	67	65	32	2
livestock	12	15	3	0
other	22	17	13	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Washington County

180 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 1.78 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	2	0	0	0	2
ADAMS	3	7	1	0	11
AURELIUS	3	2	0	0	5
BARLOW	1	5	3	0	9
BELPRE	3	1	1	0	5
DECATUR	3	4	0	0	7
DUNHAM	2	0	0	0	2
FAIRFIELD	7	3	0	0	10
FEARING	5	4	1	0	10
GRANDVIEW	2	2	0	0	4
LAWRENCE	0	1	0	0	1
LIBERTY	0	1	0	0	1
LUDLOW	1	1	1	0	3
MARIETTA	3	3	5	0	11
MUSKINGUM	5	1	3	0	9
NEWPORT	4	3	3	0	10
PALMER	3	3	1	0	7
SALEM	10	9	3	0	22
WARREN	3	4	0	0	7
WATERFORD	9	8	2	1	20
WATERTOWN	4	2	6	1	13
WESLEY	2	6	3	0	11

WAYNE COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED APR 1987,
MAY, NOV 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Wayne County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Wayne County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Wayne County (average 2.47 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

WAYNE COUNTY

Nitrate as N

WAYNE COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	224	68	75	31
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	140	34	37	15
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	22	3	8	2
1950-1970	52	13	15	8
after 1970	66	18	14	5
<u>average year drilled</u>	1965	1969	1963	1964
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	136	35	42	15
< 50 ft.	11	3	3	1
50 - 100 ft.	68	17	22	12
over 100 ft.	57	15	17	2
SPRINGS	3	1	3	3
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	102	111	104	80
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	165	49	60	24
yes	121	35	40	13
no	44	14	20	11
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	176	50	61	28
yes	111	29	40	18
no	65	21	21	10
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	178	54	62	28
yes	38	19	20	11
no	140	35	42	17
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	179	54	61	27
yes	112	28	41	22
no	67	26	20	5
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	201	61	74	29
livestock	75	25	35	14
other	48	14	10	3

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Wayne County

398 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 2.47 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
BAUGHMAN	6	4	5	0	15
CANAAN	16	1	1	1	19
CHESTER	25	9	10	13	57
CHIPPEWA	3	1	2	1	7
CLINTON	7	2	3	0	12
CONGRESS	13	3	1	0	17
EAST UNION	18	8	6	0	32
FRANKLIN	6	4	6	0	16
GREEN	27	10	11	7	55
KILLBUCK	4	0	1	0	5
MILTON	17	3	0	0	20
PAINT	1	1	0	0	2
PLAIN	17	5	11	2	35
SALT CREEK	5	0	1	0	6
SUGAR CREEK	19	4	5	4	32
WAYNE	25	7	9	2	43
WOOSTER	14	6	3	1	24

WILLIAMS COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED MAY 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Williams County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Williams County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Williams County (average 0.10 mg/L)

158 wells tested

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

16,166 wells tested

Number of wells registered by county

WILLIAMS COUNTY

Nitrate as N

WILLIAMS COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	156	0	2	0
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	81	0	0	0
1800's	2	0	0	0
1900-1949	7	0	0	0
1950-1970	31	0	0	0
after 1970	41	0	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1966	0	0	0
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	87	0	1	0
< 50 ft.	8	0	1	0
50 - 100 ft.	56	0	0	0
over 100 ft.	23	0	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	87	0	30	0
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	124	0	2	0
yes	75	0	0	0
no	49	0	2	0
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	126	0	2	0
yes	89	0	1	0
no	37	0	1	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	132	0	2	0
yes	27	0	1	0
no	105	0	1	0
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	134	0	2	0
yes	100	0	0	0
no	34	0	2	0
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	151	0	2	0
livestock	41	0	1	0
other	29	0	0	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Williams County

158 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.10 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	1	0	0	0	1
BRADY	11	0	0	0	11
BRIDGEWATER	10	0	0	0	10
CENTER	19	0	1	0	20
FLORENCE	7	0	0	0	7
JEFFERSON	16	0	1	0	17
MADISON	7	0	0	0	7
MILL CREEK	15	0	0	0	15
NORTHWEST	3	0	0	0	3
PULASKI	25	0	0	0	25
SPRINGFIELD	1	0	0	0	1
ST. JOSEPH	20	0	0	0	20
SUPERIOR	21	0	0	0	21

WOOD COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED JANUARY 1988

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Wood County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Wood County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Wood County (average 0.99 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

WOOD COUNTY

Nitrate as N

WOOD COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	67	8	3	3
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	42	3	0	2
1800's	0	0	0	0
1900-1949	8	1	0	2
1950-1970	20	1	0	0
after 1970	14	1	0	0
<u>average year drilled</u>	1963	1958	0	1919
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	40	2	0	2
< 50 ft.	7	1	0	0
50 - 100 ft.	26	0	0	2
over 100 ft.	7	1	0	0
SPRINGS	0	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	76	91	0	80
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	57	4	1	2
yes	44	3	1	0
no	13	1	0	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	59	4	1	2
yes	44	4	1	1
no	15	0	0	1
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	60	4	1	2
yes	10	1	0	0
no	50	3	1	2
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	61	3	1	2
yes	51	2	1	1
no	10	1	0	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	66	8	1	3
livestock	1	0	0	0
other	16	5	1	0

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Wood County

81 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.99 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	3	0	0	1	4
BLOOM	5	0	0	0	5
CENTER	3	2	2	1	8
FREEDOM	1	1	0	0	2
GRAND RAPIDS	1	0	0	0	1
HENRY	1	0	0	0	1
JACKSON	3	0	0	0	3
LAKE	5	0	0	0	5
LIBERTY	2	0	0	0	2
MIDDLETON	4	0	0	0	4
MILTON	4	1	0	0	5
MONTGOMERY	3	0	0	0	3
PERRY	3	1	0	0	4
PERRYSBURG	7	1	0	0	8
PLAIN	4	0	0	0	4
PORTAGE	1	0	0	0	1
TROY	7	1	0	1	9
WASHINGTON	1	1	0	0	2
WEBSTER	7	0	1	0	8
WESTON	2	0	0	0	2

WYANDOT COUNTY

A Summary of Nitrate Concentrations in Private Wells

SAMPLES COLLECTED DECEMBER 1987

The concentrations of nitrate + nitrite-nitrogen, given in milligrams per liter (mg/L), were measured in 16,166 private wells from 76 Ohio counties. The following bar graphs indicate how Wyandot County compares with the other counties in terms of average concentration, number of wells tested, and the number of wells registered. The pie charts indicate the proportions of wells falling within four nitrate concentration ranges for Wyandot County and for all wells tested.

Average nitrate concentrations by county

Nitrate concentrations in Wyandot County (average 0.82 mg/L)

Number of wells tested by county

Nitrate concentrations in all wells tested (average 1.32 mg/L)

Number of wells registered by county

WYANDOT COUNTY

Nitrate as N

WYANDOT COUNTY
NITRATE CONCENTRATIONS IN RELATIONSHIP TO WELL CHARACTERISTICS
AS REFLECTED IN WELL-OWNER SURVEYS

WELL CHARACTERISTIC	Ranges of nitrate concentration (as nitrogen), mg/L			
	< 0.3	0.3 - < 3.0	3.0 - < 10	10
RANGE TOTALS	207	13	11	7
YEAR DRILLED SUMMARY				
total responses	104	6	6	5
1800's	1	0	0	1
1900-1949	23	0	0	0
1950-1970	31	3	2	3
after 1970	49	3	4	1
<u>average year drilled</u>	1961	1970	1972	1952
WELL DEPTH SUMMARY				
total responses (excluding springs)	117	8	6	5
< 50 ft.	15	2	0	1
50 - 100 ft.	72	4	3	3
over 100 ft.	30	2	3	1
SPRINGS	1	0	0	0
<u>average depth, ft.</u>	84	69	100	95
Does well casing extend above grade?				
total responses	186	9	8	6
yes	111	9	5	4
no	75	0	3	2
Is there a septic tank within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	190	10	8	6
yes	122	6	5	6
no	68	4	3	0
Is there a feedlot within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	191	10	8	6
yes	48	6	0	2
no	143	4	8	4
Is there cropland within 200 ft of the well?				
total responses	189	10	8	6
yes	139	7	5	5
no	50	3	3	1
What is the well used for?				
drinking water	198	11	11	6
livestock	44	3	1	3
other	68	7	4	2

Regarding the map on the facing page: Each circle represents an individual well, and is centered over the location of that well. The area of the circle is proportional to the nitrate contamination found in that well. The shading of the circle indicates the four concentration ranges shown in the key below the map.

About the concentrations:

- Less than 0.3 mg/L - Assumed to represent natural background concentrations.
- 0.31 to 3.0 mg/L - Transitional; concentrations that may or may not represent human influence.
- 3.1 to 10.0 mg/L - May indicate elevated concentrations resulting from human activities.
- More than 10.0 mg/L - Exceeds drinking water standard.

Township Summary for Wyandot County

238 wells analyzed

Average Nitrate Concentration: 0.82 mg/L

State average nitrate concentration based on 16,166 wells is 1.32 mg/L

Township	Nitrate Concentration Ranges				Total
	<0.3	0.3 - <3.0	3.0 - <10	10 or more	
(NONE GIVEN)	4	1	0	1	6
ANTRIM	19	0	0	0	19
CRANE	32	2	0	0	34
CRAWFORD	15	2	2	2	21
EDEN	12	0	1	0	13
JACKSON	8	1	1	0	10
MARSEILLES	4	0	1	0	5
MIFFLIN	17	1	1	0	19
PITT	23	2	0	0	25
RICHLAND	8	0	0	1	9
RIDGE	2	2	3	3	10
SALEM	34	2	2	0	38
SYCAMORE	9	0	0	0	9
TYMOCHTEE	20	0	0	0	20
